

VALKYRIES

D4.5 Landscape of emerging technological opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

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1. Executive Summary

This document presents the initial study of the existing landscape regarding the technological opportunities for first responders by considering a cross-border, cross-sectorial, and cross-hierarchical approach applicable to first aid actuations. In particular, the document includes the review of connected and autonomous driving enablers to support the disaster response actuation, the establishment of trusted communications for sharing operational information in a multi-domain environment, and the use of wearables for tracking and analysing both patients and emergency response staff, the setting of a mobile C&C for decision-making and the potential creation of digital twins. Finally, it incorporates several gaps identified in different UCs and the improvement for adapting these considerations to real scenarios.

This deliverable is an update of the previously submitted document D4.1 – Landscape of emerging technological opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters – VA/0. The new content with respect to the last version submitted has been highlighted in yellow for easy review and identification.

2. Identification

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3. Project Overview

3.1. VALKYRIES Project overview

Mass casualty incidents (MCI) and multiple casualty disasters, where the number of victims far exceeds local resources and capabilities, are events that overwhelm the local health system, at least for a period of time.

The response of EMS first responders to these events often reveals insufficient resources (rescue personnel, medical personnel, facilities, etc.), communication difficulties and organizational interoperability problems, which are more acute in cross-border, cross-sector and cross-hierarchical actions.

Although the EU has evolved towards a strong capacity for joint coordination and cross-sectoral cooperation between Member States, studies such as the EU Mandate M/487 to establish EU security standards reveal that the Union is not yet at a stage where responders can interconnect information management systems from different organisations to share situation assessment or automate coordinated response procedures.

Echoing these needs, the project VALKYRIES (Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated Procedures for First Aid Vehicles Deployment on European Multi-victim Disasters) aims to analyse, improve and demonstrate infrastructures, protocols and data exchange standards to increase efficiency during deployment, intervention and local/remote coordination of first aid responders in multi-casualty disasters.

The VALKYRIES project aims to explore the impact of the emerging technologies, procedures and collaboration tools for supporting the cross-sectorial actuation of the first aid responders on cross-border disasters and major crisis situations. On these grounds, VALKYRIES will develop methodologies, adaptation tactics and decision criteria for their harmonisation according to the related pan-European ecosystems.

As the SIGRUN system, to be introduced as the result of the Valkyries project, is going to be “federated”, aka acting as the interoperability layer of existing technological systems working and parametrized to support different local workflows and procedures/ regulations or cross-border agreements, a minimum common workflow and operational procedures needs to be identified in order to support its functionality as such “federated system”.

For such harmonisation, discovery of regulatory opportunities, validation and demonstration will be documented and analysed, reporting practical field notes and guidelines able to feed standardisation and regulation bodies and serving as a reference for further related integrations.

3.2. WP4 Work package overview

VALKYRIES work has been split into seven work packages (WP). Three of them (WP4, WP5 and WP6) will embrace the three core blocks of working streams will be developed in parallel:

- Technologies and equipment (KARA): WP4
- Procedures and Operations (HERJA): WP5
- Collaboration and Training (EIR): WP6

The main aim of the reference integration, SIGRUN, is to provide a real use case driven implementation that allow applying the proposed normalizations on some of the discovered technological (KARA), procedural (HERJA) and collaborative and training (EIR) opportunities.

Figure 1 – Global vision of the VALKYRIES project.

The main aim of WP4 is to deliver a harmonisation and standardisation framework capable of supporting given technological solutions, developed and real use case driven implemented for first responders by considering a cross-border, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical approach, with the following capabilities thanks to the actual digitalisation/virtualisation technologies (incl. AI-based enablers) applicable to first aid actuations: 1) the utilisation of all available equipment at disaster situations for successful actuation, with particular emphasis the health support wearable devices to monitor and analyse both patients and emergency response staff; 2) enable the establishment of trusted communications for sharing operational information in a multi-domain environment of stakeholders; 3) the setting up of a mobile C&C to put in place both operational decision-making and action planning in a coordinated way; and 4) to allow the deployment of connected and autonomous driving enablers to support the disaster response actuation.

WP4 will address the following related tasks:

- **T4.1: First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units.** This task analyses the technological opportunities for first aid response on self-driving and unmanned vehicles, then revising their related regulatory and normalization gaps. From them a roadmap towards their adoption by EU first aid responders will be proposed. A subset of the investigated opportunities will be selected for fitting the end-user requirements of the VALKYRIES reference integration (SIGRUN). Land-based drones (rover) will also be

exercised to put into operation in the demonstration use cases (tasks T7.5, T7.6, T7.7 and T7.8), to prove how in disaster scenarios we can leverage

- **T4.2: Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals.** The growing landscape of trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals to enhance existing EU capabilities for first aid responses to be analysed looking for technological opportunities. The main gaps, challenges and regulatory barriers for their adoption will be reviewed, resulting in a set of harmonization opportunities and a roadmap for integration into the EU Security Market. A subset of the identified technological opportunities will be selected and harmonized to meet requirements of the VALKYRIES reference integration. In particular, the Consortium will aim to design and develop a framework capable of establishing reliable and trustworthy communication links for information sharing between the different actors in disaster situations. Many parameters will be considered for computing the trust score between parties, where it will be possible to take into consideration, for example, the underlying technology in communications being used (e.g., Bluetooth/Wi-Fi/4G/5G), the type of assets, the impact when conducting its emergency tasks, list (and satisfaction) of previous actuations.
- **Task T4.3: Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies.** The starting point will be an analysis of the state of the art of the mobile Command, Control & Communication Information Systems (C3ISR) on which the first responders in emergency situations rely, to identify the opportunities for technological improvement of these systems. In a second step, the main barriers and challenges in the incorporation of these technologies will be identified, which will translate into a definition of requirements for the adoption and subsequent standardized and harmonic implementation of the potential improvements in the systems that will be used by the First Responders of the VALKYRIES Consortium as part of the reference integration. A map of related harmonization opportunities will be generated and a roadmap for their technological adoption and normalization will be suggested. A subset of the discovered related technical opportunities will be harmonized to serve to the VALKYRIES reference integration (SIGRUN), resulting in guidelines and field notes for supporting further associated actions.
- **Task 4.4: The digitalisation on first aid actuations.** Task T4.4 will study the role of the emerging digitalization paradigm, which is leading to advanced modelling, virtualization and simulation capabilities to be applied by First Response teams. The task will review and identify potential improvements that can be incorporated considering new technological opportunities for digitisation to the sector. In this line, technologies such as modelling and simulation aggregation, BIM modelling and static digitization, Digital Twin Instances (DTI) and their interrelationship as Digital Twins Aggregated (DTA) and Portable Digital Twins (EDT) will be reviewed looking for technological opportunities. The task covers the analyses of their technological regulatory and harmonization gaps, the definition of a potential roadmap for adoption/ normalization, and the application of the VALKYRIES harmonization in a subset of them resulting in guidelines for later related actions.

- **Task T4.5: Instrumentation and health support wearable devices.** The work to be undertaken in this task will be the study and identification of technologies that can have a positive impact on this type of device, and which contribute to mapping the operational environment and improve the efficiency of response logistics while supporting the operation of the equipment. This first study of state of the art will be followed by the identification of legal barriers and challenges for the definition of a common and standard adoption framework at the European level. Among all the technologies studied (spatial planning, infrastructure and deployed unit location, logistic planning, search and rescue, etc.) those that meet the criteria defined in the standardization framework will be selected and adapted as part of the VALKYRIES reference integration, resulting in guidelines and fieldnotes for supporting further harmonization.

4. Introduction

4.1. Objective

As described in the project's harmonisation framework document (D2.5), the defined VALKYRIES harmonisation process has three main stages, as shown in the figure below:

Figure 2 - VALKYRIES harmonisation process

The first stage of the harmonisation process is the description and analysis of the existing state-of-the-art.

The aim of this document is to complete this first stage by exploring new opportunities through an analysis of the existing landscape considering a cross-border, cross-sectoral and cross-hierarchical situation in first aid response.

4.2. Scope

D4.1 (Landscape of emerging technological opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters) will provide a description of the emerging technological opportunities identified and assessed during the working streams conducted at T4.1, T4.2, T4.3, T4.4 and T4.5, fulfilling the following established base requirements:

Requirement	Name	Description	Details	Rationale
REQ_BASE_T4.1_1	First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units	VALKYRIES SHALL analyse the technological opportunities for first aid response on self-driving and unmanned vehicles, then revise their related regulatory and	Race a roadmap towards an adoption of such technological opportunities, by EU first aid responders SHALL be proposed. A subset of the investigated opportunities SHALL be selected for fitting the end-user requirements of the VALKYRIES reference integration (SIGRUN). In particular, land-based drones (rover) SHALL also be	The analysis MAY be extended to the entire EU scope, and SHOULD pay particular attention to the territories involved in the demonstrators (use cases)

Requirement	Name	Description	Details	Rationale
		normalization gaps.	exercised to put into operation in the demonstration use cases (tasks T7.5, T7.6, T7.7 and T7.8), to prove how in disaster scenarios we MAY leverage the exploitation of autonomous units to cover the tasks usually conducted by first aid responder (human) staff. In this context, drones MAY also be used to collect information in all areas included in VALKYRIES.	
REQ_BASE_T4.1_2	Self-driving and unmanned vehicles	VALKYRIES SHALL analyse the technological opportunities for first aid response on self-driving and unmanned vehicles.	Unmanned vehicles can deliver a variety of services to first and responders, the importance is to map what services is wanted by the responders and what services the vehicle systems can provide. And by this make a gap analyses	In order to make a road map for the implementation of new technology, it is vital of have a total picture of requirements, opportunities and limitations

Requirement	Name	Description	Details	Rationale
REQ_BASE_T4.1_3	Categorisation of the different systems	VALKYRIES SHALL categorize the different system in accordance with proposed plan for environment	Unmanned vehicles have a primary environment they are designed to operate in (e.g., Air, ground, surface, subsurface.) This Categorisation will be used to compare the systems possibilities with the different regulations in force throughout Europe	In order to make a road map for the implementation of new technology, it is vital of have a total picture of requirements, opportunities and limitations
REQ_BASE_T4.1_4	Type of assistance	VALKYRIES SHALL categorize the different system in accordance with category	All rescue operations consist of several different phases some in sequence and some parallel (surveillance and area clearance, first-responder assistance, command&control assistance etc.). The task is to map what type of assistance different unmanned vehicles can give to the different phases and compare this with the regulations in force for rescue operation. The aim is to find gaps between todays regulations and new regulations where unmanned vehicles is a part of it	In order to make a road map for the implementation of new technology, it is vital of have a total picture of requirements, opportunities and limitations

Requirement	Name	Description	Details	Rationale
REQ_BASE_T4.1_5	Information gathering	VALKYRIES SHALL map the end-users requirements and needs for information, data, and communication in a rescue situation	The first-responders have a variety of needs and requirements when it comes to information gathering, - interpretation and - distribution. The end-users needs will be mapped and compared with the systems possibilities and limitations	To familiarize first aid responders with the possibilities an user friendly and simple demonstration will be given during the different user cases.
REQ_BASE_T4.1_6	Information presentation	VALKYRIES SHALL present the information to end-users.	Regardless of the systems services, complexity and use a low-tech flow of information to end-users is of paramount importance. The task will look into the design of decision support system and suggest a common standard for how end-users will send and receive data regardless of language, technological systems available, skills and the environment the first responders are a part of.	To familiarize first aid responders with the possibilities a user friendly and simple demonstration will be given during the different user cases.

Requirement	Name	Description	Details	Rationale
REQ_BASE_T4.2_1	Trusted communication of end-user terminals with the infrastructure	The growing landscape of trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals to enhance existing EU capabilities for first aid responses MUST be analysed looking for technological opportunities.	The main gaps, challenges and regulatory barriers for their adoption MUST be reviewed, resulting in a set of harmonization opportunities and a roadmap for integration into the EU Security Market. A subset of the identified technological opportunities SHALL be selected and harmonised to meet requirements of the VALKYRIES reference integration.	
REQ_BASE_T4.2_2	Framework for secure and trusted communications	The framework MUST be capable of communicating in a secure and trusted fashion based on current harmonisation opportunities.	The designed framework SHOULD consider regulatory gaps, challenges and opportunities aiming to harmonize communication capabilities. It SHOULD consider currently used communication technologies (e.g. TETRA) and prospecting ones (such as Bluetooth/Wi-Fi/4G/5G) to evaluate harmonization opportunities.	

Requirement	Name	Description	Details	Rationale
REQ_BASE_T4.3_1	Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technology improvements	A map of related harmonisation opportunities SHALL be generated and a roadmap for their technological adoption and normalisation SHALL be suggested.	Roadmap SHALL suggest a subset of harmonisation technical opportunities to serve to the VALKYRIES reference integration (SIGRUN).	
REQ_BASE_T4.3_2	Preliminary C3ISR analysis	State of the art analysis SHALL be done about the current Command, Control & Communication Information Systems Reconnaissance (C3ISR)	An improvement study SHALL be carried out to find technological improvements to the support systems for the first responders.	
REQ_BASE_T4.3_3	Recognition of Technological gaps	Main barriers and challenges in the incorporation of these technologies SHALL be detected	It SHALL be identifying the pros and cons about future implementation issues as a part of the reference integration for the adoption and subsequent standardized and harmonic implementation for first responders. Effective Communication Technology	

Requirement	Name	Description	Details	Rationale
REQ_BASE_T4.3_4	Related harmonisation opportunities Map	Map of related harmonisation opportunities are RECOMMENDED to be generated resulting in guidelines and field notes for supporting further associated actions.	As a preliminary stage of the VALKYRIES project, the large ecosystem of emerging opportunities for enhancing the first aid actuation in disaster situations will be surveyed, analysed and categorized resulting in an ontological map of the existing state-of-the-art and beyond enablers, and the pros/cons of their adoption.	
REQ_BASE_T4.3_5	Roadmap for their technological adoption and normalisation	Roadmap SHOULD be created to define their technological adoptions to get the major VALKYRIES milestones. Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters	VALKYRIES SHOULD bring roadmaps for their mitigation and prompting the adoption of the disruptive solutions on the first aid response markets. VALKYRIES will also bring a roadmap of expertise landscaping and actual trends in the employment of advanced technologies, procedures, and tactics.	

Requirement	Name	Description	Details	Rationale
REQ_BASE_T4.4_1	Technological timelines	Potential improvements MAY be incorporated considering new technological opportunities for digitisation	In this line, VALKIRYES MAY apply technologies such as modelling and simulation aggregation, BIM modelling and static digitization, Digital Twin Instance (DTI) and their interrelationship as Digital Twins Aggregated (DTA) and Portable Digital Twins (EDT). In this context, potential contributions of novel technological approaches like introducing social media intelligence to improve the EMS preparedness, taking advantage of AI-based predictive Big Data analytics for guiding anticipatory actions, bringing auxiliary unmanned vehicles and autonomous driving capabilities to the conventional first aid scenarios, exploring the potential of the emerging communication paradigms, digitalisation/virtualisation; inherently demand a review of their linked operational procedures, education, training and cross-sectional collaboration.	Carry out task reviews and identify potential technological improvements RECOMMEND study the role of the emerging digitalization paradigm.

Requirement	Name	Description	Details	Rationale
REQ_BASE_T4.4_2	Technological harmonisation opportunities	MUST be identified and assess of the regulatory, certification and standardisation needs and gaps on the existing and emerging technologies for supporting first aid responses.	The requirement SHALL covers the analyses of their technological regulatory and harmonisation gaps, the definition of a potential roadmap for adoption/normalisation, and the application of the VALKYRIES harmonization in a subset of them resulting in guidelines for later related actions.	
REQ_BASE_T4.5_1	Study of opportunities for wearables technologies	Analysis of the state of the art in a categorized manner among the most promising technological alternatives. The analysis SHALL ensure compatibility with the operational environment.	The work to be undertaken in this task MUST be the study and identification of technologies that MAY have a positive impact on this type of device, and which contribute to mapping the operational environment and improve the efficiency of response logistics while supporting the operation of the equipment, aiming to improve human-computer interaction.	

Requirement	Name	Description	Details	Rationale
REQ_BASE_T4.5_2	Analysis of legal terms	Review the legal terms based on the communications and information transmitted between the different technologies. The review SHALL indicate the legal impact at the European level that may occur.	Identification of legal barriers and challenges for the definition of a common and standard adoption framework at the European level.	
REQ_BASE_T4.5_3	Categorization, selection and applicability of technologies within the framework	Selection of the most promising technologies with a high possibility of applicability in the project and adapting them to the requirements of the deployed environment.	Among all the technologies studied (spatial planning, infrastructure and deployed unit location, logistic planning, search and rescue, etc.) those that meet the criteria defined in the standardization framework MUST be selected and adapted as part of the VALKYRIES reference integration, resulting in guidelines and fieldnotes for supporting further harmonization.	

Table 1 - D4.1 Requirements

4.3. Methodology

This first stage by exploring opportunities thought an analysis of the existing *landscape of emerging technological opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters* has followed this methodology:

1. Define the scope of the landscape and the document.

2. Divide the analysis into areas of knowledge limited by the scope of the tasks.
3. Identify the state of the art of each of the areas. Based on:
 - Personal experience
 - Scientific studies
 - Reference standards and guidance
 - Expert consultation
 - etc.

There is a special methodology section on consultation strategy (see point 4.4).

4. Filter the information on the basis on:
 - The scope of the task
 - Focused mainly on VALKYRIES use cases and
 - Focused mainly on the countries involved.
5. Identify future areas of improvement, where technologies are moving forward and what the next steps in these areas will be.
6. Pre-identify the needs of end-users and responders.
7. Pre identify opportunities for improvement
8. identifying legal barriers that may affect the development of these opportunities
9. Finally, develop conclusions to outline the next steps in terms of opportunities in each of the areas.

4.4. Consultation strategy

The VALKYRIES project is committed in analysing, improving, and developing infrastructures, protocols and raising data exchange standardisation and harmonisation tactics able to increase the effectiveness and interoperability in emergency situations, such as those prevailing in operation of first aid vehicles or cross-frontier disaster response.

Three work streams will be developed in the project: First Responder Technologies and Equipment (KARA), First Responder Procedures and Operation (HERJA), and First Responder Collaboration and Training (EIR).

According to the general strategy of the VALKYRIES project, contained in the VALKYRIES D1.7 Consultation strategy D1.7, a common consultation strategy was designed for those 3 work streams of the project.

4.4.1. Objectives and motivation of the WP4 consultation

- **Motivation:** transversely to the different work packages outlined in the project, acquiring the vision from external experts plays a pivotal role, as it will lead to drive the harmonization of protocols and technologies consistently with the project objectives.
- **Objective:** generation of a report describing the emerging technological opportunities identified and assessed regarding the work streams.

4.4.2. Tools and methods

Questionnaire distributed among technical and operational managers of different EU emergency services.

Three questionnaires were defined by WP4, WP5 and WP6 researchers, oriented respectively to each of the project's work streams:

- WP4 (KARA): Technologies and Equipment for first aid responders
- WP5 (HERJA): Procedures and Operation for first aid responders
- WP6 (EIR): Collaboration and Training for first aid responders

4.4.3. Targeted WP4 questionnaire stakeholders

- First round: first responders' partners of the consortium of the EAB and of linked projects. These results will be included, as an approximation of the reality at EU level, in the first draft of deliverable D4.1.
- Second round: emergency services potentially involved in responding to mass casualty incidents or disasters in the EU. Each Emergency Service participating in the study would provide a single response to the WP4 questionnaire. These results, more comprehensive and representative of the reality at EU level, will be included in the final version of deliverable D4.5.

4.4.4. Facilitators

Valkyries project researchers (emergency services contact and questionnaire distribution).

4.4.5. Timing

Distribution and completion of the questionnaire: 27 May to 6 June 2022.

4.4.6. Data storage

The collected data will be cloud-stored in the general repository of the project. After the project, the report will be stored in the project official website to be used upon request for future actions related to the project objectives.

4.4.7. Data analysis

The objective assessment will be made based on the information gathered from the consulted Emergency Services.

The data will be analysed and evaluated by the VALKYRIES tasks leaders in order to extract policy and recommendations on the possible exploitation of VALKYRIES solution.

The results will always be presented in an aggregated form, so that it will not be possible to identify the individual responses of each service.

4.4.8. Reporting

The results will be accessible for:

- VALKYRIES researchers throughout the project life cycle.
- Reporting back to the Emergency Services consulted (if they are interested).
- Other related projects and third parties upon request it once the project is finished, under the terms established in the project's intellectual property agreement of VALKYRIES' s project.

5. Tasks chapters

5.1. First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units

5.1.1. Introduction

There are a large number of remotely controlled or autonomous units available ranging from the small private flying drones, remotely controlled toys to flying war drones, cargo ships and automatic trains. All of these unit could have a practical application in different types of SAR operations, but they are not necessarily a good choice. I this chapter we will go through some of the types and categories that are available in one or another way. We will cover all types such as flying, ground moving, surface (Water) and sub-surface drones. At USN we have worked on maritime drones both surface and sub-surface for more than 15 years. During the last years we have also taken up activities on flying drones. Finally, we have also carried out some experiments with ground moving rovers (drones). Our closest University in Norway, NMBU, have developed these types of rovers for agricultural applications in a hilly farmland.

5.1.1.1. What is an unmanned vehicle?

An unmanned, remotely controlled or autonomous vehicle can be (are often) categorized by the physical environment where it operates such as air, solid ground or water. In table 1 we have tried to define some groups and give a very simple description of the unit.

Name	Shortening	Propulsion system	Communication	Comments
Unmanned aerial vehicle	UAV	Quadcopter	Radio	Easy to operate. Quick Low payload Sensitive to weather
		Rotorcrafts		
		Fixed wing		
Unmanned ground vehicle	UGV	Moving by belts	Radio	Require more skill to operate Slow Can carry a significant payload Less weather sensitivity
		Moving by wheels		
		Moving by pods		
Unmanned surface vehicles	USV	Sail/wind	Radio	Easy to operate Medium speed Medium payload Some sensitivity to weather conditions
		Propulsion		
		Water jet		
Unmanned under water vehicles	UUV/AUV	Propulsion	Acoustics	Require more skill to operate Relatively slow Reasonable payload Low sensitivity to weather conditions

Table 2 - Types of unmanned vehicles

5.1.1.2. Unmanned aerial vehicles-UAV

Figure 3 - Quadcopter

Figure 4 - Helicopter

Figure 5 - Fixed Wing

This includes all vehicles using air as the transport area. They are often named drones or flying drones. The most common unit in private and non-military operation are Quadcopters. They are easy to control and well suited for area mapping/imaging and can also carry a number of sensors to measure temperature, pick up sound, do chemical analysis and so on as long as the equipment is limited in weight. Quadcopter and other smaller units are sensitive to wind and other weather conditions. Also varying temperature as above a forest fire may give problems. Fixed wing units can normally carry most load and are less sensitive to the environmental conditions. Flying time may also be an issue since the battery has to be carried. Some details on performance are given in the table 2 and 3.

At USN we are running or participating in three different projects beside VALKYRIE, aimed at carrying post and goods in urban areas, surveying farms and transporting medical equipment and samples between hospitals. There will be a clear synergy between the projects.

Group:	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5
Size:	Small	Medium	Large	Larger	Largest
Max take-off wt (lb):	< 20	> 20 & < 55	> 55 & < 1320	> 1320	> 1320
Operating altitude (ft):	< 1,200	< 3,500	< 18,000	< 18,000	> 18,000

Group:	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5
Speed (kn):	< 100	< 250	< 250	Any speed	Any speed

Table 3 - Unmanned vehicles - performance

Category:	Very close range UAVs	Close range UAVs	Short range UAVs	Medium range UAVs	Long range UAVs
Range (km):	< 5	> 5 & < 50	> 50 & < 150	> 150 & < 650	> 650
Endurance (hr):	0.5 – 0.75	1 – 6	8 – 12	12 – 36 or 48	> 36 or 48

Table 4 - Unmanned vehicles – range and endurance

5.1.1.3. Unmanned ground vehicle-UGV

Figure 6 - Pods

Figure 7 - Wheels

Figure 8 - Belts

This group is also quite large and could include everything from remotely controlled toys to advanced equipment used in military operations and farming. Some units are already in use in SAR operations and some others are tested for such applications. Small units are used for mapping of buildings and other complicated structures where there is a high risk of using people. UGV's will have some of the same issues regarding weather conditions, heat and so on. They are also quite slow and can cover smaller areas than a flying drone.

They can be equipped with most of the same equipment as a flying drone. They are also in some cases able to carry more load than the flying drones (depend on size).

At USN we have tested two different UGV's suitable of operating in rough terrain. Both units have wheels and can adapt to the terrain to avoid turning over. They are slow but securely in a forest area. More details will hopefully come later.

5.1.1.4. Unmanned surface vehicles-USV

Figure 9 - Survey Drone

Figure 10 - Different test drones

Figure 11 - Small Survey Drone

USN's or sea drones have been in use for a number of years in mapping and surveillance at sea. They are typically from about 10 meters long to small vessels less than a meter long. At USN we have worked on this type of drones for approximately 15 years and the drones have been used in application like mapping and characterization of pollution and oil spill, picking plastics, mapping sea bed and similar operations. We have so far not tested units on searching for people. A combination of a flying drone and a sea drone may be a good solution in establishing a good

situation awareness at sea. Small sea drones may have issues when operation in tough weather since they are relatively sensitive to larger waves.

In the local sea rescue training center, they also have a small R&D unit. They work on different medical and technical topics. One of the present projects is a remotely controlled “lifesaving floating device” that can pick up people that are conscious.

We are looking on a concept where a larger unmanned mother ship approaches an accident. Close to the accidents smaller flying or sea going drones can be launched and enter into the accident area to establish a good situation awareness. The mother ship will also act as a charging unit and may also pick up larger volume of data.

5.1.1.5. Unmanned under water vehicles-AUV

Figure 12 - Search AUV

Figure 13 - Mapping AUV

This is a smaller group of unmanned vehicles, but they have been in use for a relatively long period of time in survey missions under water. They are used in both private, civilian, and military operations. They are not necessarily important in early-stage SAR operation but may play an important part in searching drowned people, pollution, or special items like operation recorders.

5.1.1.6. Final remarks

We will make more detailed reports on each group of vehicles and have started with flying drones.

5.1.1.7. *Common rules and regulation for the EU*

- Since January 2021 all countries in the EU have the same rules and regulations for operating drones (technical term: Remote Piloted Aircraft System, RPAS)
- It is the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) that sets the regulations for use of RPAS in the EU
- So far, the regulations focus almost exclusively on drones with a human pilot. Further regulations for autonomous systems will be developed in the near future.

5.1.1.8. *Piloted, automatic and autonomous*

- Piloted: Drones are being controlled by a human pilot.
- Automatic: Drones follow a pre-planned flight plan and execute the plan without human intervention. A human pilot must be able to intervene in case of emergency/failure.
- Autonomous: Drones make autonomous decisions about how and where to fly. Regulations are weak at the moment. Human pilot must be able to intervene in case of emergency/failure. Regulations seems to be weak at the moment.

EASA defines three categories for drone operations:

1. Open
2. Specific
3. Certified

Open

- Low risk operations
- No authorization required, but must self-register
- Divided into 3 subcategories:
 - A1 max 250 g
 - A2 max 2.0 kg
 - A3 max 25 kg
- Pilots must pass test
- VLOS only (spotter ok)

Specific

- Medium risk
- Requires authorisation from National Aviation Authority
- Proper risk assessment (SORA or similar)

Certified

- High risk e.g. transport of humans in urban environment
- Heavy machines with high power
- Pilot on board or off board
- Requires authorisation from National Aviation Authority

5.1.1.9. *Operational Manual*

1. Concepts of operation

- The con ops document will describe all operations that the organisation will perform.
 - It will also outline the limits of operations, e.g. not flying in darkness, no fly zones (embassies, prisons etc.), necessary permissions (e.g. from land owner).
 - The document will outline how and where to dump/crash drone in case of emergency.
 - In Norway, other cameras than RGB visual requires explicit permission from Norwegian National Security Authority (NSM)
2. Quality assurance system
- To ensure the safety for all drone operations, the quality assurance system has as its main role to ensure that there are proper routines for
 - Training pilots
 - Maintaining documentation and documents
 - Dealing with deviations
 - Storing flight logs and other information relevant for improving operation quality
 - Continuous learning from operations and improving operations
3. Risk assessment
- The risk assessment (model) serves the purpose of identifying potential hazards that may occur during an operation. The risk assessment model will help us prepare mitigating actions before accidents occur.
4. Training
- Pilots need to be properly trained before they can take part in a mission. This subsection of the OM will document what training is required, e.g.
 - Notam and AIP(Aeronautical publication, like limitations in airspace)
 - How to reserve airspace
 - Coordination of pilot and other relevant personnel
 - Airmanship
 - Knowing the limitations on the drones (due to weather et cetera)
5. Emergency procedures
- The OM must contain a section on emergency procedures, and pilots must be trained in the procedures. Situations that may arise are:
 - Fire
 - Loss of power of one or several motors
 - Necessary to trigger kill switch
6. Check lists
- Before starting an operation, we must ensure that:
 - Drone is fully functioning, no damages to propellers, batteries are charged etc.
 - The airspace is cleared for drone operations
 - GNSS/GPS is fully available
-

- Permissions are ok
- It may be useful to have several lists
 - Before flight, during flight, after flight and emergency
- 7. Proof of insurance
 - Copy of insurance document should always be present.
- 8. Packing list
 - Before going to an operation, use packing lists so ensure that all parts are taken along.
 - Drone equipment like radio controller, batteries, propellers, power supplies
 - Tools
 - HMS equipment. Helmet, glasses etc
- 9. Flight logs
 - The flight log will preserve important information about the flights
 - Duration (important for maintenance cycles)
 - Battery status at the end of operation
 - Pilot

5.1.2. State of the art analysis

A comprehensive literature review is conducted with focus on the first responders' possibilities to use new technology including supportive autonomous units to build a common operational picture (COP) to heighten the situational awareness for the whole team. This will among other improve the effectiveness of the relief operations with the available assets, heighten the safety of participating personnel and relieve personnel of some tasks, making them available for other tasks.

Also, the command level will benefit from the use of autonomous units since their overall situational awareness will improve and the allocation of available resources will be more accurate. The information needed for the C² centre is of vital importance for them to build a common operational picture, this necessitates first responders to feed information back to the C² as more advance systems becomes available the demand for first responders to give information increases. The solution is to primarily use systems that can gather, sort and feed information back to C² without an active part of the first responders. Example the use of head mounted camera feeding video without the first responders needing to actively take photos or videos.

Another challenge is the first responders' ability, competence, and time to use new and sometimes advanced technology in their emergency response training and operations. It is time-consuming to learn and maintain the needed competence to use advance systems and several sources point at this as one of the main challenges with autonomous units.

The use of information gathered from these supportive autonomous units must be accompanied with software solutions assisting in sorting, analysing, and presenting information in order to reduce the risk of information overload.

5.1.3. Comparative tables (summarizing the SotA analysis vs the required features / identified requirements)

System assisting	Tools	Action
Communication platforms	UAV and UGV	Build Ad hoc communication network for voice and data transfer to secure common operation picture and situational awareness
Tracking of personnel involved in operation	Infrastructure based: Id tag, RFID, RF detection (e.g., mobile phones, Wi-Fi, BLE) Device based: GNSS-data reported via devices	Be able to track personnel involved in the operation for optimizing resource management, enhance personnel safety and build track history.
Navigation and communication in congested areas and closed spaces	Id tag, UAV/UGV, tablet	Assist personnel with navigation, area search, and secure comms reliability within team and back to command centre
Support in Situational awareness	UAV, UGV, USV Field sensors (e.g., IoT) Human reports Satellite imagery	Search areas with all available sensors to heighten the situational awareness for all involved personnel
Situation awareness software support	Software, machine learning, AI etc	To assist in the filtering of information to hinder information overload.
Build advanced map with real time information	UAV, UGV, USV. CCTVs, documents, drawing	Use all available information to build a 3D model of the disaster area.
Collect, sort and present data from external sources	Comms systems, internet, telephones, television. Weather systems	Use information to enhance the overall situational awareness.
Medical vehicles and their equipment - Road ambulances	UNE-EN 1789:2021 / / CEN EN 1789:2020	Meet the requirements about design, testing, performance and equipping of road ambulances used for the transport, monitoring, treatment and care of patients.
Patient handling equipment used in road ambulances	UNE EN 1865	Set of standards whose define the minimum requirements of handling equipment used in road ambulances (general stretcher systems and patient handling equipment, power assisted stretcher, heavy duty stretcher,

System assisting	Tools	Action
		foldable patient transfer chair, stretcher support)
Firefighting and rescue service vehicles	EN 1846	Set of three standards (Nomenclature and designation, Common requirements - Safety and performance, permanently installed equipment - Safety and performance)
Firefighting and rescue services vehicles and equipment	CEN/TS 15989:2015	Graphical symbols for control elements and displays and for markings

Table 5 - Comparative table related unmanned vehicles

5.1.4. Technical opportunities identified

5.1.4.1. Build ad hoc communication grids

When a large disaster occurs, there is a high probability that communication systems will be off grid due to damage to antennas, servers or power systems. If this is not the case, there is a constant imbalance between the supply of communication systems and the demand for them. Incomplete damage to any network element reduces supply. The influx of emergency teams and personnel in need of communication considerably increases the demand. In some cases, the interveners themselves may deliberately cause the network to be disconnected if there are doubts about the criminal use of the network (e.g. terrorist attacks on the Madrid regional trains). In order for the first responders to communicate with each other and team leaders and receive and deliver data to command posts an ad hoc communication microgrid must be set up. The use of rapid deployable communications stations complemented by unmanned vehicles (aerial, ground) can provide radio links and a data grid.

Parameters such as control, network topology need to be taken into account so that the proper formation of ad hoc microgrid to be established in such cases. Such a system can also provide communication with first responders inside buildings, caves and other closed environments.

5.1.4.2. Tracking of personnel

A common problem in all disaster area operations is tracking of personnel. By using a blockchain based tag system on emergency response personnel and vehicles the command centre can have live updated information of where they are physically. This information has several possible benefits, such as area monitoring for better understanding of what areas have been actually searched (historic track data), to provide assistance to personnel in congested areas or inside buildings in order to find quickest and/or safest way to injured people for medical aid and evacuation or to get them to safe areas if the situation deteriorate.

Personnel monitoring, if geographical location information can be accompanied by passive measurement and transmission of physiological data, can also be used for the detection of accidents among rescue personnel, for locating rescuers during emergency evacuations (e.g., during aftershocks in earthquakes) for the assessment of first responders' fatigue to evaluate breaks or relays, etc.

The same system can also be used to keep track of victims and survivors that are found during any given use case. It should be taken into consideration that for each use case a different methodology should be followed and become adaptable depending on the conditions and multiple variables that may occur during those cases.

5.1.4.3. Build common Operational Picture for situational awareness

Figure 14 - Common operational flow

Suggest referring a wide number of input sources, not just UxVs. Refer sensors (IoT, ground), HUMINT, satellite, etc. Autonomous units are ideal to gather data for the common operational picture, by employing aerial, surface and ground driven units the command structure will receive updated information on the situation, and they can deploy units to investigate high interest areas or to give a continuous feed from key areas. Fixed wing drones can cover larger areas to scan for other/further incidents/victims and provide a better scope of the situation to the Command Units.

High altitude autonomous platforms (HAAPS) systems (HAAPS) can also provide better rural coverage and large scale areas, Earth observation and mapping to conduct preliminary assessment of the area of interest or to auxiliary communications coverage, acting as a relay station of the areas. Such UAV's communication channels must be secured to their ground control stations.

5.1.4.4. Conduct search and relief missions

Aerial autonomous units is ideal to conduct search and mapping of large areas. Equipped with different sensors they can pick up different signs like heat signatures to locate missing people, SAR sensors to spot oil spills in the sea, collect LRF data for earthquake 3D scenario analysis, etc Combined with logistic drones and rovers, the system can send different equipment like communication, food or first aid to the people assist them until rescue personnel can arrive.

Based on the use case/conditions of the area, specific aerial autonomous units should be considered for further use. Units that can carry a specific amount of weight and capabilities depending on the use cases that going to be deployed.

Currently a combination of different aerial unmanned platforms systems are already in use for multiple search and relief missions, EMSA and UK government use fixed wing UAVs to perform maritime SAR operations. VTOL UAVs are also a good aid to perform coastal inspection SAR

operations to spot potential victims near cliffs, Mountain's search operations looking for missing people, etc. These assets provide not only real-time, allowing C2 systems and commanders to have a better view of the operational field, follow specific events which enables real-time coordination, better decision support data, and may other features.

SAR operations are critically time sensitive and life threatening to victims, the combination and timely available of multiple data is of the utmost importance, that requires proper planning. Valkyries provides the means to Integrate multiple and different UAV systems in a federated solution and improve the effectiveness and agility of the operations.

5.1.5. Analysis of T4.1 questionnaire

Regarding task 4.1, the questionnaire asked for the following key aspects:

The following table presents the most common answers for each one of the questions presented:

	Result
Describe your most common tasks as a first responder	46% Paramedics 42 %Search & Rescue 12% Firefighter
In transport – towards a mission – describe how you receive information.	Most: Written txt Second: Speech
During operation as a first responder – Describe how you receive information	Most Speech. Second: Written txt
How will you prefer to receive critical personal safety information during crisis (scale 5 -1 with 5 preferred)	Alarm (average/Standard Deviation) Visual, Sound and vibration: 4,33 / 0,89 Alarm sound: 4,23 / 1,17 Visual sign on maps: 4,08 / 0,76 Verbal instructions: 3,75 / 0,97 Colours on maps: 3,55 / 0,99 Buzzing, vibration 2,67 / 1,55
In operation – what communication technologies is in use? Drones? Pictures? Text? Verbal?	In response vehicles: Radio: 100 % Digital Maps: 70 % Verbal information: 55 % Misc other sources: 26 % On response site: Radio: 93 % Verbal information: 52 % Digital Maps: 33 % Misc other sources: 30 %
Most common used way of receiving information.	Underway to response site: Hearing 56% / Visual 44 % On response site: Hearing 56 % / Visual 44%
Preferred information about own safety	Where it is safe: 41 % Where it is dangerous: 59 %

	Result
Importance of different subject information (scale 5-1 5 high importance)	Information of danger areas: 4,48 / 0,83
	Information of instability: 4,46 / 0,80
	Sending my position: 4,37 / 0,91
	Information of future threats: 4,28 / 0,78
	Direction to safe areas: 4,26 / 1,14
	Medical / first aid 4,20 / 1,02
	Information on ongoing fires 3,79 / 1,44
	Information of toxic gazes: 3,78 / 1,56
	Procedures / manuals 3,78 / 1,20

Table 6 - Results obtained for Task 4.1.

Perception of risk. The willingness to find practical solutions on the one hand, in meetings with strict regulation increases the need of shared situation awareness led to increased risk.

Emergency organizations can be seen as different entities when they collaborate in rescue operations. Professional first responders train their basic routines daily. Being detailed, small changes in procedures takes place continuously.

Such tedious details are the way of flight security. Minimal changes in procedures are the norm. This represents a challenge in the collaboration with volunteering experts. It can create unforeseen problems and dangerous situations.

The experience forms the first responders was that technology do not play a central part in their operations. The planning skills, craftsmanship, and experience within the group secures the implementation of a rescue plan and the success of the performance. Even though new technology would be nice it is still the basic training and the experiences that is vital.

5.2. Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals

5.2.1. Introduction

Nowadays, **emergency** situations involve enormous material and personal losses, causing significant problems. Unpredictability and uncertainty are some of the primary triggers for this type of situation. **Pandemics, natural or even war** become disasters when they exceed a limit of normality. The effects of these events can be amplified by poor resource planning, such as the lack of security or control measures, emergency plans and warning systems that can increase the options for predicting their occurrence or controlling their progress once they have occurred.

Information is the most precious and important raw material in an emergency, essential during the decision-making process. It is vital to ensure a timely, and appropriate response to people affected by a disaster or emergency. Data is as essential in damage assessment, coordination, and strategic planning once an event has occurred as it predicts the possible occurrence of the event. In this sense, it is essential to collect and obtain as much data as possible on the environment and resources to try to combat and cope with such situations by anticipating or forecasting factors and events. Having data available quickly and reliably can lead to a better knowledge of the current and real state of an emergency, which can imply a better strategic organisation of the available resources by the bodies in charge of coordinating emergencies and security (CECOES 1-1-2, Fire Brigade, etc.), better anticipation of the problem and less waste of resources, both material and personal.

In this way, the primary responsibility of communication technologies is the reliable transmission of information gathered during the disaster of multiple victims between the different participants, thus favouring that, given the integration of this system in the organisms linked to the strategic management of emergencies, the possibilities of increasing the chances of:

- To reduce the response time in emergencies, thus reducing personal and material losses
- To favour the strategic management of the personnel and resources available at the site where an emergency has occurred by having up-to-date information

It should be taken into consideration that, in disasters of greater magnitude or extent, communications networks may be part of the initial damage, and substantially compromise the possibility of employing the solutions established for information gathering and exchange.

It is therefore important to also focus part of the efforts on establishing solutions that allow for some recording and exchange of information to ensure adequate interoperability also in these extreme cases.

5.2.2. Use cases overview

One of the objectives of the Valkyries project is to analyse and ensure the trusted communication infrastructure and end-user terminals. In the project, there are 4 Use Cases which are very different. These 4 Use Cases represent a heterogeneous scenario where secure communications must be ensured. In the final project phase, the use cases will be carried out to test the trusted communications in them. Therefore, a brief overview of the use cases and networks that may be vulnerable in these scenarios is necessary.

5.2.2.1. UC1: Forest Fire in Spain-Portugal

Description: A cross-border forest fire, with multiple fire sources localized in the border area between Spain and Portugal. There are several urbanized areas with limited access due to the mountainous terrain, high forest density and an underdeveloped road system are affected.

Potential communications risk: The mountainous terrain may mean that there is not good signal at all points near the incident. Less densely populated areas usually have the lowest number of mobile phone antennas installed. Geographical features also hinder the transmission of radio waves. While for a long-time coverage in neighbouring areas of different countries has been a problem due to roaming, within the European Union this is no longer an issue. If a mobile phone handset uses coverage in another European country, there are no additional charges due to the EU roaming policy. Finally, the direct impact of fire on telecommunications-related infrastructures (electricity grid, antennas, etc.) may make them more difficult to use.

5.2.2.2. UC2: Toxic spill in Slovakian - Italian

Description: Technological incident and release of the toxic plume. Explosion/fire in the private company storing different materials and/or waste dump storing also dangerous materials (in particular polyurethan foams). Toxic cloud is heading towards densely populated part of the town as well as to close village behind borders.

Potential communications risk: No risks identified. Fire can destroy electricity connection or antennas, but toxic cloud does not pose a significant impact on communication risk. Open issue is fast communication with related bodies in the neighbouring country, mainly with the basic level of responders. At the same time, the loss of some information is possible due to the time stress and information overload in some steps of rescue actions. This might be improved by using of modern IT solutions and harmonized procedures.

5.2.2.3. UC3: Earthquake in Bulgaria – Greece

Description: A strong earthquake caused a series of humanitarian crises and industrial accidents threatening the lives of the population in the Bulgarian-Greek border area. The earthquake caused the destruction of a reservoir and the leakage of large amounts of the toxic substance acrylonitrile at a polymer plant in a close town.

Potential communications risk: The telephone connection, including the connection of the mobile operators, has been disrupted, which makes communication in the area difficult.

5.2.2.4. UC4: Sea rescue in Norway, Denmark and Sweden

Description: Two vessels, one passenger ship and one chemical tanker, has collided. It is urgent need to attend to passengers and to get control of the fire. The content of toxicity in the smoke is unknown but assumed poisonous.

Potential communications risk: No particular risk due to the incident. Only risks arising from being at sea.

5.2.3. Heterogeneous scenarios, adaptability

First responders' scenarios cover a wide range of operations, different needs, geographical restrictions, infrastructures availability or degraded capabilities. Within each scenario first responders will face different constraint for which SIGRUN should provide a common operative and technological frame, capable of being adapted to each specific scenarios' constraints.

A key function of the SIGRUN is the capability to provide the mean of communication that enables different users, equipped with different communications assets to interchange data and interoperate in a coordinated way.

These heterogeneous communications can be built in three different build-up structures:

1. Heterogeneous Networks connectivity
2. Common network data exchange layer
3. Data Interoperability

5.2.3.1. Heterogeneous Networks Connectivity

Figure 15 - Network connectivity in heterogeneous scenarios

The first element is, therefore, the connectivity or the capability to establish a communication connection between the different actors and users. For each scenario we will find different communications networks:

Each actor or first responder force will be operating under some kind of network, as presented in the previous picture. Each scenario may explore one or some of these networks, and although they can be used in a segregated way, the optimisation of the resources may push for an integrated usability of these networks.

Although all the networks can potentially be used in any use case, some are more easily explorable in specific scenarios. Based on the USE CASES established for VALKYRIES, it was mapped the communications technologies and the functions provided:

USE CASE	5G	WIFI	TETRA	D2D	SATELLITE	MBR
WILDFIRE	- Support - Coord	- Local - Support - Logistics	- Coord C2 (C)	- Support - Health	- Support - Logistics	N.A.
TOXIC LEAKAGE	- Coord (C)	- Local - Support - Logistics	- C2 - IC - Responders	- Support - Health	- Support - Logistics	N.A.
EARTHQUAKE	N.A.	- Local - Support	- Coord - C2 (C)	- Support - Health	- C2 - Coord(C)	N.A.

		- Logistics				
MARITIME SAR	N.A.	- Local - Support	N.A.	- Support - Health	- Support - Health - Coord	- C2 (C) - Coord (C)

(C) - Critical function supported by the communications networks

IC - Incident Commander info

COORD - Coordination communication info other than C2

C2 - Command and Control info (also referred to C3ISR)

Health – Medical and health info

Support – communication info enabling the support activities (may not require tactical data)

Logistics – communication info to support the operations logistics

Local - Local communications connectivity

Table 7 - Communications Technologies Functions used by USE CASE

5.2.3.2. Common network data exchange layer

Secondly, the merge of the different communication networks can provide a wider connectivity, therefore, establishing bridges between the different networks will provide new actors access to the SIGRUN data, and enable higher level of interactions, resilience, and adaptability to different scenarios (see Figure 16).

Figure 16 - FR Communications networks integration. From D2.3 (14).

Therefore, the different networks should be able to interface and establish a minimum capability to exchange data between them. By establishing nodes and bridges that connect both 2 networks, an IP layer was defined to harmonize the different connectivity layers and support the multiple networks connection.

Some of the ordinary features for a software solution are (1):

- Instant communications and real time communications:
 - The information shared must be updated in real time and manage correctly historic information to avoid risks and cause confusion.
 - Two-way communications or multi-channel:

- Grants flow communication between two points. It is needed to confirm information by 'double-check' which permit to know who has received the information and make follow-up. Also, they permit analyse information received to determine priority of the emergency response. Another point is using dynamic information to adapt the response to the current scenario behaviour.
- Event monitoring. Measure the success of the emergency plan and / or evaluating communication system, security of data, service, and support.
- Measurement tools with analytics and reporting

5.2.3.3. Data Interoperability

The last elements of heterogeneous scenarios refer to the data interoperability. Data interoperability addresses “the ability of systems and services that create, exchange and consume data to have clear, shared expectations for the contents, context and meaning of that data” (2).

To support the different types of information shared within the SIGRUN network, a common data reference model is required, a common reference language and a common semantics (meaning, understanding dictionary, etc.). Such semantics is established in the WP2.

The data interoperability model also establishes the mechanisms for end-user applications to interchange data, defines the data orchestration processes and the models that support a heterogeneous of applications to operate in a joint operation without the need to fully redesign the applications. Instead, it uses gateways and APIs to integrate the applications in a common operational environment. Thus, a software for any emergency or heterogeneous scenario should help reaching all actors or participants, near and far, with the critical information and notifications timely, aiming to provide the required information when needed. The data interoperability includes the shared data as well as the metadata generates and exchanged.

5.2.4. Trusted Communications

As the information handled during emergency situations (3) is sensitive information that should be available during the actuations, the protection against malicious user is strictly necessary. In this context, the trusted communications are performed over trusted channels (4), which allow to establish communications with the necessary confidence to support the security policies.

To provide these interoperable trusted mechanisms, capable to work over multi-vendor environments across multiple endpoints, it is necessary to establish the use of standards, policies, compliance, security automation and protocols (5) to provide appropriate confidentiality, authentication, and content-integrity protection.

5.2.5. Security concerns

Data controllership means that a subject can control means and purposes of data flows, namely establishing when, where and how information about themselves is used and by whom. Privacy is one of the significant grounds of assessment in communication networks. For two remote nodes to communicate, they have to declare that they are active in the network and participate in the routing protocols, with the consequent publication of their position/location in the network.

Privacy attacks can be both active and passive. In active attacks, malicious users participate in the network protocol they intend to break, either through external attacks (users outside the

system) or with internal attacks (lawful network members). On the other hand, passive attacks do not disrupt the regular operation of network protocols, and attackers listen unauthorisedly to packets being transmitted over the network. Thanks to traffic analysis, extrapolate information such as transmission paths and message content or the identity, position or movement of nodes.

Privacy is a comprehensive concept, but in the case of network communications, what interests us is to focus mainly on three of its properties:

1. **Anonymity of data:** the property of not including personal data, i.e., information does not make them identified/able. “No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honour and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks” (6). Both those affected and those involved in a disaster have the right not to be identified. However, in order to care for the injured, responders may need to access to a series of information including sensitive one, like electronic medical records not only to consult but also to report on medical actions taken. In addition, the need to communicate this data eventually to the hospitals of destination may pose a risk of exposure of this data. Therefore, privacy shall here be combined with the data protection concept that includes the privacy preserving principle and the conditions to enable a free circulation of the required data to achieve a given purpose under a specified lawful basis. In this regard, the EU General Data Protection Regulation n. 2016/679 (hereinafter “GDPR”) stated binding conditions for data controllers to properly process personal data, enabling those communications that are functional to pursuing a public interest, to preserve a vital interest of the data subject in a manner that protects the availability, integrity, and confidentiality of data flows by design and by default.
2. **Unlikability of messages:** property of hiding the existing relationship between communication and the people who carry it out.
3. **Undetectability:** inability to distinguish whether an element exists or not. In the case of messages, undetectability means that the messages are not sufficiently discernible from, for example, white noise.

The ongoing transition to a networked society necessitates network infrastructure and services that are both reliable and secure. New security challenges emerge as networks evolve from simple point-to-point systems to complex, software-defined, ultra-high capacity and reach, and distributed cloud environments.

Malicious attackers see communication networks as a desirable target because they are a key enabler of the information society. Network breaches occur at all layers of the network, and their frequency, magnitude, and sophistication are increasing.

Malicious attacks are typically classified into three categories: confidentiality, integrity, and availability. Only authorized parties have access to the communication, which is referred to as confidentiality. Integrity refers to the completeness and trustworthiness of received data that has not been tampered with, either accidentally or intentionally. Availability refers to the ability to access and use service, data, and network elements in response to a valid request.

Threats can be inadvertent or intentional, active or passive. A threat that is unintentional, such as a system or software failure or a physical failure, is known as an accidental threat. An intentional threat is one that is realized because of a conscious act. Intentional threats can range from a cursory examination using readily available monitoring tools to complex attacks requiring special system knowledge. An attack occurs when a deliberate threat is realized. An active threat is one that causes a change in the state or operation of a system, such as data alteration or physical equipment destruction. There is no change in state with a passive threat. Passive threats include eavesdropping and wiretapping.

A security vulnerability is a flaw or weakness in a system or the information it contains that could be exploited. If there is a vulnerability, a threat could be realized successfully unless effective countermeasures are in place (7).

5.2.6. Resilient Network Systems for emergency scenarios

The implementation of resilient systems, able to react against adverse situations, is essential in any technological solution. It is desired that these systems can recover against failures or malicious actions. These principles could be included from different perspectives, such as implementing dynamic network mechanisms to reconfigure the network against failures or by having back-up communication links. This is especially critical in emergency situations, where different approaches could apply, as subsequently presented.

5.2.6.1. Network Resilience principles

Fundamental to disaster management is the existence of a resilient network system that has the capacity to absorb external influences and reorganise itself as change occurs, so that it maintains essentially the same function, structure, and identity (8). Examples such as what happened in the first moments after the plane crash in Barajas in August 2008 (9), when the saturation of the mobile phone network made initial communications extremely difficult, leading to an inadequate sizing of the situation, with a massive dispatch of ambulances, show how important this aspect is.

So, a number of resilience principles have been defined as part of resilience frameworks in order to address difficulties in a more systematic manner. These principles aid in the various areas and concepts associated to resilience, taking into account prerequisites, trade-offs, enablers, and behaviour. Figure 17 shows a high-level summary of various resilience principles (8).

Figure 17 - An overview of resilience principles (10)

Many applications in sectors including public wireless networks, disaster information networks, and intelligent traffic transportation systems have been developed because of modern wireless communication technology. Wireless communication systems are extremely useful in crisis situations.

As shown in Figure 18, the required information varies in time before and after a large natural disaster based on the investigation of previous large natural disasters.

t1 is normal time, t2 is estimated period, tx is time at disaster, t3 is the period just after the disaster, t4 is stable period, t5 is recovery period, and t6 is recovered time, where t1 is normal time, t2 is estimated period, tx is time at disaster, t3 is the period just after the disaster, t4 is stable period, t5 is recovery period, and t6 is recovered time.

Figure 18 - Required disaster information (11)

By exchanging the disaster information through this stratified network, the system can persistently continue to provide communication capability and can automatically perform handover to the other access networks which have enough available network resources by wireless cognitive network functions even if in a part of the network infrastructure, some network node and line failures occur. The approach is to develop our system based on SDN technology, by integrating 3G,4G,5G, LTE, WiMAX, and satellite networks.

5.2.6.2. DTN Networks

A possible resilient concept to accommodate within SIGRUN, is Delay/Disruptive Tolerant Networks (DTN). A DTN architecture is a store-and-forward communications architecture in which source nodes send DTN bundles through a network to destination nodes. DTN implements congestion control mechanisms where each router can make decisions based on local information. (An example is the router-to-router bundle data transfer acceptance). To decide either to accept the transfer of the data the algorithm take into consideration other

factors, such as: storage availability; historical data from the network connection (past adverse effects); data loss rate, etc. (12)

DTN encompasses a suite of standard protocols that use information within the data stream (headers attached to data units) to accomplish end-to-end data delivery through networks and networks nodes. DTN enables data delivery in situations that involve:

- Intermittent connection (e.g., end-to-end link unavailability).
- Delays.
- Data rate mismatches between networks.

The main differences between DTN and traditional communications networks are presented below.

Characteristics	DTN	Traditional communication network
survival time	Nodes with short survival time	Do not consider the survival time problem
Space ratio	Reduce the space ratio to extend node working time	The bigger the better
Storage capacity	High demand for storage function and extra memory required for long queue time	Memory and cache, low memory requirements

Figure 19 - DTN vs Traditional Networks Comparison (13)

5.2.6.3. LoRa Networks for SIGRUN IOT

LoRa, as subsequently presented in detail in Section 5.2.8.2, is a physical layer LPWAN technology that offers a wide network coverage using a reduced power but having a limitation in the data throughputs. This technology has been conceived to be robust against interferences and offer good connectivity to devices that need to transmit data every few minutes. In this sense, LoRa natively complies with a set of requirements that enables higher resilience, namely:

- Low power consumption
- Long range (up to 16 km)
- Penetration underground and concrete
- Operation in adverse weather conditions
- Operation in RF noisy environment

Additionally, LoRaWAN is a L2 standard that enables the communication of LoRa devices, managing their physical capabilities and requirements for each situation. Thus, it offers adaptability to a wide variety of adverse situations, being an ideal candidate for backup network solutions where main systems such as TETRA and mobile communications fail. It is intended either for devices for reduced network requirements, or for situations in which communication must be established and a reduced data transfer rate is preferable to no communication at all.

5.2.6.4. Integration of multiple MCI networks

In a MCI event scenario, there are several challenges in setting a reliable and trusted network supporting highly mobile emergency service's actors and assets:

- The existing infrastructure might be physically damaged, because of a natural disaster.
- Emergency professionals are inherently mobile and might be deployed in areas with low network infrastructure density, limiting or constraining access to network services.

- A large number of users try accessing the existing network infrastructure (e.g., call 112, call their families, search information) causing network (and spectrum) congestion and denial of service.

It is therefore paramount to provide **resilient network systems** for emergency service's actors, capable to offer digital services while at the same time recover from physical damage, loss of connectivity and operate independently of citizen's usage. Resilient networks can be achieved by using multiple technologies in combination or alternatively, seeking the best connection and performance, across different environments, as depicted in the Figure 20 (14).

Figure 20 - FR Communications Networks connection node

With the aim to achieve dedicated and secure networks ensuring service availability even in extreme situations, many European emergency (and security) services have heavily invested in **TETRA networks** to achieve communications services operating on segregated spectrum (not shared with civilians, thus not impacted by citizen usage) (15). However, TETRA is, in practice, limited to voice services, not enabling data exchange and services: TETRA systems only support about 28,8 kbit/s while TETRA release 2 (TETRA-2) brings high-speed capability (TEDS) with about up-to 500 kbit/s (16), but TETRA-2 is only deployed in few locations in Europe (17).

Communications technologies like **LTE and 5G** support high throughput data exchange (peak bit rate of 10 Gbps; average of several 100Mbps), effectively enabling data services as those envisaged in VALKYRIES. However, LTE and 5G (i) network coverage may lack in non-populated areas (e.g., mountains and sea) (ii) spectrum is shared with civilians which may cause service unavailability in cases of high usage. In this regard, combining TETRA (voice) with LTE or 5G (data) is seen as a good option to obtain secure voice services and data services. Interestingly, there are radio manufacturers providing TETRA LTE hybrid devices (as well as Wi-Fi, NFC and RFID), allowing exploiting several technologies in combination (18).

Additional technologies like **Wi-Fi** for providing local network coverage, and **ad-hoc networking** (e.g., MANET) allow to extend connectivity by connecting nearby terminals. However, connected nodes need to be in "proximity" of each other and, for the MANET case, each additional "hop" adds latency to communications.

Concerning long-range and global communications, options include **maritime broadband radio** and **satellite communications** (14). These technologies are essential when considering deployments at sea or at remote locations where existing infrastructures are inexistent.

Characteristics	Technologies						
	TETRA	D2D	Wi-Fi	4G	5G	MBR	Satellite
Dependence on infra-structure	Partial	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Congestion control	No	Partial	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Quality of Service	No	Partial	Partial	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial
Mobility	Yes	Yes	Partial	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial
Inter-operability and heterogeneity	Yes	Yes	No	Yes		No	No
Security and privacy	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Robustness and flexibility	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial	Yes	Yes	No
Data transfer rate	Low, Medium	Low	Medium High	Low, Medium, High	Very High	Medium (50km at 16.5 Mbps)	Medium

Table 8 - Communications Technologies comparison

5.2.6.5. SIGRUN Networks Gateway

To cope with a variety of different technologies and challenging scenarios, VALKYRIES proposes a **GATEWAY solution** to provide interoperability between different networks, as well as providing a bridge between them, as depicted in the figure below:

Figure 21 - Gateway Interfaces Overview. From D2.3 (14).

The GATEWAY allows IP and non-IP networks to communicate and exchange data, while also being able to change between different protocols and technologies, according to availability and performance. The GATEWAY supports multiple communications technologies (e.g., 4G, Wi-Fi, SATCOM) and implements inter-network connections. Importantly, the GATEWAY can operate as an access point to other devices. GATEWAYS can be installed in aerial units (like UAVs) for

wide area communications provision to ground assets. By monitoring communication channels, the GATEWAY selects the appropriate communication mechanism, delivering a solution for resilient communications.

VALKYRIES approach to resilient communications consists in exploiting various technologies, selecting those appropriate for the scenario at hand:

- The proposed GATEWAY is fit for deployment at vehicles and advanced posts, that can cope with “more demanding” power and weight requirements.
- Emergency professionals, highly mobile, need lightweight terminals and can benefit from hybrid terminals supporting TETRA, LTE and other technologies.
- Concerning connected devices (IoT), two different classes are considered: (1) unconstrained (can operate without limitations); (2) constrained (are limited on power, size and/or computation). The latter need to consider low-power technologies (e.g., BLE, LoRa) that are often also limited on range (e.g., personal devices, like bodycams and health monitoring).

To support networks resilience, the GATEWAY provides several functions:

- Routing data between different networks.
- Convert connection protocols between the different networks.
- Reports to the application layer the available bandwidth (data prioritization is not responsibility of the gateway).
- Provides IP Layer network service to non-IP native networks or devices.

These gateway functions enable a more agile data transmission, by switching to an uncongested and available network, when the original network is in overload or malfunction, thus increasing the global data transfer more resilient.

5.2.6.6. Software Defined Networks

Software-Defined Networking (SDN) is an approach to the networks controlling infrastructure that uses software controllers and APIs to interface with the network hardware infrastructure and dynamically redirect the traffic in a network and change the data routing models to better manage the available bandwidth and improve the network efficiency and resilience, mainly to data overload.

The main characteristic and advantage of this type of network lie in the logical separation of the network control (control plane) and the traffic relay layer (data plane). This separation is achieved using an Application Programming Interface (API), allowing SDN controllers to exercise direct control over the data plane.

One of the significant challenges of VALKYRIES disaster scenarios is the heterogeneity of end-user terminals, which have different network technologies to interconnect to SIGRUN. To fulfil this purpose, the data flow coming from end devices, e.g., mobile devices, first responder's computers, technological equipment of an ambulance has to be translated to IP. In this sense, well-known gateways are deployed, which allow the corresponding translation to be performed depending on the source technology. With this translation, we offer the possibility of adapting this heterogeneity to an IP scenario where the SDN controller can manage and adjust to the changing scenario of a catastrophe.

These gateways must be redundant since they are a key element in the interconnection of the end devices to SIGRUN, being physical elements and therefore vulnerable to external conditions occurring during the emergency. Ensuring this adherence between technologies and an IP scenario allows us to maintain correct and efficient addressing, detecting any level of management while guaranteeing a minimum level of security in communications when standards and protocols are applied in the upper layers of communication.

Figure 22 - SIGRUN SDN Network Topology

Thus, SDN provides additional network resilience by dynamically adapt the re-routing protocols to overcome networks points of congestion, preventing or reducing data loss or data late delivered.

5.2.6.7. Additional resilient elements

Additional elements are included to improve the overall SIGRN resilience.

5.2.6.8. Error correction code in protocols

Communication messages between the systems includes several controls to provide the means to check if the message suffered any transmission error, bit change. Different protocols use bit check code. LRC, VRC, CRC are methods commonly used, by include in the message several control bits.

In addition to the error detection, protocols can also include mechanisms, protocols, and control bits to enable the receiver to correct the error received. Some error correction examples are:

- **Automatic Repeat Request (ARQ)** - in a simple description, it refers to the exchange process control where the message is resent when the receiver does not acknowledge to have received the message without error.
- **Forward error correction (FEC)** - Refers to an error correction technique where several control bits are included in the transmitted message allowing the receiver not only to detect that there is an error, but also, to correct the error, without the need for retransmission. FEC can, generally, be of two types, Convolutional code or Block Code.
- **Convolutional codes** – The message comprises of data streams of arbitrary length and parity symbols are generated by the sliding application of a Boolean function to the data stream. They are particularly suitable for implementation in hardware.
- **Block codes** – Block codes are processed on a data block structure, instead bit-by-bit. The message is divided into fixed-sized blocks of bits and then a number of control and redundancy bits are added for error correction.
- **Mix** - A combination of the above code correction approaches can be used that best fit the purpose. E.g., in small bit message length adding additional control and recovery bits may not be necessary and resend is the best option.

5.2.6.9. Data integrity assurance

Data Integrity refers to the valuable and significance of the data used, and for that it means a context. Within data integrity it includes data quality as a subset. Data quality refers to the consistency, validity and completeness, which means that the data is processed correctly but to provide significance of the outcome, data needs also to have integrity.

There are currently several types of data integrity (19):

- **Physical integrity** is the protection of the wholeness and accuracy of that data as it's stored and retrieved. When natural disasters strike, power goes out, or hackers disrupt database functions, physical integrity is compromised. (See backup and disaster recovery plan chapters)
- **Logical integrity** keeps data unchanged as it's used in different ways in a relational database. Logical integrity protects data from human error and hackers as well, but in a much different way than physical integrity does. There are four types of logical integrity:
 - **Entity integrity** - to ensure that data isn't listed more than once (The data is not duplicated or there is no more than one data entity for the same data concept representation (e.g.: in the system there is just a single data entity that represents the age of a victim).
 - **Referential integrity** refers to the series of processes that make sure data is stored and used uniformly. Rules embedded into the data structure about how to reference the data entity are used to ensure that only appropriate changes, additions, or deletions of data occur.
 - **Domain integrity** is the collection of processes that ensure the accuracy of each piece of data in a domain. In this context, a domain is a set of acceptable values that the entity can take (e.g.: the victim age entity cannot take the significant value of -1 years)
 - **User-defined integrity** involves the rules and constraints created by the user to fit their needs. Sometimes entity, referential, and domain integrity aren't

enough to safeguard data. Often, specific operating rules must be considered and incorporated into data integrity measures.

5.2.6.10. Hot system update

Hot system update is a function of the disaster recovery Plan. This function provides the mean for an application entering the federation, new application or a restore of an application that had to restart, to catch-up to the same operational level of the federation.

This process is natively executed once the application is registered into the federation and publishes its required data needs and the data that is able to share. The federation orchestration provides the mechanisms to ensure that new application can enter into the federation, due to the redundancy and continuous backup of the data shared.

5.2.7. Cybersecurity solutions applicable to current technologies

Since this project is not physically oriented but instead network and security-oriented, the first and second layers of the model (medium access layer) will not be addressed. Any current and promising technology applicable to multi-victim scenarios will be considered valid and accepted. Similarly, since the content is network related, the last two layers (presentation and application layer) have been chosen because they are more linked to services and data. Figure 23 shows the WP4 general aspects related to the different OSI layers.

Figure 23 - WP4 general aspects

The second layer would be the first layer for data routing, using the physical address of the device, i.e. using the MAC (Media Access Control) address to route packets. The MAC address is a unique address that differentiates each machine. In addition, at this layer, the transition from cable to network device occurs; this device is the switch. The switch is responsible for various functions such as: creating data frames, sending them in an orderly fashion and flow control (it orders the sending of a frame once the previous one has been received if several devices are sharing the same medium, the switch allows the sharing of the medium in an efficient and orderly manner), among others. In Point-to-Point (PPP) connections, only layers two and above would be sufficient to establish a connection between two devices.

Layer three is one of the most important layers for communication since it does not use the physical address of the device (MAC) for routing, but a virtual address called IP address, in addition to one of the possible routing protocols (BGP, OSPF, RIP, among the best known and

which will be discussed in more detail in the following sections), which allows communication between devices belonging to different networks. The devices in charge of routing data frames through a communications network are routers. In addition, as layer three devices, firewalls also belong to this group, which allow the communication of specific destinations, thus providing the network with particular security by only allowing the indicated connections and routing the received frame.

The fourth layer acts on the data that is sent in each data frame, sends it in an orderly fashion, relocates it upon receipt of all the frames, and if it needs to resend any of them, it requests it. It also maintains a direct source-destination communication between the devices in such a way that until one (or more than one, depending on the configuration) frame has been received and indicated as received, the next frame is not sent; if the waiting time is exceeded, the frame is resent. In addition, it can maintain, separate and differentiate the data it is receiving from different applications by maintaining simultaneous connections (e.g. two different d's with simultaneous connections). The two protocols involved in this layer are TCP and UDP, the former is connection-oriented, i.e. it delivers the frames in order and has flow control, while the latter is a non-connection-oriented protocol, i.e. the higher level will be in charge of ordering and presenting the frames. UDP is faster but less reliable, and widely used in IP voice communications and streaming.

The fifth layer is in charge of maintaining active sessions during data transmission, synchronising hosts and controlling data transfer. The real utility of this layer is the transfer of files between two machines or remote connections. The most used protocol in this second layer is the RPC (Remote Procedure Call) which allows a client to perform operations on another machine (server) remotely.

Table 9 shows the different current network technologies identified in the landscape: TETRA, Ad-hoc, Wi-Fi, 2G, 3G, 4G, 5G and satellite communications. For each of them, their capacity of adaptation for congestion control, quality of service, mobility, interoperability and heterogeneity, security and privacy, robustness and flexibility, and data transfer rate is incorporated.

Characteristics	Technologies					
	TETRA	Ad-hoc	Wi-Fi	2G-3G-4G	5G	Satellite Communications
Congestion control	No	Partial	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Quality of Service	No	Partial	Partial	Yes	Yes	Partial
Mobility	Yes	Yes	Partial	Yes	Yes	Partial
Interoperability and heterogeneity	Yes	Yes	No	Yes		No
Security and privacy	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Robustness and flexibility	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial	Yes	No
Data transfer rate	Low, Medium	Low	Medium High	Low, Medium, High	Very High	Medium

Table 9 - Summary of technologies according to the different characteristics of the multi-victim scenario

5.2.7.1. Ad-hoc communications

This section represents the possible deployment of smart contracts and the usage of blockchain as the middleman for data security and communication link. The overall architecture can be enhanced by mechanisms that will embed the blockchain capabilities.

Metadata that are generated from on-site communications can be stored safely in decentralised databases and the interactions with them can be recorded safely using smart contracts. Also, smart contracts can enable specific persons to interact with the datasets and have certain privileges to those data.

Cutting out the middleman in communications can be a great thing for privacy and security reasons. There a lot of intermediaries, and their man function is to establish trust between two or more parts. For example, in cyber security, the blockchain using cryptography verifies and secures the data. That eliminates the need for middleware making it more efficient than many legacy systems.

SECURITY CAPABILITIES

Regarding the security section, blockchain can be characterised as one of the most secure tools that can easily be adapted to any type of platform. Each data will be stored encrypted, and each data unit is connected using identity controls. So, in each use case we can identify the demonstration using the corresponding wallet address. In order for any party to access encrypted data, only by the use of the wallet that was used for doing the transactions into the blockchain. Moreover, the blockchain offers the capability of decentralised databases meaning that data is shared through the blockchain blocks which is more complex to target a specific database. Therefore, storing or retrieving data requires consensus mechanisms which eliminates malicious procedures. Furthermore, each transaction can later on be registered on the corresponding blockchain explorer where any interested party can review any type (GET, POST) activities that we need to be aware of. Each data received from ad-hoc can be restored to the blockchain directly and used for information sharing and network connection only by the persons who will be given access based on the mapping of the data to the use cases.

5.2.7.2. Wi-Fi communications

The IEEE 802.11 specification (20) is an international standard that defines the characteristics of a wireless local area network. Different standards have been implemented over time to improve connectivity and performance. All are improvements and build on the initial 802.11 standards. Regardless of the frequency band, the 802.11 families of standards share some limitations (21).

Firstly, the range is one of the common limitations. This depends firstly on the location and obstacles in the path between the access point and the terminal and secondly on weather conditions and interference. While the different standards can achieve the theoretical speeds shown in Table 10, because of the effect of the protocols required to carry the user information over the channel, the rate is much lower, a common limitation for all of them.

Version	Frequency band	Bandwidth	Transmission scheme	Modulation	Antenna	Max. data rate	Max. range
Wi-Fi 1	2.4 GHz	20 MHz	DSSS	QPSK	SISO	1-11 Mbps	Out: 300 m In: 30 m
Wi-Fi 2	5 GHz	20 MHz	OFDM	64-QAM	SISO	6-54 Mbps	Out: 100 m In: 10 m
Wi-Fi 3	2.4 GHz	20 MHz	DSSS OFDM	64-QAM	SISO	54 Mbps	Out: 140 m In: 38 m
Wi-Fi 4	2.4 GHz 5 GHz	20 MHz 40 MHz	OFDM	64-QAM	SU-MIMO 4x4:4	600 Mbps	Out: 250 m In: 70 m
Wi-Fi 5	5 GHz	20 MHz 40 MHz 80 MHz 160 MHz	OFDM	256-QAM	SU-MIMO 8x8:8	433 Mbps – 6.93 Gbps	Out: 100 m In: 35 m
Wi-Fi 6	2.4 GHz 5 GHz	20 MHz 40 MHz 80 MHz 160 MHz	OFDMA	1024-QAM	SU-MIMO 8x8:8	600 Mbps – 9.6 Gbps	Out: 120 m In: 30 m

Table 10 - Comparison between Wi-Fi standards

In terms of quality of service, not all traffic is of equal importance from each user's point of view. Thus, it can be considered that a VoIP call would have to take priority over a file transfer. The most widespread WiFi protocols do not include any mechanism to prioritise one type of traffic over another, which is detrimental when mixing traffic flows with very different requirements, such as voice and data.

As for the security of WiFi networks, they did not have very sophisticated security mechanisms, but with the success of this technology, it became necessary to introduce improvements in this aspect. The lack of security of these networks is one of the biggest detractors. 802.11i resolves most of the original weaknesses, to the point of making them comparable in security to fixed networks.

SECURITY CAPABILITIES

Wireless networks have undergone a significant evolution, from their initial deployment in small local area networks to their deployment in wide area networks. This is possible because the WiFi network architecture is easily scalable.

Security (22) is the most crucial point, often overlooked and the cause of many problems. One of the problems that WiFi technology is currently facing is the progressive saturation of the radio spectrum due to the massification of users, which significantly affects long-distance connections (greater than 100 metres). The WiFi standard is designed to connect computers to the network over short distances; any use over a more extended range is exposed to an excessive risk of interference.

A very high percentage of networks are installed with no regard for security, thus turning their networks into open networks (or entirely vulnerable to attempts by third parties to access them) without protecting the information that circulates through them. In fact, the default configuration of many WiFi devices (e.g. routers) is very insecure since the device identifier can be used to find out the device's password. Therefore, access and control of the device can be gained in just a few seconds.

Unauthorised access to a WiFi device is very dangerous for the owner for several reasons. The most obvious is that they can use the connection. But, in addition, by accessing the WiFi, one can monitor and record all the information that is transmitted over it (including personal information and passwords, etc.). Unlike wired networks, one has no control over the medium where the data circulates. Encrypting the data guarantees the confidentiality of the data. This is done with the help of a key. This key also makes it possible to protect access to the network because if we do not know it, we cannot communicate and therefore cannot read the frames and send them in the correct format.

In particular, the interest comes from the protocols referred to by the National Cryptologic Centre, from now on CCN (23), in the guide CCN-STIC-816 Wireless Network Security in the ENS. These are IEEE 802.11i (24) and IEEE 802.11w (25). Although outside the 802.11 standard, the guide also considers the use of IEEE 802.1x (26), a model that governs port control. Brief descriptions of the above standards are given below:

- **IEEE 802.11i:** is a revision of the original standard in which the original security mechanism, which was WEP (Wired Equivalent Privacy), was modified. The reason for this change was the detection of vulnerabilities in WEP, proving it to be unsuitable for securing wireless networks. This was what IEEE 802.11i corrected, going on to create more robust mechanisms than WEP, such as WPA (WiFi Protected Access) and WPA2, which is the one currently in use.

The latter two standards, WPA and WPA2, use the cryptographic protocols Temporal Key Integration Protocol (TKIP, from now on) and Counter-mode/CBC-MAC Protocol (CCMP), respectively. CCMP uses the Counter with CBC-MAC (CCM) mode of operation, also known as Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), using a 128-bit key and 128-bit block size. To increase confidentiality and data integrity, CCMP combines several methods to enhance the performance of TKIP and WEP.

- **IEEE 802.1x:** Two implementation modes (Personal and Enterprise) are defined for WPA and WPA2. The Enterprise mode uses the 802.1x authentication mechanism in which uses an Authentication Server (AS) to authorise incoming connection requests to the network.

The combination of both standards allows us to create the concept encompassed in IEEE 802.11i, the RSA (Robust Security Networks), which are networks that only allow the creation of RSNA (Robust Security Network Associations). To ensure the robust security of a network, all devices must use RSNA.

- **IEEE 802.11w:** It is an improvement to the IEEE 802.11i standard, because it adds security to the management traffic during the connection. It provides confidentiality, integrity, authenticity and anti-send protection for management frames. For the implementation of these standards, we have seen that three hardware elements are involved: the client, the Access Point and the Authentication Server:
 - **Client:** any user device that requests access to the wireless network to perform user data transfer. They can be, for example, laptops, smartphones, game consoles, etc.
 - **Access Points (APs):** are part of the equipment that make up the wireless infrastructure, and are responsible for connecting client devices to each other, or to the organisation's wired infrastructure.

- **Authentication Server (AS):** these are devices in charge of managing client access to the network and issuing certificates. They are able to maintain a database with each user and grant each one a different password to access the WiFi network.

WiFi technology allows the encryption of communications. Various methods have been used for this purpose, which have evolved to address weaknesses that have appeared over time. The security of WiFi communications can be established:

- **Unencrypted:** no encryption password is set on the connection, so any device can join and communicate. Unencrypted: No encryption password is set on the connection, so any device can join and communicate over the connection.
- **WEP (Wired Equivalent Privacy):** the first encryption mechanism, included in the first IEEE 802.11 standard. It is based on the RC4 encryption algorithm, using a secret key of 40 or 104 bits combined with an Initialisation Vector (IV) of 24 bits; making a total of 64 or 128 bits. This encryption method is strongly discouraged due to vulnerabilities and many devices no longer allow its use as it is considered vulnerable.
- **WPA (Wi-Fi Protected Access):** developed to solve the problems presented by WEP encryption, its main feature is the use of an authentication server (RADIUS1 type or similar) (WPA-Enterprise) using the EAP protocol. It is also possible to use pre-shared keys (PSK, Pre-Shared Keys) (WPA-Personal), although security is reduced. It incorporates the Temporary Key Integrity Protocol² which takes care of dynamic key change. AES encryption is optionally possible.
- **WPA2 (Wi-Fi Protected Access 2):** is an enhancement of WPA that corrects certain shortcomings of its predecessor. It uses AES encryption by default. In principle, it is the most secure security protocol for WiFi now.

5.2.7.3. TETRA communications

Terrestrial Trunked Radio (TETRA) is a digital trunked mobile radio standard developed by the ETSI to meet the needs of the Professional Mobile Radio (PMR) organizations (e.g. military, public safety, government or transportation), such as:

- Wide area fast call set-up group calls.
- Direct Mode Operation.
- Encryption to meet the security needs of public safety organizations.
- Emergency calls even if the system is busy.
- Full-duplex voice for telephony communications.
- Use of different priority levels to guarantee resources to certain users or call types.
- Queuing system in case there are no free channels.
- Integration of vehicle location systems (AVL) within the terminals.

TETRA was developed as a standard for Europe, but it has already been deployed in many regions and nations outside Europe (mainly focused on Asia), positioning TETRA as a global standard. The ETSI TETRA continues to evolve beyond the actual release (Release 2), and ETSI has no plans to develop a substitute standard. Nonetheless, TETRA is not the only trunked radio standard; some relevant alternatives are:

- **TETRAPOL:** standard developed by EADS, mainly used by security forces.

- **P25:** standard developed by the Telecommunications Industry Association (TIA) and supports by the Association of Public-Safety Communications Officials-International (APCO), widely used in USA and Canada.
- **SIRDEE:** TETRAPOL variation used by Spanish security forces.

Today, TETRA continues to be the most widely used network for critical communications equipment in emergencies services, in over 100 countries around the world.

A very important advantage is that it does not imply an absolute dependency on the network to be able to communicate with TETRA terminals. Thus, in areas with limited range, some terminals can be used as a repeater. Similarly, in disaster situations with damage to communication infrastructures such as mobile networks, point-to-point communication is possible with TETRA, even with limited range. Unlike mobile networks, which connect one subscriber to another one (one-to-one), TETRA is built to be able to connect one-to-one, one-to-many and many-to-many. These operating modes are directly designed for public safety and professional users.

The TETRA communication equipment most commonly used by emergency services today are:

- Walkie-talkie type portable terminals.
- Fixed terminals.
- Intelligent devices (PCs, tablets, smartphones) linked to TETRA, as they allow data transmission although with a very low bandwidth of about 10 Kbps, without taking into account a future implementation of TEDS (TETRA Enhanced Data Services). It is mainly used for sending operational status and short text messages. Generally, these devices combine this with other data transmission options (WiFi, 3G, 4G...).

TETRA has been designed to provide the highest possible level of security and protection, and aims to meet the common security capabilities, summarized in the following bullets (27):

- Provide identity for users and networks.
- Ensure confidentiality, integrity, and privacy of communications. Furthermore, the data protection is maintained by law).
- Correct charging of system's users.
- Security control and management.

To do so, TETRA offers the following security measures (28):

- Security Profiles: each class has associated features as described in the **Table 11**.

Class	Authentication	OTAR	Encryption	Enable-Disable
1	Optional	N/A	N/A	Optional
2	Optional	Optional	Mandatory	Optional
3	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Recommended

Table 11 - Security profiles

- **Authentication:** enables by the secret key relationship of the root key K to ITSI and supports of MS by SwMI, of SwMI by MS and manual authentication. With these mechanisms, TETRA networks are protected from attempts of malicious access through cloned identities.

- **Over the air key management support (OTAR)**, allowing to distribute and manage the keys, associated to one or more encryption services over the air.
- **Encryption**, offering confidentiality on voice and data and some protection of the signalling. TETRA offers ciphering signalling and traffic information on radio links between terminals and stations, the latter encrypting traffic between points.
- **Over the air enable and disable**, providing disable facilities as it allows to deactivate a radio, temporarily (radio stun) or permanently (radio kill).
- **Crypto capabilities:** TEA1, TEA2, TEA3, TEA4 (communications) and TAA1 (authentication and key management).

5.2.7.4. Mobile communications (2G, 3G, 4G)

Mobile phones, smart phones and tablets are becoming more and more indispensable. Their use within control systems has also increased to facilitate some tasks. But mobile communications are not only used with these devices, point-to-point communications are also possible with this technology.

Mobile phone communications remain the most widely used alternative system for emergency services. As well as being used for voice communications, they support connection via 2G, 3G and 4G of other devices, such as tablets used for clinical reports, or other devices (GNSS, temperature sensors, clinical monitoring devices, etc.) present in the vehicle.

Features	2G GSM	2.7G EDGE	3G WCDMA	3.5 HSPA, HSPA+	4G LTE	4G LTE-Advanced	4,5 LTE-A Pro	5G
3GPP Release	Rel. 97	Rel. 98	Rel. 99	Rel. 5,6,7	Rel. 8,9	Rel. 10,11,12	Rel. 13,14	Rel. 15,16,17, 18
Use case	Digital voice and messaging	Enhanced 2G	Voice, Data and video	Enhanced 3G	Data and voice over IP	Enhanced 4G	4G evolution towards 5G	eMBB, critical MTC, massive MTC
Channel access	TDMA/FDMA	TDMA/FDMA	WCDMA	WCDMA	OFDMA	OFDMA	OFDMA	Modified OFDMA
Bandwidth	200 kHz	200 kHz	5 MHz	5 MHz	20 MHz	100 MHz	640 MHz	Up to 2 GHz
Service	CS	CS/PS	CS/PS	PS	PS	PS	PS	PS
Architecture	Controller	Controller	Controller	Controller	Distributed	HetNet	Cloud	Cloud, co-existence slicing
DL speed	40 Kbps	500 Kbps	384 kbps	14-84 Mbps	150-300 Mbps	1 Gbps	3 Gbps	> 10 Gbps
Latency	~500 ms	~300 ms	~150 ms	~50 ms	~10 ms	~10 ms	~5 ms	≤ 1ms

Table 12 - Summary of mobile networks features

SECURITY CAPABILITIES

Security features have also evolved along with the technology, changing encryption algorithms, and adding new security measures. GSM technology offers:

- Authentication of the user's identity.
- Confidentiality of the user's identity.
- Confidentiality of the signalling data.
- Confidentiality of the user's data.

All these security measures are implemented at the hardware level using symmetric key encryption systems and algorithms A3, A5 and A8, which are currently considered insecure. 3G networks offer a higher degree of security compared to their 2G predecessors. Among the most important features are:

- Authentication Network authentication.
- End-to-end security. Replacement of A5/1 (vulnerable) stream cipher with KASUMI.

5.2.7.5. Mobile communications (5G)

The name 5G refers to the fifth generation of mobile networks as we know them. The most significant advance will come in speed. 5G will allow browsing at up to 10 GBps (gigabytes per second), in addition, latency (network response time) will also see a significant improvement. According to the operators, it could be reduced to 5 milliseconds, a period almost imperceptible to humans, allowing us to connect in near real time. Thanks to this new technology, we can, for example, exponentially increase the number of connected devices. Vehicles, industrial robots, street furniture (speed bumps, roadways, bus stops) or any electronic device we have at home.

SECURITY CAPABILITIES

5G networks introduce a new security element called Edge Protection Proxy (SEPP) (29). This element is responsible for providing security between home networks and visited networks. It provides application layer security and protects against eavesdropping and replay attacks. Provide end-to-end authentication, integrity and confidentiality protection via signatures and encryption of all HTTP/2 roaming messages.

On the other hand, 5G changes the protocol stack used to IP for network management, thus enabling a strong interconnection with the other protocols for IP security that exist today. Thus, the stack would look like this (Figure 24).

- HTTP/2 over N32, replacing Diameter over the S6a reference point
- TLS as an additional layer of protection providing encrypted communication between all network functions (NF) inside a public land mobile network (PLMN)
- TCP as the transport layer protocol as replacement of the SCTP transport protocol.
- RESTful framework with OpenAPI 3.0.0 as the Interface Definition Language (IDL).

Figure 24 - 4G and 5G protocol stacks

5.2.7.6. Satellite communications

Satellite communications (30) come in many forms, from small and cheap cubesats (31) to large GEO satellites. Multiple types of orbits exist, and many factors influence on which orbit would be the appropriated for a satellite to use. Between the satellites with communication capabilities, the following can be found:

- Geostationary orbit (GEO): these satellites circle above the equator, following the Earth's rotation at the same rate and they cover a large range of Earth. These satellites stay over a particular place on Earth, allowing to keep antennas on Earth constantly pointed towards them; these property makes them useful a telecommunication satellite. The geostationary transfer orbit (GTO) satellites are a special kind of GEO satellites that are able to switch between orbits
- Low Earth orbit (LEO): normally at an altitude between 160 and 1000km, and their orbits and rotation frequency does not match with the Earth's. In order to have constant coverage, the LEO satellites should be deployed in large constellations, creating nets. Their proximity makes them useful for satellite imaging
- Medium Earth Orbit (MEO): functioning in the range between GEO and LEO, the MEO satellites are commonly used as navigation satellites
- Polar orbit and Sun-synchronous orbit (SSO): particular type of LEO satellites deployed to take images of certain polar places

Satellite communications (32) (SATCOM) provide connectivity to users in remote areas and where alternative communications are compromised (e.g. crisis areas, floods...). SATCOM is being used in commercial applications (COMSATCOM), military domain (MILSATCOM) and governmental domain (GOVSATCOM).

This is a technology that is currently not widely used in emergency medical services. However, it is being introduced progressively in these scenarios since they can surpass the limitations introduced by a disruption of classical communication based on radio, such as mobile communications or TETRA. For example, as complementary systems in medical helicopters.

SECURITY CAPABILITIES

Along the multiple types and uses of the satellites, many security capabilities have been explored. With the rapid development of SATCOM, the security has gradually become a critical topic, and often the security relies on the functionality offered by the satellite.

Nonetheless, many common solutions have been explored, such as:

- Physical layer security, many focused on the power allocation and the beamforming (33)
- Security for file delivery over unidirectional transport (FLUTE) (34)
- Symmetrical encryption schemes like AES in satellite applications (35)
- The use of security mechanisms for aeronautical data link communications (36)

The most common security mechanisms rely on the upper layers of the communications, which means that they depend on the use of the particular satellite and their capabilities are highly variable. However, it is expected that a secure SATCOM will be provided in the EU by the new GOVSATCOM programme, offering secure and cost-efficient communications capabilities to security and safety.

5.2.7.7. Tactical Data Links

Tactical Data Links (TDL) establish communications networks that allow their participating units to share their information, extending the coverage of their sensors, composing the global tactical situation, and providing them with the capacity for coordination and joint action. The main challenges of this type of communications networks are to maintain connectivity and ensure interoperability between units through different secure communications media, which act with different roles and use a variety of implementations, versions, and protocols. At the same time, these units must maintain strategic, operational and tactical objectives in interoperable joint operations.

TDL refers to the communication stack (Layer 1 – physical + layer 2 and layer 3 of the network + data protocol) that provides the means for the users /Nodes in the networks to exchange coherent tactical data. In the context of the use cases scenarios, the tactical data is translated into the assets data (FR positions and time; victims Position and status; assets position, time and status, etc). This technology establishes a series of formatted and specific messages, handshake protocols (error checking and confirmation) to exchange tactical data, which can be text, video or file. The TDL is secure due to its data cryptography and secure keys. Also, it provides not only an information layer and the construction of a common view of the tactical situation, but also enables the tactical action by providing messages to establish actions from the operational command.

In VALKYRIES, the concept of the TDL is that the joint forces should be able to have a common tactical protocol enabling the sharing of tactical objects data. In this case, tactical objects refer to:

- FR Vehicles: Ambulances; firefighter vehicles; drones; etc.
- FR units: FR person
- Victims: Person
- Threat objects/element: Dangerous elements like toxic container; collapsed structure; oil leaking boat

The tactical objects shall provide the information that enables the users to know its situational awareness:

- Position
- Status
- Kinematics
- Link with other elements
- Time of the information
- ID of the element
- Metadata

SECURITY CAPABILITIES

Military TDL are equipped with encryption and cypher security elements, with a high control process to provide the encryption key. Several developments are currently ongoing regarding keys distribution based on quantum keys.

TDL are radio based (RF) and make use of several techniques to ensure the datalink is secure against jamming, interference, signal spoofing and eavesdrop, including RF spread spectrum, frequency hopping, Cryptos, etc.

<i>Threat</i>	<i>Vulnerability</i>	<i>Impact</i>	<i>Risk</i>	<i>Primary Control</i>
Denial of Service	Low-High	High	Low-High	Layer specific mechanisms [1]
Eavesdrop	Low	High	Low	Cryptography [10]
Masquerade	Low	Very High	Medium	Trust System [11] and Cryptography
Modification	Low	High	Low	Cryptography
Traffic Analysis	High	Low	Medium	Traffic Obfuscation [12]

Figure 25 - Qualitative Risk Analysis for Tactical Networks (37)

For application other than defence, tactical communication and tactical networks also require security capability. Although facing different security constraints and requirements, security is a key capability not only to prevent private information to be accessed without control, but also to ensure that there is no damage inflicted to the operations, intentionally or not, to prevent networks congestion by unauthorized personnel, etc. Tactical communication typically operated in reserved frequencies, which usually require dedicated device terminals / radios that are not publicly accessed.

In both contexts, military and civil protection, tactical communication security is now seeing the integration of blockchain technology as a security option, but still require further understanding about its operational impact on fast development and events with limited network access.

5.2.8. Cybersecurity solutions applicable to promising technologies

The technological advance in recent years has generated a growth of new technologies for communication. These new approaches are interesting for their consideration and inclusion in emergency scenarios as back-up or complementary systems. Additionally, these systems also have cybersecurity considerations that need to be reviewed for their suitability in emergency scenarios.

5.2.8.1. Device-to-device (D2D) communications

The Device-to-device (D2D) communications are a new paradigm for enhancing network performance. D2D communications (38) allow to communicate terminals with each other, with or without additional network infrastructure, as well as to discover geographically close terminals which is extremely useful in emergency and search-and-rescue situations (39).

Between the D2D technologies, two main groups can be identified, depending on the industrial, scientific and medical (ISM) bands they work on:

- Unlicensed D2D, including techniques such as Bluetooth, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), Near Field Communication (NFC, based on RFID), Zigbee or WiFi Direct.
- Licensed D2D, including LTE Direct or Dedicated Short Range Communication (DSRC, also known as Vehicle-to-Vehicle V2V communication).

RFID

RFID is a mechanism that allows to read data from a RFID tag by triggering an electromagnetic interrogation pulse from a reader device. It can be used in multiple frequency bands, including ISM bands (e.g. mm-wave), UHF 433MHz for short range devices or microwave.

NFC

Set of low-speed communications protocols that enables communications over 4cm or less distance using a frequency of 13.56MHz. Such communications are applicable mainly to wearable id devices that can be used during the cases as -made products (40).

BLUETOOTH

Bluetooth is a short-range wireless technology that uses ISM bands between 2.402 GHz and 2.48GHz, commonly used to deploy personal area networks (PAN) to interchange information or connect devices. The Bluetooth standard was developed by the IEEE 802.15.1 group.

WI-FI DIRECT

Also known as Wi-Fi Peer-to-Peer (Wi-Fi P2P) is a Wi-Fi variant that allows to establish peer-to-peer communications. Unlike standard Wi-Fi, Wi-Fi Direct is not an IEEE standard as it has been developed and maintained by the Wi-Fi Alliance. Wi-Fi Direct allows one-to-one or one-to-many connections, and not all the connected devices need to be Wi-Fi direct certified.

DSRC

The DSRC (41) is a technology designed to support applications based on vehicular communication that works in the 5.9 GHz band (42). Between its known applications, the collision avoidance applications pose as the main desired capability. It is included in the IEEE 802.11p for the standardization for wireless access in vehicular environments (WAVE), as well as IEEE 1609.2, 1609.3 and 1609.4 for security, Network Services and Multi-Channel Operations.

LoRa

LoRa is a low power, long range, technology that uses RF free spectrum adaptable bands (according to the region) to implement a MAC control enabling a fast and simple IOT node to exchange data with other IOT nodes.

ZigBee

ZigBee is a technology developed by the ZigBee Alliance⁷ that adopts the IEEE 802.15.4 standard for the lower layers of the OSI model, i.e. the physical layer (PHY) and the medium access sublayer (MAC); and adds the network and application layer.

The main feature of ZigBee is its low power consumption, which makes it very suitable for devices that do not have a continuous power supply and require the use of external batteries. These devices can operate for more than 2 years on batteries. The features gained by ZigBee by adopting the IEEE 802.15.4 standard are as follows:

- Transmission rate from 20 kbit/s up to 250 kbit/s depending on the frequency. Use of free band frequencies: 2.4 GHz (like WiFi), 915MHz and 868MHz.
- 1, 10 or 16 5 MHz channels available depending on frequency.
- Short range, excluding mesh functionality between 10 and 200 metres.

SECURITY CAPABILITIES

The use of RFID might pose a risk for handling personal and sensitive data, such as medical information. To prevent skimming and eavesdropping, cryptographic methods must be used (43).

The main strength of NFC security relies on its extremely short range (4cm or less), but it is vulnerable against eavesdropping and data modifications. The applications that use NFC can use cryptographic solutions to secure the communication channels. Blockchain technology can address the cryptography gap, as well as provide additional means to secure communications carried out over the internet.

The Wi-Fi Direct standard includes WPA2 and WPS (44) security, which can be an issue when it is poorly implemented, but many manufacturers claim that this does not pose as a problem due to the short range (less than 100 meters) that Wi-Fi Direct offers (45).

The DSRC security is based in the IEEE 1609.2 (46), the standard for wireless access in vehicular environments – Security Services for Applications and Management Messages, which defines secure message formats and processing for WAVE, as well as administrative functions to support core security functions.

The security features of Bluetooth are like those of other wireless technologies. They include:

- 128-bit encryption.
- Robustness, given by:
 - Adaptive Frequency Hopping (AFH) (47).
 - Forward Error Correction (FEC), which allows the receiver to correct errors in transmission without the need for forwarding.
 - Narrow frequency channels, which means less interference from other devices.
 - Low sensitivity to reflections or multiple paths.
- Bluetooth security can have several modes of operation:
 - No security. All security mechanisms (authentication and encryption) are disabled. Devices allow all other devices to communicate with them.

- Service level security. Security is initialised after a channel is established between LM (Link Manager) and L2CAP level. Security policies and trust levels are applied independently, allowing access by applications with different requirements.
- Security at the link level. All routines are inside the Bluetooth chip, and nothing is transmitted in the clear. Security is initialised before a channel is established and all communications are encrypted. In addition to communications encryption, it uses a shared secret link key (PIN) between the two communicating devices and security at the MAC level. This methodology consists of sharing a secret Link Key between a pair of devices each time they communicate for the first time.

Transmission and data security are key issues in ZigBee technology. Therefore, ZigBee uses the IEEE 802.15.4 MAC sublayer security model, which specifies 4 security services:

- Use of AES 128bits encryption: ZigBee uses symmetric key cryptography and also allows network key rotation, which provides an extra level of security in the exchange of information, thus preventing devices outside the network from joining the network
- Access control of devices, maintains a list of 'checked' devices on the network
- Frame integration to protect data from being modified by others.
- Refresh sequences, to check that frames have not been replaced by other frames. The network controller checks these refresh frames and their value to see if they are the correct ones. to see if they are as expected.

In ZigBee, the keys are the basis of the security architecture and therefore the protection of the keys is fundamental. To understand this architecture a little more, the 128-bit keys used in this architecture are briefly described below:

- Master key: key from which the different link keys are generated. The security of the entire network depends on it, as the different services will use one-way variations of the link key to avoid security risks. Given the importance of this key, the initial master key has to be obtained by secure means either by transport or by pre-installation.
- Link key: provides security for point-to-point communications at the application level. It is a key known only to the elements involved in a particular communication.
- Network key: a key used at network level and known to all elements belonging to the network.

5.2.8.2. Low Power Wide Area Networks

Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN) comprise a set of technologies that offer wide coverage capabilities while keeping a low power and, thus, a low energetic consumption. However, for allowing these advantages, they have the limitation of a low bandwidth. In recent years, several technologies have emerged, such as LoRa and LoRaWAN, Sigfox, NB-IoT and NB-LTE, among others. They all share the same principles commented before, offering a particular implementation for solving a common problem. Based on that, and due to its popularity and capabilities, this section will only present detailed aspects of LoRa.

LoRa (short for Long Range) (48) is a proprietary spread spectrum modulation technique derived from chirp spread spectrum (CSS) technology. LoRa is a long range, low power wireless technology that has become a widely used standard for wireless platform of Internet of Things

(IoT). LoRa model acts at the first layer of the OSI protocol, so it stands as a physical link in the RF spectrum, used in Europe in the 863-870/873 MHz band.

This technology offers wide coverage, of around 2-5 km in urban areas and around 15 km in rural ones. However, the drawback of LoRa is the reduced throughput during data transmission, limited to 0.3 – 50 kbps. Based on that, this technology is interesting for devices that send reduced amounts of information every several seconds or minutes, such as those used in IoT environments.

This can be better understood attending to Figure 26, which indicates the communication flow between end user LoRa devices and applications that interact with the acquire information.

Figure 26 - LoRa Network data dissemination model

However, LoRa just focuses on physical layer transmission. Based on that, LoRaWAN is an LPWAN specification that covers the second layer of the OSI model. Thus, as a media access control technology, it allows the connectivity between LoRa devices, managing low level connection parameters, such as the channel to communicate, the bandwidth or the data encryption to be used. Thus, it allows for each manufacturer to establish the resilience level of the data transmitted, including the mechanisms to sustain the datalink resilience. In conclusion, LoRa devices and networks such as the LoRaWAN enable smart IoT applications and devices to be easily added in the network or to data clouds.

Figure 27 presents the layers of the LoRa network. The lower protocol setting (regional parameters) sets the physical link parameter according to the regional RF available frequencies/channels. LoRaWAN operates in unlicensed radio spectrum, and the channels and frequencies may change from region to region. On top of that, the classes implement the communications routines that supports LoRa WAN.

Figure 27 - LoRa Network Layers

At the network layer, LoRaWAN covers both the physical hardware that sits at the edge of the network to communicate with LoRaWAN nodes and the services that sit in the cloud. This includes the receiving, routing, processing data from, and routing data to the local LoRa network. Another important point is that LoRa does not directly connect on IP network, which can be done by having a LoRa nodes gateways to bridge with IP Networks. This can be observed in Figure 28, which presents the network architecture of a LoRa system, indicating the layers covered between each communication link.

Figure 28 - LoRa layers

SECURITY CAPABILITIES

LoRaWAN has been conceived with security in mind. It is based on standards, robust algorithms and end-to-end encryption. Particularly, it provides mutual authentication between the LoRaWAN network and end-devices as part of the network join procedure. For that, it uses over-the-air authentication during as well as AES-CMAC. Thus, two session keys are derived, one for providing integrity and another for end-to-end encryption. Additionally, LoRaWAN MAC and application messaging are origin authenticated. All of this provides integrity and confidentiality protection against malicious actors.

Figure 29 summarizes the security measures performed for each communication link between elements of the LoRaWAN architecture.

Figure 29 - LoRaWAN security summary (49)

5.2.8.3. WiMax communications

WiMAX (Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access) wireless technology is a so-called last-mile technology that allows data to be received by microwave and retransmitted by radio waves. WiMAX networks emerged as an alternative to cable to bring communications to isolated rural areas where physical infrastructure was very expensive. This technology reduces equipment and environmental impact in rural areas, as only antennas are needed, often in locations shared with television or mobile phone antennas.

WiMAX has several advantages, among which are the broadband services it offers in areas where the deployment of cable or fibre has very high costs per user (rural areas) due to the low population density. This communications technology adopts the IEEE 802.16 standard and there are 2 variants:

- WiMAX (802.16d-2004) or "fixed WiMAX": for low population density areas.
- WiMAX (802.16e-2005) or "mobile WiMAX": for applications requiring high bandwidth in both directions. bandwidth in both transmission directions and in mobility

SECURITY CAPABILITIES

WiMAX defines a security sublayer specifically dedicated to cover the three basic principles of network security (confidentiality, authentication and integrity) in order to provide users with the most secure navigation possible within their network. WiMAX bases its security system on two principles:

- Authentication: This method guarantees users secure access to the network, preventing other unauthorised users from using the wireless connection. Two authentication processes are defined in the IEEE 802.16-2009 standard:

- OSA (Open System Authentication): the client makes an authentication request associated with its MAC address, which is followed by a response from the Base Station (BS) with the acceptance or denial of the request. The BS performs only and optionally a filtering by MAC address
- SKA (Shared Key Authentication): is used in shared key processes, where both ends must know the keys to guarantee a more secure authentication. For shared key authentication WiMAX defines the PKM (Privacy Key Management) protocol so that a Subscriber Station (SS) can exchange keys and obtain authorisation from the Base Station. In addition to this task, the PKM protocol also takes care of key refreshing, periodic re-authorisation, etc. The following describes the process that the PKM protocol follows to perform authentication between the BS and the SS
- Encryption: After the Base Station authorises the User Station, an encryption mechanism is also necessary to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of the data shared between the two. For this purpose, the SS sends to the BS a request for encryption keys called TEK (Traffic Encryption Keys), which are sent by the BS in a reply message. These messages are in turn encrypted with a key known to both parties. The algorithm used for the encryption of TEKs can be of 3 types: 3DES (Triple Data Encryption Standard), AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) and RSA (Rivest, Shamir and Adleman). Once TEKs are known, various techniques can be used for data encryption: CBC (DES), CBC (AES), CTR (AES), CCM (AES), M (AES). Some of the advantages of the encryption mechanisms implemented by WiMAX over other technologies are the following:
 - Robust algorithms
 - Allows independent encryption for each data stream
 - Supports dynamic key generation with variable lifetimes

5.2.9. Security network-level

The section addresses all currently available and applicable network security. From the perspective of network security protocols and deployable protection systems to ensure network robustness and reliability (see Figure 30), closely related to the architecture presented in VALKYRIES D2.3 deliverable (14).

Figure 30 - Security elements in a real topology

Security is a critical requirement for systems that supported first aid responders in emergency situations. To overcome the inherent lack of security in standard network protocols, many real-time security protocols have been developed for network security ensuring basic aspects of security such as privacy, origin authentication, message integrity, and non-repudiation. The main characteristics of the applicable network layer security protocols for critical systems used in emergency scenarios are discussed briefly in the next three subsections.

5.2.9.1. SSL/TLS

Secure Socket Layer (SSL) and Transport Layer Security (TLS) are security protocols in the Transport Layer. Currently, the two protocols are considered as one, under the name SSL/TLS, after the SSL standardization was passed over to Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) by the Netscape consortium.

SSL was designed to provide an encrypted end-to-end data path between a client and a server regardless of platform or OS. Secure and authenticated services are provided through data encryption, server authentication, message integrity, and client authentication for a TCP connection through HTTP, LDAP, or POP3 application layers. It was originally developed by Netscape.

The SSL objectives were to secure and authenticate data paths between servers and clients. These objectives were achieved through several services that included data encryption, server, and client authentication, and message integrity:

- **Data encryption:** To protect data in transport between the client and the server from interception and could be read only by the intended receiver.
- **Server and client authentication:** The SSL protocol uses standard public key encryption to authenticate the communicating parties to each other.
- **Message integrity:** Achieved using session keys so that data cannot be either intentionally or unintentionally tampered with.

These services offer reliable end-to-end secure services to Internet TCP connections and are based on an SSL architecture consisting of two layers (see Figure 31): the top layer, just below the application layer that consists of three protocols – the SSL Handshake protocol, the SSL Change Cipher Spec protocol, and the SSL Alert protocol. Below these protocols is the second SSL layer, the SSL Record Protocol layer, just above the TCP layer.

Figure 31 - SSL Architecture Diagram

TLS version 1.0 was an evolved SSL 3.0. TLS was charged with providing security and data integrity at the transport layer between two applications. The following additional features have been added to the new SSL/TLS standard:

- **Interoperability:** Ability to exchange TLS parameters by either party, with no need for one party to know the other's TLS implementation details.
- **Expandability:** To plan for future expansions and accommodation of new protocols.

TLS 1.3 is the latest version of the TLS protocol. TLS 1.3 dropped support for older, less secure cryptographic features, and it sped up TLS handshakes, among other improvements (50).

SSL/TLS is commonly used by web browsers to protect connections between web applications and web servers. Many other TCP-based protocols use TLS/SSL as well, including email (SMTP/POP3), instant messaging (XMPP), FTP, VoIP, VPN, and others.

TLS and SSL are the standard protocols used for securing stream-based TCP traffic. Datagram Transport Layer Security (DTLS) is based on the Transport Layer Security (TLS) protocol and built on top of the User Datagram Protocol (UDP). DTLS is well-suited for securing applications and services that are delay sensitive.

5.2.9.2. IPsec

Internet Protocol Security (IPsec) is a suit of authentication and encryption protocols designed to address the lack of security for IP-based networks. It is the most common network layer security control, typically used to encrypt Internet Protocol (IP) traffic between hosts in a network and to create a virtual private network (VPN). It runs transparently to transport layer and application layer protocols.

Depending on its implementation and configuration it can provide any combination of the following types of protection (51):

- **Confidentiality:** IPsec can ensure that data cannot be read by unauthorized parties. This is accomplished by encrypting data using a cryptographic algorithm.

- **Integrity:** IPsec can determine if data has been modified (intentionally or unintentionally) during transit. The integrity of data can be assured by generating a message authentication code (MAC) value. If the data is altered and the MAC is recalculated, the old and new MACs will differ.
- **Peer Authentication:** Each IPsec endpoint confirms the identity of the other IPsec endpoint with which it wants to communicate, ensuring that the data is being sent from the expected host. This prevents spoofed IP addresses.
- **Replay Protection:** The same data is not delivered multiple times. However, IPsec does not ensure that data is delivered in the exact order in which it is sent.
- **Traffic Analysis Protection:** A person monitoring network traffic does not know which parties are communicating, how often communications are occurring, or how much data is being exchanged. However, the number of packets being exchanged can be counted.
- **Access Control:** IPsec endpoints can perform filtering to ensure that only authorized IPsec users can access network resources. IPsec endpoints can also allow or block certain types of network traffic, such as allowing Web server access but denying file sharing.

IPsec is a set of protocols, it consists of the following main components (52):

- **Authentication Header (AH):** The AH protocol provides source authentication and data integrity, but no confidentiality. AH is an older method for IPsec transport of non-encrypted data. This method is no longer recommended by the NIST guidance (51).
- **Encapsulating Security Protocol (ESP):** The ESP protocol provides authentication, data integrity, and confidentiality. If only integrity protection is needed without encryption, the ESP protocol can use NULL encryption, instead of AH protocol. ESP encrypts the IP header and the payload for each packet – unless transport mode is used, in which case it only encrypts the payload. ESP adds its own header and a trailer to each data packet.
- **Security Association (SA):** SA refers to a number of protocols used for negotiating encryption keys and algorithms. A security association is a unidirectional security arrangement defining a set of items and procedures that must be shared between the two communicating entities in order to protect the communication process.

One of the most common SA protocols is Internet Key Exchange (IKE). IKE is the protocol used by IPsec to negotiate IPsec connection settings; authenticate endpoints to each other; define the security parameters of IPsec-protected connections; negotiate session keys; and manage, update, and delete IPsec-protected communication channels. The current version is IKEv2.

Approved by the NIST (51) publication, which provides practical guidance to organizations on implementing security services based on IPsec so that they can mitigate the risks associated with transmitting sensitive information across networks, cryptographic algorithms, and their options for using in IPsec and IKE are described in Table 13.

Table 13 - IKE options

Option	Recommended	Expected
IKE		
Version	IKEv2	
IKEv2 exchanges	All	
IKEv1 exchanges	Main Mode, Quick Mode	

Option	Recommended	Expected
IKE		
Encryption	AES-GCM, AES-CTR, AES-CBC, AESCCM (128, 192, 256-bit keys)	
Integrity/Pseudorandom Function (PRF)	HMAC-SHA256, HMAC-SHA384, HMAC-SHA512	HMAC-SHA-3
Diffie-Hellman (DH) group	DH 14 to DH 21 RFC 3526 and RFC 5114	DH 31 and DH 32, RFC 8031
Peer authentication ⁴	RSA, DSA, and ECDSA with 128-bit security strength (for example, RSA with 3072-bit or larger key)	RSA, DSA, and ECDSA with less than 112 bits of security strength
Lifetime	24 hours	
IPsec		
Mode	Tunnel mode, Transport mode	
Protocol	ESP, IPComp	
Version	IPsec-v3	
Encryption	AES-GCM, AES-CTR, AES-CBC, AESCCM (128, 192, 256-bit keys)	
Integrity	HMAC-SHA256, HMAC-SHA384, HMAC-SHA512, AES-GMAC	HMAC-SHA-3
Perfect Forward Secrecy (PFS)	Same or stronger DH as initial IKE DH	
Lifetime	8 hours	

Table 13 - IKE options

ESP is the core IPsec protocol. ESP has two modes: tunnel and transport (51).

In tunnel mode (see Figure 31), a new packet is constructed containing the (original) IP packet being sent through the tunnel by:

1. Placing an ESP header and trailer around the original IP header and its payload.
2. Encrypting the original header, payload, and ESP trailer.
3. Computing and Integrity Check Value (ICV) over the ESP header and the encrypted data.
4. Placing the ICV at the end of the packet being constructed.
5. Adding a new IP header to the beginning of the packet.

The ICV computation does not include the new IP header. The new IP header lists the endpoints of the ESP tunnel (such as two IPsec gateways) as the source and destination of the packet and contains the entire, now-encrypted, original packet as its payload. Because of this, tunnel mode can be used with all VPN architectures described in the next section. The tunnel mode can encrypt and protect the integrity of both the data and the original IP header for each packet. Encrypting the original IP header and its payload protects their confidentiality; encrypting the original IP header conceals the nature of the communications, such as the actual source or destination of the packet, protocol, and ports used that would indicate which application is likely being used. The ICV is used to detect any changes to the data over which the ICV is computed.

ESP tunnel mode is used for gateway-to-gateway deployments, remote access VPNs, and various network virtualization deployments.

Figure 31 - ESP Tunnel Mode Packet (53)

ESP transport mode is used for host-to-host deployments within data centres, local networks, and virtual machines where no NAT is deployed. In transport mode (see Figure 32), ESP uses the original IP header instead of creating a new one. The ESP payload and trailer are encrypted, and an ICV is computed over the ESP header and the encrypted data. Integrity protection is not provided for the IP header. The overhead of the transport mode is less than that of the tunnel mode because it does not have to create an entire new IP header.

Figure 32 - ESP Transport Mode Packet (53)

5.2.9.3. VPN

Virtual Private Network (VPN) (54) is a private network that makes use of the public telecommunication infrastructure by adding security procedures over the unsecure communication channels. Because a VPN can be used over existing networks, such as the Internet, it can facilitate the secure transfer of sensitive data across public networks. VPN must implement the following activities:

- **IP encapsulation:** This involves enclosing TCP/IP data packets within another packet with an IP address of either a firewall or a server that acts as a VPN endpoint. This encapsulation of host IP address helps in hiding the host.
- **Encryption:** It is done on the data part of the packet. The encryption can be done either in transport mode, which encrypts data at the time of generation, or tunnel mode, which encrypts and decrypts data during transmission encrypting both data and header.
- **Authentication:** It involves creating an encryption domain that includes authenticating computers and data packets for public encryption.

VPNs generally rely on both symmetric and asymmetric cryptography algorithms. Asymmetric cryptography is used to provide peer authentication; symmetric encryption is used to protect the actual data transfers because of its relative efficiency.

There are three primary models for VPN architectures, as follows (51):

- **Gateway-to-gateway:** It connects two networks by deploying a gateway to each network and establishing a VPN connection between the two gateways. Communications between hosts on the two networks are then passed through the VPN connection, which provides protection for them. No protection is provided between each host and its local gateway. The gateway-to-gateway is most often used when connecting two secured networks, such as a branch office and headquarters, over the Internet. Gateway-to-gateway VPNs are typically transparent to users and do not involve installing or configuring any software on clients or servers.
- **Host-to-gateway:** It connects hosts on various networks with hosts on the organization's network by deploying a gateway to the organization's network and permitting external hosts to establish individual VPN connections to that gateway. Communications are protected between the hosts and the gateway, but not between the gateway and the destination hosts within the organization. The host-to-gateway model is most often used when connecting hosts on unsecured networks to resources on secured networks, such as linking traveling employees to headquarters over the Internet. Host-to-gateway VPNs are typically not transparent to users because each user must authenticate before using the VPN and each host must have VPN client software installed and configured.
- **Host-to-host:** It connects hosts to a single target host by deploying VPN software to each host and configuring the target host to receive VPN connections from the other hosts. This is the only VPN model that provides protection for data throughout its transit. It is most often used when a small number of users need to use or administer a remote system that requires the use of insecure protocols and can be updated to provide VPN services. The host-to-host model is resource-intensive to implement and maintain because it requires configuration on each host involved, including the target.

The most common use of IPsec implementations is providing VPN services. A VPN can be established even within a single network to protect particularly sensitive communications from other parties on the same network or deploy a mesh of IPsec connections between all nodes in a single network so that no unencrypted data ever appears on the network.

The main alternatives to IPsec for particular needs and environments VPNs are: Data link layer VPN protocols, such as PPTP, L2TP, and L2F; transport layer VPN protocols, primarily TLS/SSL; and application layer VPN protocols, including PGP and SSH (51).

Data link layer VPNs can protect various network protocols, so they are often used for non-IP protocols. Data link layer VPNs are most commonly used on top of PPP to secure modem-based connections, although PPP actually encrypts the traffic.

PPTP protects communications between a PPTP-enabled client and a PPTP-enabled server, and uses GRE to transport data between them. L2TP protects communications between an L2TP-enabled client and an L2TP-enabled server, and uses its own tunnelling protocol over UDP port 1701 to transport data. L2F protects communications between two network devices, such as ISP network access servers and VPN gateways. It is transparent to users, but it does not protect communications between user's systems and ISPs.

Transport layer VPNs most commonly provide security for communications with individual HTTP-based applications, and can also protect other applications' communications. Each application server must include support for the VPN protocol, as must the client portion of each application. Because all major Web browsers include support for the TLS/SSL protocol, users typically do not need to install client software or reconfigure their systems.

TLS/SSL proxy servers provide network, transport, or application layer VPNs (depending on the configuration). Typically, remote users connect to the proxy server using TLS-protected HTTP and authenticate themselves; the user can then access designated applications indirectly through the proxy server, which establishes its own separate connections with the application servers. Non-Web-based applications can be accessed by deploying special programs to clients and then tunnelling the application data over HTTPS or another protocol. Unlike IPsec, TLS proxy servers cannot protect IP header characteristics, such as IP addresses.

Application layer VPNs protect part or all of the communications for a single application. For example, e-mail encryption conceals the content in the body of an e-mail, but not the e-mail headers. Protection is either provided by using a separate program (e.g., a standalone file encryption program) or by building the application layer VPN protocol into the application itself. If neither of these is feasible, a different layer VPN may be needed.

5.2.9.4. Cybersecurity protection system

Despite the cybersecurity solutions provided by current technologies or network protocols, it is necessary to have other cybersecurity protection mechanisms. In this case, it is advisable to have devices that monitor the information transmitted on the network or guarantee the security of the nodes to avoid malicious requests or actors (e.g., use of firewalls, IDS, or proxies).

NETWORK MONITORING (SYSLOG)

Network monitoring is the process of constantly monitoring a computer network for problems such as slow traffic or failure of any component. To monitor traffic, we need to use network monitoring software and hardware tools. Tools that are always scanning the network and track various aspects of a network in real time to catch up early and prevent any kind of failure as well as provide status updates. Those tools are designed to automatically notify network administrators via email or phone when a problem occurs. Not all network monitoring tools are the same, may differ depends on the problems we want to monitor and the network security we want to provide. Real time monitoring is critical to maintaining the network integrity. The benefits of network monitoring are:

- **Visibility:** Easy to understand of all connected devices across the network is important to quickly identify failures and problems before outages occur
- **Automation and better use of IT resources:** Automatic critical tasks leading to higher utilization of critical IT resources
- **Warning indication:** Network monitoring provides early warning indication giving a heads-up indicating the need for upgrading or adding capacity to given network components. Tools can give us the ability to identify security threats faster
- **Identifying unexpected behaviours:** Tools can identify unexpected spikes in network traffic that can indicate a problem brewing due to cyberattacks

Network failures can affect the whole IT execution and cause accessibility issues over the organization. Network monitoring has a few critical benefits to the organization by empowering early discovery issues including:

- Cost savings by reducing downtime and speeding remediation
- Early problem detection that leads to prevent performance problems
- Network security enhancements
- Rogues' application usage can be caught

Thus, it is necessary the use of a System Logging Protocol (Syslog). It is a server process network devices can use a standard message format to communicate with a logging server. It was designed specifically to make it easy to monitor network devices. Devices can use Syslog agent to send out notification messages under a wide range of specific conditions. Syslog monitoring can improve the organization's maintenance, security and help troubleshoot issues quickly.

The most important thing of syslog is that the log server can monitor a huge amount of syslog events via log files. Routers, switches, firewalls and server can generate log messages as well as printers and other devices.

Beyond simply collecting syslog messages, syslog monitoring provides data filtering and management. Cause of the huge amount of syslog data, syslog server needs a large database which leads to management and filtering needs. Management and filtering data can be done with syslog monitoring software that enables the server to automatically generate alerts, alarms and notifications. The importance of filtering allows a sysadmin to easily call up files from certain source, such as firewall, for a specific period. Syslog data also can be used for detailed reporting and to generate diagrams to determine the structure of the network.

FIREWALL

A firewall is a network security device that monitors incoming and outgoing traffic and decides whether to allow or block specific traffic based on a set of pre-defined security restrictions. There are different types of firewalls:

- **Proxy firewall:** This is an upstream type of firewall appliance that acts as a gateway between one network and another for a given application.
- **Stateful inspection firewall:** A stateful inspection firewall allows traffic to be blocked according to criteria based on state, port and protocol. It monitors all activity from the opening of a connection until it is closed. Filtering decisions are made based on both administrator-defined restrictions and context.
- **Unified Threat Management (UTM) Firewall:** An UTM appliance typically independently combines the functions of a stateful inspection firewall, intrusion prevention and anti-virus

There are different methods of traffic filtering:

- **Firewall policies:** These allow blocking or allowing certain types of network traffic not specified in an exception policy. The firewall suspends any communication request that does not come from the internal network or the system itself so that nobody will be able to scan the network, from the outside only the IP address of the firewall is visible, no internal resources within the network are visible.

- **Anti-Spam Firewall:** This service protects against spam, phishing, the technology comes from recurrent pattern detection (RPD)
- **Antivirus Firewall:** Service that some Firewalls incorporate, it is the first line of defence to protect the internal network against attacks coming from the Internet or WAN link
- **Content Filtering:** Allows administrators through a system of exclusion rules to easily block certain types of web content without having to manually block each individual URL. Inappropriate websites and social networking websites are blocked quickly and easily.
- **WAP Managed Service:** Allows control of WAP devices and manage usage for authorised users and defined services.
- **DPI Services:** This is the name given to Deep Package Inspection (DPI) procedures. It allows the administrator to control specific applications known as Trojans and backdoor applications that can infiltrate your internal network.

IDS

An Intrusion Detection System, or IDS, is a security tool that tries to detect or monitor attempts to compromise the security of a computer system. To carry out this task, their defence relies on more than classic access control, as they analyse network traffic and examine packets, looking for pre-defined patterns that may allow detection of attacks at an early stage.

IDSs are designed to deal with intruders, which can range from a hacker trying to compromise the integrity, confidentiality, or availability of a resource, to an unauthorised user trying to obtain privileges that do not belong to him (55).

A robust IDS must fulfil certain purposes in any network environment:

- The ability to run continuously without the need for human supervision, i.e. they must be configured in such a way that their regular work is transparent to the operators of the computer environment
- The system should not place an excessive burden on the system, if it has a high false positive rate, or has excessive logs (which record detected activities), operators may choose to ignore it and security-compromising situations may be overlooked.
- Good adaptability is desirable, i.e., the ability to adapt quickly to changes in the working environment, as IT systems are not static. Finally, high fault tolerance is always desirable, as well as optimal responsiveness to unexpected situations.

IDSs can detect an intrusion in different situations and in different ways. That is why they are classified in three different ways, although the main ones are those that distinguish them according to which systems they monitor and how they do it.

Depending on which systems monitor:

HIDS: Host-Based. These were the first IDS to appear in the computer security world. It protects only the machine on which it runs, so a HIDS would be needed to monitor each individual system. To carry out their task, they use log analysers (which record the activities carried out on the system), generated by different applications or by the operating system kernel itself, paying attention to suspicious logs.

NIDS: Network. This type of system directly monitors the packets circulating in the same network, specifically within the same collision domain, in search of elements that denote an attack against any of the systems located in it. To do this, at least one network interface of that sensor machine must work in promiscuous mode, thus analysing all the frames that circulate through a segment of the network (whether or not they are destined for the equipment in question) in search of patterns suspicious of compromising security.[5] To analyse these patterns, it is sometimes enough to look at the TCP/IP network frames, since there are certain values that can represent a real attack with a high probability.

Depending on how they act:

Anomaly detection. They identify as an intrusion any excessive deviation from the usual behaviour of a system, based on the concepts of negative knowledge and positive knowledge. The system itself can analyse the data available to it to obtain statistical elements, such as averages or variances, with which it defines a user behaviour profile, which is updated and compared with the last recorded profile, in search of deviations.

Misuse detection. This consists of specifying possible intrusions that may compromise the security of a system and waiting for them to occur. So-called expert systems can be used, in which intrusions are described as if-then rules, based on the analysis of the logs of any Unix system. For example, if a user with an open session on one machine (and a log is found on the system that records it) tries to log in from another machine, the action defined in the rule would be performed, usually alerting the security officer.

PROXY

A proxy server operates as a middleman between user and the internet. Proxy servers provide multiple levels of operations, functionalities, security, and privacies depending on the use case and needs or company's policies. If someone using a proxy server, internet traffic and data flows through the proxy server on its way to the requested address. The request then comes back through that same proxy server and then proxy server forwards the data received from the website to you.

Every computer on the needs to have a unique internet protocol (IP) address. A proxy server is basically a computer on the internet with its unique IP address. Let's see a standard example of how proxy server works:

1. A user enters a website's URL.
2. The proxy server receives the user's request.
3. The proxy server forwards the request to the web server.
4. The web server sends a response back to the proxy server.
5. Lastly the proxy server forwards the response(data) to the user.

A proxy server can change your IP address, so the web server doesn't know exactly where you are in the world. It can encrypt your data, so your data is unreadable in transit. And lastly proxy server can block access to certain web pages, based on IP address. Modern proxy servers have much more utilities than forwarding web requests, in the form of data security and network performance. Proxy servers act as a firewall and web data filter, providing shared network connections, and cache data to speed up common requests. Lastly, proxy servers can provide a high level of privacy (56).

There are several reasons organization and individuals use a proxy server:

- To control internet usage
- Bandwidth savings
- Speed improvement
- Provide privacy
- Improved security
- Blocked resources access
- Web filtering
- Web acceleration

Proxy servers are generally classified according to their purpose in the network:

- **Transparent Proxy:** A transparent proxy tells website that it is a proxy server, and it will still pass along your IP address, identifying you to the webserver
- **Anonymous Proxy:** An anonymous proxy will identify itself as a proxy, but it won't pass your IP address to the website – this helps prevent identity stolen and keep your browsing data private.
- **Distorting Proxy:** A distorting proxy server passes along a false IP address for you while identifying itself as a proxy. This serves similar purposes as the anonymous proxy, but by passing a false IP address, you can appear to be from a different location to get around content restrictions.
- **High Anonymity Proxy:** High anonymity proxy servers periodically change the IP address they present to the web server, making it very difficult to keep track of what traffic belongs to who. High anonymity proxies like TOR Network, is the most private and secure way to read the internet.

These proxy servers operate based on the protocol they implement. Among the most common are:

- **Socks Proxy Server:** This type of proxy server provides a connection to a particular server. Depending on socks protocols, this type of server allows the multilayering of various data types such as TCP or UDP
- **FTP Proxy Server:** This type of proxy server caches FTP requests' traffic and uses the concept of relaying.
- **HTTP Proxy Server:** This proxy was developed to process a one-way request to the web pages using HTTP protocols.
- **HTTPS/SSL Proxy Server:** This type of server was developed using the concept of TCP relaying being used in the SOCKS proxy protocol to allow Web Pages requests. HTTPS protocol has today become the standard for most websites and online services.

HTTPS or SSL proxy is any proxy server that uses the SSL protocol. SSL proxy using encryption and decryption between the client and the server, without either of them being able to detect the proxy's presence. SSL encryption gives you the benefit that your connection cannot be intercepted, and all modern browsers will give a warning if you try to connect to a website without an SSL certificate.

5.2.10. Mechanisms for ensuring system availability

Availability of critical systems such as those used in emergency scenarios is vital for ensuring a proper actuation. In this sense, this section presents different strategies to offer availability in this kind of scenarios.

5.2.10.1. Backup functions (full, differential and incremental)

In a federated approach each application is responsible for the backup of its own data, according to its own technical capabilities and organisation policies. However, the information exchanged, including the metadata, may be required to be backed-up according to its the mission goals, for the following purposes:

- **Operational sustainability of the SIGRUN data:** resilience of the federation approach is a critical success factor, and when a subset of the SIGRUN solution leaves or enters the SIGRUN network due to connectivity issues, it may require resynchronization of the elapsed data during the absence period. This require recent data to be stored and available for re-synchronization.
- **Data auditing:** to support the auditing of private, confidential, or protected data, the metadata of the exchanged data should be stored and backed-up for future assessment.
- **Learning process:** Learning from experience is an improvement process widely experienced by First Responders' organizations by storing and back-up the events data enables its post event analysis and lessons learn.
- Recover from data deleted due to intentional wrongfully assess and deleted data.

According to the ISO 27001, backup policy is part of the standard and protects the organization from data loss. Apart from having the data backed up, it shall define the backup location, frequency, data retention, and what measures are implemented to keep backup data secure (applies to both on-premise and cloud backups).

SIGRUN backup functions do not stores the full applications data but only the exchanged data/metadata. Each application should provide its auto backup capability and policy. All the data exchanged is relevant and will be stored in the following means:

- Metadata: all messages' metadata shall be stored in the BLC network
- Transactional data: all transactional data shall be stored in the BLC network.
- Non metadata: stored on backup server cluster.
 - Orchestration data (SIGRUN DATA)
 - Files transferred.
 - Stream data
- Private data: not stored, only metadata is stored.

With all this, data backup policies are:

- Data stored in the BLC network is not required to establish additional backups, as the BLC network already provides, natively, the way to store the data in a secure, reliable and with integrity way.
- The backup of the other data, streaming, images, text, non-transactional data, etc, is stored and backup in dedicated servers cluster, enabling redundancy of the backup. The physical location of these servers is not relevant, and the data shall be stored in the cloud.

- **Incremental Back-up:** Because the data is stored in a cluster of servers, it is not required to perform full-backup of the data available at a certain time. So, the back-ups will store only the new (Incremental) data. Another advantage of the incremental back-up is that consumes less bandwidth compared to the full or differential backup.

5.2.10.2. *Disaster Recovery Plan*

Disaster recovery Plan serves the purpose of ensuring that critical data is not lost and can be recovered in case of system failure, wrongfully erase data, intentionally or not, data ransom, etc.

In an MCI event, the data is backed-up according to the backup policies (see above section), and to ensure recovery of the data the back-ups and all the data should be stored in a recoverable, and secure way. Note that Disaster Recovery Plan does not ensure data recording failure.

Furthermore, MCI events are fast development situations where the data time validity usually tends to have a short period of validity. In case of the need to apply a data recovery procedure, the usability of that data is limited to the current situation. So, in MCI event the recovery Plan should consider the data to have two goals that may require recovery. An important goal metric is the definition of the acceptable down-time and time recovery:

- **Operational Data recover:**
 - Purpose: To ensure that tactical and operational data is recovered in case of data loss.
 - Acceptable downtime availability: minutes.
- **Post event data recover:**
 - Purpose: To ensure that in case of data loss during, or after the MCI event, the data can be recovered for post event analysis.
 - Acceptable downtime availability: days.

The DRP for MCI event shall define several policies to ensure the execution of the recovery goals:

- **Personnel:** Every disaster recovery plan must detail the personnel who are responsible for the execution of the DR plan and make provisions for individual people becoming unavailable.
- **IT inventory:** An updated IT inventory must list the details about the hardware and software assets, as well as any cloud services necessary, including their level of criticality.
- **Backup procedures:** The DRP must set forth how each data resource is backed up – exactly where, the devices, the responsibilities, and how the team should recover each resource from backup. (See above chapter)
- **Disaster recovery procedures:** These specific procedures, distinct from backup procedures, should detail all emergency responses, including last-minute backups, mitigation procedures, limitation of damages, and eradication of cybersecurity threats.
- **Disaster recovery sites:** Any robust disaster recovery plan should designate a hot disaster recovery site. Located remotely, all data can be frequently backed up to or replicated at a hot disaster recovery site – an alternative data centre holding all critical systems. This way, when disaster strikes, operations can be instantly switched over to the hot site.

Under SIGRUN the sites are to be located according to the architecture to establish the VALKYRIES D2.3 deliverable (14).

Following best practices to ensure a disaster recovery plan includes detailed restoration procedures for recovering from a loss of full systems operations. In other words, every detail to get each aspect of the operation back online should be in the plan (57). VALKYRIES SIGRUN solution is a federated system, therefore the DRP is composed of two different components:

- Data entity owned: The data that belongs and is used only under the specific organization and application within the SIGRUN federation. The DRP for the entity owned data is of responsibility of the entity.
- SIGRUN shared data: The data shared under SIGRUN, the core services data and data generated under SIGRUN shall be under SIGRUN DRP responsibility

A significant part of the data created, used, shared and assessed, under SIGRUN refers to privacy data or data that require governmental legal coverage before being shared with other countries. Therefore, the data backed-up and for recovery must comply with the requirements laid down by these constraints.

Blockchain is a distributed operated network, with peer data check and validity. The DRP must specifically address the way BLC data is able to be restored. In this case, restoring does not refer to the actual recovery of the data stored in the BLC chain, but to define how the data backup up in other systems are coherent recovery and operationally recovered to continue to operate the Blockchain.

5.2.10.3. *Distributed database server for continuous data distribution*

Part of the SIGRUN resilience approach includes the architecture design of the services and IT infrastructure that support the SIGRUN. As mentioned before the SIGRUN architecture encompasses solutions such as Blockchain network (for metadata store and share) and other services for the remaining data shared needs.

Blockchain network already provides natively its own data resilience model, in the way data is stored, recorded and secured.

For the remaining data the SIGRUN architecture established a number of dedicated databases and servers to enable the sharing of stream, files, and non-transactional data. It includes:

- Brokers databases
- Data stream services
- Call services

For these elements, and to improve the level of resilience, mainly during MCI event operations, the architecture includes redundancy of the databases and of the data sharing mechanisms:

Figure 33 - Redundancy of Data Brokers. From D2.3 (14).

Figure 34 - Redundancy of data stream servers. From D2.3 (14).

This approach improves the services availability, better management of the load balancing of the services, improve responsiveness of the system and provides redundancy in case of malfunction or connectivity loss of one of the clustered elements, thus improving the resilience of the system.

5.2.11. Analysis of T4.2 questionnaire

The questionnaire for this task mainly focused on the cybersecurity aspects and capabilities of communications that the organisations actively used. The most relevant aspects asked are subsequently presented:

- Use of security measurements during the transmission of communication in emergency situations (e.g., VPN, HTTPS, IPSec, proxys)
- Admissibility to transmit sensitive information without security mechanisms in situations with dramatic limitations of network capabilities
- Prioritisation of authorities or first responders to send data.
- Privacy constrains and data protection regulations applicable in the country.
- Use of additional technology to increase communication coverage.
- Use of security systems (e.g., IDS, firewalls, honeypots)
- List of communication technologies used in emergency scenarios.
- List of limitations identified in the communication technologies used.
- Use of satellite networks other than geolocation services.
- Utilisation of ad-hoc systems to overcome coverage issues (e.g., drones, air balloons)
- Applicability of emergent communication technologies (e.g., LPWAN, D2D)
- List of limitations when using TETRA and, particularly, concerning TETRA repeaters and gateways
- Feasibility to deploy additional antennas to improve coverage.
- Difference in connectivity between metropolitan and rural areas
- Specific organisms in charge of improving coverage in emergencies.

After indicating the key aspects covered by the survey for this task, we present the most common results obtained for each of the questions.

	Most common answer in the Survey
Use of security measurements during the transmission of communication in emergency situations	Yes
Admissibility to transmit sensitive information without security mechanisms in situations with dramatic limitations of network capabilities.	Yes

	Most common answer in the Survey
Prioritisation of authorities or first responders to send data.	Yes
Privacy constrains and data protection regulations applicable in the country.	GDPR
Use of additional technology to increase communication coverage.	Dedicated communications vehicle
Use of security systems (e.g., IDS, firewalls, honeypots).	Yes
List of communication technologies used in emergency scenarios.	Mobile networks, TETRA, VHF
List of limitations identified in the communication technologies used.	Limited network coverage
Use of satellite networks other than geolocation services.	No
Utilisation of ad-hoc systems to overcome coverage issues (e.g., drones, air balloons).	No
Applicability of emergent communication technologies (e.g., LPWAN, D2D).	Yes, No
List of limitations when using TETRA and, particularly, concerning TETRA repeaters and gateways.	Data transfer rate, cell saturation
Feasibility to deploy additional antennas to improve coverage.	Yes
Difference in connectivity between metropolitan and rural areas.	Yes
Specific organisms in charge of improving coverage in emergencies.	National civil defence, Civil protection, telecommunication providers

Table 14 - Results obtained for Task 4.2.

Considering the previous answers, the agencies responding the questionnaire highlighted the importance that secure communications have in emergency scenarios. Although most institutions use security capabilities in their communications, there is still room for improvement as a substantial number of entities indicated they use no security at all.

Additionally, it is relevant to note that most responders indicated that, in case of an emergency, data transmission has a higher priority than the protection of the communications. This is relevant for this work package since it helps understand the needs of these organizations and define a better analysis of the capabilities of existing and next-generation communication technologies.

Additionally, there is a wide variety of communication technologies used, such as mobile networks, TETRA or traditional VHF radio. Thus, this questionnaire highlights a need for interoperability between technologies, also indicating that agencies are open for the inclusion of emerging technologies that could improve identified limitations, highlighted in terms of network coverage, particularly in rural areas. Moreover, and despite the ability of most of these agencies to extend the network capability in emergency situations, there is still room for the inclusion and integration of novel ad-hoc systems, such as drones.

5.3. Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies

5.3.1. Introduction

First aid responses require Command, Control, Communication, Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance (C3ISR) for acquiring Situational Awareness (SA), developing a Common Operational Picture (COP) and facilitating Operational Coordination between cross-sectorial, cross-hierarchy and even cross-border teams. The wide pan-European on Information and communication Technology (ICT) depicts a promising context for exploiting C3ISR opportunities that enhance the personnel adaptability, operational decision-making and course of action planning (Big Data analytics, advanced simulation environments, etc.), real-time collaboration and information sharing (distributed computing, decentralized databases, etc.) or mission-centric risk management. Resourceful data mining for future use cases and improvement of existing infrastructure and for adaptability purposes in order to achieve the best overall architecture that will facilitate and combine multiple technologies as one. VALKYRIES analyses in-depth these operational and harmonisation opportunities, serving as core for the SIGRUN platform.

The approach to structure the state-of-the-art study within mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies is based on the OODA methodology described in the project's harmonisation framework document.

Figure 35 - Description of the OODA Loop (58)

First phase of the OODA loop is regarding **observe**. Status, scenario and the catastrophe set of information regarding multiple casualty incident shall be collect. Having observed the situation, we next **orient** to it. Estimations, assumptions, analyses and judgements can create a cohesive mental image. In this sense, we have improved the analysis to figure out what the situation means to us.

Observing and orienting correctly are the key to a successful decision. If these steps are not correctly defined, they lead to a flawed decision and a wrong subsequent action. So, while speed is important, so is improving analytical skills and being able to see what is really happening.

Based on our conclusion from the orientation phase, we are going to **decide** which action plans will be suitable on the field. After deciding what actions will be deployed to harmonize the organizations between countries, action shall be started up.

Finally, **action** phase is ready. This phase includes disseminating the decision, supervising to ensure proper execution, and monitoring results through feedback, which takes us full circle to the observation phase. Having acted, we have changed the situation, and so the cycle begins again. It is worth noting that, in any organization with multiple decision makers, multiple OODA

loops spin simultaneously, although not necessarily at the same speed, as commanders exercise C&C at their own level and locale (59).

The closing loop of the OODA includes the continuous Observation of the actions taken on the previous loop, thus feeding back on the effectiveness of the action and impact of the action in the scenario, which may trigger different orientation or new decisions.

In the OODA cycle all the phases run simultaneously in time, observations occurs while the orientation and decision making are done, etc. So, it should be understood not just as an operation flow, but also as a data information flow (see Figure 36).

Figure 36 - OODA LOOP – Data functions

In the data cycle of OODA, applied to VALKYRIES, can be established as:

- **Identify Needs:** Identify the data needs and priorities
- **Plan:** Establish a plan to collect the data, the sources and platforms
- **Collect:** gather the data action, follow the plan established
- **Clean:** Evaluate/Clean the data (Data Quality)
- **Analyse:** Analyse the data collected, and obtain additional information data to support the understanding of the situation
- **Integrate:** fuse the data and establish relations between the data to improve the situational awareness
- **Intell:** Derive the meaning of the data within the operational scenario and establish analysis scenarios
- **Store:** Store the data collected, including its metadata, in a structured, organized, accessible way

- **Visualize:** tools to compile the information gathered, analysed, generated, and forecasted displayed in a Common environment to establish a reasoning and understanding of the situation awareness's

Figure 37 - OODA LOOP – Data flow

Note: Although a specific data flows from the identification of data needs process up to the generation of intelligence, all the steps identified above are continuously being executed and the data changes from one process to the following, while new data is feeding the processes, presented in Figure 37.

5.3.1.1. Situational awareness (SA)

SA is a key concept in emergency response, an effective response relies on successful multi-agency coordination, and to carry out this coordination is essential that each agency has a complete knowledge of what is going on (SA), as depicted in Figure 38.

Figure 38 - Emergency Situational Awareness

In order to help emergency accountable people to get a right SA, C&C systems must gather information from all available sources such as: information from first responders, information from other agencies, video, radio, photos, satellite images, images from drones, online services such as weather, traffic, rss, social networks etc. All gathered information must be filterer and summarized in order to extract the relevant information, and then finally show it on maps and different dashboards. In this way accountable people for making decisions in emergency situations can have a complete view of what is happening.

The information must be received taking advantage of all available technology. Within these technologies we find, among others, IoT and/or social networks; with a fast and reliable response of useful information (60). Technology should be applied to improve the accuracy of data received from various information sources. Technology must provide optimal information management, in terms of speed, responsiveness and data reliability.

5.3.1.2. Common Operational Picture (COP)

The concept of COP is closely related to SA, the COP must filter and summarize situational and operational information from all available sources, and then make the relevant information available to the involved stakeholders. The COP must offer a complete view of what is happening and how is being resolved. This procedure is presented in detail in Figure 39.

Figure 39 - Common operational picture (COP)

The COP must be continuously updated based on the information received about the current situation of the emergency, the degree of progress of the operational work and the conclusions obtained from all the information available.

The COP must summarize information on at least the following items:

- **SA** (information from first responders, information from other agencies, video, radio, photos, satellite images, images from drones, online services such as weather, traffic, rss, social networks etc.)
- **Maps** (weather, wind, etc)

- **Tactical maps** with real time situation, and the possibility of saving versions at specific times during the emergency, in order to allow the possibility of analysing the progress of the emergency over time
- **Critical infrastructures and points of interest**
- **Operation planning**
 - Action plans, sequence of steps that must be taken, or activities that must be performed in order to manage the emergency
 - Lines of actions
 - Incident response interventions
 - Planned interventions
- **Resources**
 - Intervention teams
 - Command hierarchical structure
- **Contacts directory of the operation**
 - Contact directory of the operation based on the contingency plan
- **Document attachments**

There is a new concept related to the COP, the Common Operational Relevant Picture (CROP) is a subset of the COP with relevant information oriented to specific groups of stakeholders, for instance external agencies, private organizations, governments or notices to the population.

In order for the COP to be a most useful tool, the data presented must be consistent and the interpretation of its displayed data not unambiguous. For that purpose, each COP must be consistent when using its icons and pictures.

We can find different COPS with different icons and graphical patterns, according to the purpose of a specific COP. But the same COP must provide some basic components / behaviours, such as:

- Be consistent when presenting an information
- It shall be clear and not create ambiguous interpretation
- It shall provide the tools to query the operational picture
- It shall display only the needed/requested information
- It shall avoid data overload
- It must have a clear colour standard schema, in particular when representing critical elements, alerts, actions, and results
- It should provide the landscape of the scenario, which can be a geographic Map (in real world tactical scenarios) or other meaningful landscape map, as applicable
- It shall provide the tools to display time valid data and hide/show past data

Depending on the size of the event, the COP may be dematerialized in different functions. I.e., the medical and health entity responsible for the victim's transportation, may need only to visualize the ambulances and FR Vehicles tactical data. So, each user with a specific responsibility and role may select only to display the COP data that is relevant for his role.

5.3.2. Situational data gathering (observe)

The OBSERVE phase of the OODA cycle focuses on the critical action of gathering the data, as much as possible, with as much time validity available, with the means available in order to provide analysts and decision makers the most complete and broad range of information.

In MCI scenarios, the observe means collecting data for different purposes, from different sources, some require a pre-planned actions while other data is unplanned.

The purposes can be aggregated in the following scopes:

- SITUATIONAL DATA GATHERED: focus on collecting as much information as possible, with the purpose of feed the situational awareness process: register the data, its source and time, for the purpose of the understanding of the current operation or for post operation assessment
- ACTION MONITORING DATA: focus on collecting the data of the operation to enable the assessment of the results of the actions and of the decisions process
- POLITICAL & CONTEXT DATA: focus in collecting data that outside the scope of the tactical operation but may impact it, such as political decision/positions; public opinion; other events that may impact the availability of the response resources and political context

Within this scope, the VALKYRIES technological solution will focus on the first two.

With relation to the source's nature, we can establish as:

1. Aerial information: imagery or other collected by aerial platforms
2. Ground information: imagery or other data gathered by ground elements such as IOT devices; fixed or moving sensors in ground platforms
3. Human data: Data gathered by humans:
 - a. First responder: FR own data (wearables, position, etc.)
 - b. Victims: victims' own data: Wearables; health sensors; cell phone, etc.
 - c. Citizens: Cell phone / social media data: imagery, video, audio; text; etc.

These sources can also be classified as planned information or opportunistic:

1. Planned: Data that requires a preparation of the capability to be collected (e.g. task a satellite; plan an aircraft/Drone flight, etc.; victims and FIR data)
2. Unplanned or opportunistic: Data that is provided by unplanned personnel that do not require a planned action: social media, voice call from 112, etc.

In a generic vie the OBSERVE is the phase where the system intention is to “sense” the environment, in as many possible ways as it can be to provide data and information about it.

The understanding of the sensing effort and means is very closely linked to:

Nature of the event: Use case (Wild Fire, earthquake, etc), as highlighted in Figure 40.

Figure 40 - SIGRUN MCI event type context

Each MCI event may have specific information needs and, therefore, require specific data services (data sets, sources, time updates, etc), to enable a good understanding of the situation:

- **Type of data:** EO / IR / SAR imagery; voice data; people data;
- **Validity of the data** (e.g., location of the fire front is continuously moving)
- **Location of the event and access to infrastructure** (electrical and communications)
- **Nature of the event and medical assistance to provide** (e.g., CBRNE requires specific protocols, data and sensors)

Scale of the event: National, regional, wide area or local. See Figure 41.

Figure 41 - SIGRUN event scale context

The magnitude of the event may require a more complex coordination and planning of the data gathering process, which includes using increasing number of sensors and courses in the field. The larger the scale, it also includes considering additional factors, due to the limitation of the sensors. Therefore, as the scenario grows the planning of the deployment of technological artefacts to support the data gathering also increases.

This means:

- Planning the satellite passed-by at the area of location
- Planning drones and manned aircraft flights path, time window and sensors carrying.
- Planning of deployment of potential IOT sensors
- Planning of other aerial or land platform to collect data

All these planning shall consider several limitations and need of the event and capability available:

- Area of the event
- Critical elements to cover
- Data/sensors needs: EO / IR / cell phones detection / etc
- Time on site
- Availability of the capability (24/7; crew + assets availability)
- Sensor’s coverage range
- Sensors + platform data resolution (especially for imagery data)
- (Many other factors)

5.3.2.1. Data and Information sharing artifacts in the disaster field

Nowadays, most of the devices used in domestic sector, social sector, or in industrial sector are directly connected to the Internet to provide various services without human intervention in many cases. In social sector, applications are increasing, especially based on IoT systems for disaster prevention, alarm in case of a materialized disaster, and its monitoring and follow-up.

RADIO AND TELEVISION

They are still the most used conventional means to help in crisis. It is cheap, offers a secure way of communication and does not involve new applications and technological deployments. Radio can be a much more accessible channel for people affected by disaster, particularly in rural areas, the maritime sector (sailors at sea), and areas with low literacy.

SATELLITE RADIO

Satellite radio gets signal from a communication satellite, and its reach goes beyond commercial radio. It is useful when transmission towers are affected by the disaster. Satellite radio, together with smartphones, is a more powerful factor for the transmission of support in the face of an emergency and the assets that are attending and managing it.

MOBILE TELEPHONES

Today, people are connected to the digital world through their smartphones. They have become an essential part of the day.

Most mobile phones are built with automated emergency protocols that can be activated with the push of a button, very useful if you are one of the people affected by the disaster.

The following tables show the mobile phone technologies used in disaster management (61):

Apps
Huge variety
Usually context-specific
Data upload

Apps
Contribute to modelling
Information display
Often integrated platforms

Table 15 - Common Application function used in disaster events

Photo and video:
Can be geotagged
Used by apps, social media
Direct calculations
Most smartphones
Tangible and engaging

Table 16 - Common photo and video features in disaster events

Sensing technology
Attached to smartphones
Increasing sophistication
Link to professional science
Suitable for most hazards
Becoming cheaper

Table 17 - New features of sensing technology used in disaster events

Social media:
Popularity location-specific
Emergency response
Rapid information sharing
Informal and formal use

Table 18 - Social Media features exploitable in disaster events

Position data:
Emergency response
Evacuations
Mobile signal is enough
Mobile GIS
Risk, vulnerability maps

Table 19 - Positional data applicability in disaster events functions

SMS messages
Low cost
Minimal information
Target a mass audience
Marginalised communities
Generalised alerts

Table 20 - Advantages of SMS messages in disaster events.

Voice Calls:
Non-smartphone
Manual data transfer

Table 21 - Using of voice calls in disaster events.

Figure 42 shows the uses that can be given to the mobile phone during the management of a disaster.

Figure 42 - Mobile phone uses during a disaster (62).

FIXED TELEPHONES

The use of landlines is useful for rural areas with a low rate of technology use by the population.

It can also be a communication mechanism when the networks used by mobile phones are unavailable due to collapse or failure of related infrastructure.

Although the broadcast can only be done one by one, it can become one of the few communication channels enabled.

CELL BROADCASTING

It's a mobile technology that is part of the 2G, 3G, 4G and 5G mobile technology standards. It's a geographically focused one-to-many (one2many) messaging service, unlike SMS which is a one-to-one service. The technology allows a text or binary message to be defined and distributed to all the mobile terminals connected to a set of cells, since the messages are addressed to the radio cells, and not to a specific terminal. It is integrated into most of today's network infrastructure services, and does not require additional costs. It can be scaled geographically so that a message reaches millions of terminals.

SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING

Remote sensing is a technology for remotely studying the properties of objects by using electromagnetic radiation, without touching the objects directly. Satellite remote sensing covers wide-ranging areas, operates continually during all hours and in all types of weather, and is used to survey Earth's surface and atmosphere to study global environmental problems, monitor disasters, and explore resources, and so on (63).

- Cameras on satellites and airplanes take images of large areas on the Earth's surface, allowing us to see much more than we can see when standing on the ground

- Sonar systems on ships can be used to create images of the ocean floor without needing to travel to the bottom of the ocean
- Cameras on satellites can be used to make images of temperature changes in the oceans

Some of the uses of this technology are:

- **Emergency mapping:** the objective is to provide an agile and effective response to disasters. It provides very useful data and information for emergency management, planning and monitoring. Examples of uses in different scenarios:
 - Monitoring of large forest fires can be mapped
 - Follow-up evolution for volcano eruption
 - Follow the evolution for sand storms
 - Monitoring wind patterns. Hurricanes can be predicted as an early warning to reduce damage
 - Help predict weather
 - Earthquake detection
- **Data analysis:** can be used to predict the future occurrence or extent of a calamity, as the data obtained can be used to record the extent and strength of the calamity which simplifies data comparison
- **Allocation of resources:** examining areas and groups affected, simplifies the allocation of funds, minimizing fraud and misuse of public money
- **Relief operations:** many areas become inaccessible after a natural disaster. Assists in sky-based disaster assessment and monitoring by providing important information to operations. An example can be flood management, supporting rescue missions in places where it has been flooded in rainy season
- **Reconstruction of affected areas:** it can be a great challenge to rebuild devastated areas. Remote Sensing helps to cover a larger area to cover relocation

UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLES (UAVS)

UAVs are increasingly incorporated in a wide range of domains such as disaster management and rescue missions. UAV path planning deals with finding the most optimal or shortest path for UAVs such that minimum energy and resources are utilized.

Drone application is another way to categorise and comprehend how drones are deployed:

MAPPING OR DISASTER MANAGEMENT

Drone mapping is useful in construction, agriculture, mining and infrastructure inspection. Hence, they are very useful for disaster management, monitoring and evaluating damage.

The benefits it provides are the following:

- Obtain real time data to be able to make quick decisions. Multi-rotor platforms are more flexible and suitable for inspecting small areas or isolated buildings. Instead, fixed-wing drones are better suited to mapping large areas such as floods or wildfires. In any of the platforms, a high-resolution orthophoto is obtained in a few minutes, speeding up the subsequent analysis of the event, allowing the most affected areas to be identified and the damage to infrastructure to be evaluated

- Operates in dangerous areas so as not to put rescue team people at risk. They are much more cost effective than fixed-wing light aircraft or helicopters for use in extreme weather conditions. They are used to assess building damage in hard-to-reach areas by allowing 3D models of the disaster site using specialized software
- Data collected improves situational awareness
- Provides technical capabilities that humans don't have, such as thermal or infrared scanning

SEARCH AND RESCUE

Drones, flying over the affected area, and using thermal sensors can help spot people where they can't be easily seen, trapped under debris, or taking cover until help arrives.

Through the processing of the images captured by drones, it is possible to predict how the incident will progress (advancement of the line of fire of a fire, how the water will rise in floods, for example). This allows rescue teams to create more efficient evacuation plans by identifying the area at risk and planning how to relocate people.

TRANSPORTATION

In a natural disaster, the supply of medical or emergency material in the affected area becomes a critical point.

Drones are capable of delivering medical supplies (such as insulin or other medications), medical material (defibrillators), blood samples during emergencies, and food with a maximum weight of 17 Kg using the rope suspension method under the supervision of a remote pilot.

POST-DISASTER

Drones can also be used to assess damage after a natural disaster. Drones capture video and take photos to assess damage.

This evaluation includes the analysis of data to be able to detect fire impacts, prevent future disasters such as floods or landslides by observing the loss of trees and vegetation.

Through communication antennas, drones can restore communications for first responders in case traditional communication lines are lost, allowing people to connect, and manage water, food, medical supplies and other emergency equipment.

TRAINING

Drones are an excellent resource to train and prepare emergency personnel in the investigation of natural disasters. Participants of some tests with simulated scenarios of large open spaces and with a large number of victims and with the use of drones, managed to significantly improve their self-perception at the end of the simulation (64) (63).

5.3.2.2. Aerial data gathering

Aerial data gathering to support ground-based operation, can explore a wide number of different sensors, from EO / IR cameras + Radar / SAR imagery with foliage penetration; SIGINT, IAS (Maritime environment), etc.

The operation of such sensors can be made through different platforms, Satellite; HAPS; RPAS, piloted aircrafts, small drones, balloons, etc.

Each platform provides different pros and cons, as presented in Table 22.

Platform	Autonomy (Time on site)	Sensor payload	Weather imagery limitation	Weather operation limitation	Manoeuvrability (Ability to follow specific event)	Area Coverage	Imagery resolution
Drones / RPAS	High	High number & adaptable	Medium	High	Very High	Medium	Very High
Satellite	intermittent	Reduced number & fixed	Very High	Low	Low	Very High	Low
Manned aircraft	medium	Very high & adaptable	Medium	Very High	Very High	Medium	Very High
HAPS	Very high	Very High & adaptable	High	Medium	Medium	High	Medium
Balloons	High	High & adaptable	high	Very high	Low	Low	Medium

Table 22 - Analysis of advantages and disadvantages of each platform.

Satellites have the disadvantage of clouds effects, revisiting time, and passed orbit which prevent from having the area of interest under continuous observation, etc; manned or unmanned aircrafts have the flights time disadvantage when compared to satellites, smaller coverage, and requires a higher crew to operate the flight.

On another hand aircraft imagery provides a higher ground imagery resolution, can stay more continuous time on target and can easily manoeuvred to specific location and spots. Other limitations are due to the aerial envelop conditions (max wind, max altitude, endurance, etc).

Generally speaking, it seems to be widely accepted that while drones aren't going anywhere, so to speak, it's not anticipated that they will replace satellites as the primary means of collecting and generating mapping and navigational information for the globe. Satellites are just too effective on a larger scale.

Instead, smaller scale, detailed locations and places that are hard to reach may be areas where drones outperform satellites.

Even though in cases of severe damage in areas, satellite images upon request can be provided, even though the costs can be extremely high. If the case of a large-scale destruction, where multiple drones need to be used in order to cover and map the area, the possible case of satellite images and the deployment of a simple UI for extreme use cases should be considered as a valuable solution (65). For a comparison between satellites and drones for aerial data gathering, refer to Table 23.

Satellites	Drones
Macro view of the terrain is needed	Micro view take of the land is apropos and scaling up does not matter
When a large amount of data must be gathered quickly	Fine details

Satellites	Drones
Huge set amount of data	More spot-checking, rather than gathering a huge glob of data
More sophisticated satellites can look a bit flat	More control over the angle at which an image is captured
Unforeseen weather changes can affect	Better response to unforeseen weather events. I.e., clouds can cover parts of your area of interest and drones can sort it

Table 23 - Comparison of capabilities between satellites and drones for aerial data gathering.

The use of aerial platforms faces some limitation in scenarios of manned and unmanned platforms being used simultaneously, or the selection of the platform & sensors to be used, according to the operational conditions.

Drones or manned aircraft face different constraints to obtain aerial imagery according to the situational context. As an example, a Wildfire smoke column may limit the air platform flight path to avoid the smoke and high gases into the engines, thus limiting the imagery that can be collected.

The regulations about airspace flight areas and conditions should be taken into consideration when selecting the aerial platform. In several countries, in wildfire events, aerial platforms are limited by VFR rules, meaning they can only flight from sunrise to sunset. Unsegregated airspace between manned platforms and drones is not yet real situation due to safety issues. Therefore, airspace segregation is required when simultaneously flying manned aircrafts and drones. A standard segregation approach is to have different Flight levels and having drones flying a further altitude and distance from the event. Therefore, the data (imagery) ground resolution may be limited.

Combining both capabilities provides a power tool to gather data and Intel required to build an operational picture and an overall situational assessment.

SATELLITE IMAGES

During the last years, satellite technology and image analysis techniques have developed to an extent where civil and commercial Earth-observation satellites can significantly contribute to support the management of major technical and natural disasters, as well as humanitarian crisis situations (66).

Satellite and drone aerial imagery can be a tool of crucial significance for the management of emergency situations and disasters. They can provide a variety of information not only for the assessment, analysis and monitoring of small and/or large-scale natural catastrophes, such as earthquakes, volcanoes, floods, hurricanes, but also for the facilitation of the emergency response, the appropriate and timely deployment of resources.

Various kinds of satellites, including satellites for communications, meteorological satellites, remote sensing and geophysics satellites, exist. Today, more than 4550 satellites are orbiting the Earth. Satellites are useful not only for governmental and military purposes but for civilians as well, as they provide the capability for internet connections, geolocation and a huge variety of applications. Satellites are mainly used for the following purposes (67):

- Communications: 63%
- Earth observation: 22.1%
- Technology development: 7.8%
- Navigation/global positioning: 3.6%
- Technology demonstration: 0.77%
- Earth science: 0.44%
- Space observation: 0.22%
- Space science: 2.3%

The altitude, on which satellites orbit the Earth, and their orbits, are dependent on they are meant to facilitate and serve.

Figure 43 - Satellite Orbiting Types (68).

There are different satellite orbiting types as presented in Figure 43. Satellites in geostationary orbit (GSO), are following the Earth's rotation, circling the planet above the equator from the west to the east, completing a whole circle in about 24 hours. Because of their movement, they stay constantly above one place over the Earth. They are used mostly for telecommunication purposes, and they are useful for Earth Observation. In this orbit are usually set weather monitoring satellites as well. There are also satellites that circle the Earth from the north to the south, called Polar orbit and Sun-synchronous orbit (SSO) satellites. These are meant to provide pictures of a specific area with the aim to identify changes by comparing these images. For that reason, the exact same circumstances are required, i.e., same time each day, so that the sun is at the same spot in the horizon. This kind of satellites are unique for weather observation as well, because they can assist in the detection of emerging weather patterns, in the prediction storms etc., proving to be essential tools even in ongoing disasters e.g., wildfires and floods. Furthermore, they can provide images for gradually evolving disasters e.g., deforestation or sea level rise. When monitoring emergency situations and natural disasters like wildfires or floods, or to accumulate data like deforestation or rising sea levels.

The satellites that are used for communication and remote sensing are mostly orbiting in a close distance above the Earth, called Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites. This kind of satellites does not

follow a particular path around the Earth. This answers the question why there is a numerical superiority of this type of satellite orbits. As these satellites are the nearest to the surface of the planet, they can provide higher resolution images and are most preferred for satellite imagery. Most LEO satellites can make a full rotation around the Earth in about 90 minutes. Very often, they are set together as a net, so to better cover large areas.

At a greater altitude, there are the Medium Earth Orbit (MEO) satellites, which are used for navigation systems, like the European Galileo system. Medium earth orbit, as LEO orbits, don't require following specific paths.

Communications, radio and remote sensing satellites are set at a Highly Elliptical orbit (HEO).

Finally, some satellites are set at specific points in the outer space, called Lagrange points (L-points), where the gravitational fields of the Earth and Sun neutralize each other, thus retaining the orbit of the satellite stable. These satellites are mainly set for dark space observations.

Figure 44 - Satellite Map (69).

Satellite and drone imagery is crucial for crisis management. Manual surveying, especially of large areas, could take days, but with the help of satellite images, the situation is rapidly assessed, and the time needed for the first responders to be activated is critically limited, while the capability for a successful and timely operation is greatly enhanced. According to (70), satellites imagery and geospatial information can be very helpful in:

- Emergency planning
- Risk assessment
- Monitoring of disaster areas and response
- Damage assessment and recovery efforts

Maps, geospatial information, and thematic analysis derived from satellite imagery can support decision making and situation awareness during all four phases of the disaster and crisis management cycle (mitigation, preparedness, response, recovery) (71).

In case of large disasters in remote areas, where other means of situation assessment may fail or lack quality, the fast delivery of updated, accurate and comprehensive images can greatly assist in the accomplishment of situation awareness and a common operational picture among engaged first responders and, therefore, facilitate the response and recovery phases.

It is important to mention, that depending on the type of the disaster, different data and analysis techniques are required. The most important data sources are Very High Resolution (VHR) optical data, thermal imagery and synthetic-aperture-radar (SAR) systems.

Very High Resolution (VHR) satellite images have a spatial resolution i.e., the level of describing and presenting details of the ground, below 2 meters, with the best VHR sensor giving capture of our planet in a 30 centimetres spatial resolution.

Nowadays, there is a variety of free satellite imagery platforms, like the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (EMS), which provides free of charge mapping services in cases of natural disasters, man-made emergency situations and humanitarian crises all over the world and for all phases of the emergency management cycle. The data and available information can be used by service providers, public authorities and international organizations.

The Copernicus programme has in its property a set of dedicated satellites, called Sentinel, that serve the need of the Copernicus information services and their users, and use satellite data from contributing missions, either from private companies or from institutional partners. Today, there are seven Sentinel satellites in orbit around the Earth from four different types. Until 2030, the European Union intends to set in orbit for about 20 satellites.

Copernicus satellites, along with ground-based, airborne and seaborn measurement sensors provide a major variety of weather data e.g., land and sea surface temperature, air quality etc., whereas they can even trace gases in the atmosphere. These in-situ observations are regularly updated. All the collected data can be processed and analysed leading to the production of maps. There are six thematic streams of Copernicus services:

- Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS)
- Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS)
- Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS)
- Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)
- Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS)
- Copernicus Security Service (72)

In natural and man-made disasters, the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) provides maps depicting the impact on the ground, throughout all disaster management cycle phases, thus enhancing also SaR operations. Evacuation routes and sheltering of affected populations can also be facilitated. CEMS maps are also used to monitor recovery and reconstruction after the occurrence of the disaster.

The early warning component of the CEMS, consists of three systems:

- The European Flood Awareness System (EFAS), concerning ongoing and forecasted floods up to 10 days in advance

- The European Forest Information System (EFFIS), concerning real – time and historical wildfires, as much as forest fire regimes in the European, Middle Eastern and North African regions
- The European Drought Observatory (EDO), concerning information related to the drought phenomenal and early – warnings for Europe

At a global level, these systems are incorporated in the Global Flood Awareness System (GloFAS), the Global Wildfire Information System (GWIS) and the Global Drought Observatory (GDO). (73)

The maps that are produced have two temporal modes:

- **Rapid Mapping**, consisting of satellite imagery and geospatial information of the disaster areas within hours and days from the incident, to monitoring and support the crisis circle
- **Risk & Recovery Mapping**, consisting of satellite imagery and geospatial information of an area, that is activated under a demand to support Disaster Management activities (74)

Through satellite imagery, there is also the capability of accurate weather forecasts, which can prevent or eliminate a potential disaster and, even more save, human lives.

Satellite technologies used by Greek first responders

In Greece, the General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSCP) is part of the Copernicus Program, since its inception as “Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES)”. The Emergency Planning, Prevention and Response Directorate is the national contact point for the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) and consists of staff with satellite data processing competence and expertise.

The Emergency Management Service Mapping focuses on the response and early recovery phases and not on the phase of prevention. Till today, it has been activated a total of 41 times by the GSCP, and specifically 38 times for the rapid mapping of wildfires (27 times) and floods (11 times), 2 times for recovery purposes and once for risk assessment. For the activation of CEMS the cooperation between first responders (the Fire Service, the Police, forestry services, Municipalities and Regional Prefectures) and the Emergency Planning, Prevention and Response Directorate, which is the national contact point, is required, however, there are cases, during which the CEMS has been activated on the request of first responders.

For an effective use of the CEMS products it is essential that the time, that intercedes between the occurrence of a disaster and the activation of CEMS is limited, that there is low cloud of smoke concentration in the atmosphere and that satellite data for the affected area are available and up to date.

First responders can access CEMS products through the CEMS or the GSCP websites. Additionally, Sentinel and Landsat images are used but lack in data, that are of utmost importance for the first responder e.g., road networks, critical infrastructures and assets, buildings etc.). For users with a certain level of competence web tools such as the “Copernicus Open Access Hub” have considerably facilitated the acquisition of satellite data. (75)

The National Coordination Center of Operations and Crisis Management of Greece, which consists of the Land and Maritime Operations Unit, the Air Operations Unit, the Stakeholder

Unit, the European Mechanism and International Assistance Unit and the European Emergency Number Unit, as well as, the Hellenic Fire Service use the ENGAGE IMS/CAD system, provided by Satways Ltd., which operates as a call center solution for first responders and public safety organizations (76). These calls may come from citizens who use the 112 or 199 number, fire watch stations, volunteers, civil aviation aircrafts, that detect fires etc. It provides the end users with enhanced situational awareness, facilitates decision making and information processing. The ENGAGE system uses as a basemap the Sentinel-2 VIS image mosaic as a basemap.

ENGAGE may also provide a simulation of the fire spread taking into consideration topography and meteorological conditions as well. Concurrently, resource tracking (vehicles, personnel) can be achieved with the use of tracking technologies e.g., AVL, AIS, LRIT) (77).

Figure 45 - Real time of the fire spread and the exact positions of firefighting means in Vilia, Attica Greece, 2021 (78).

The ENGAGE user interface can be adaptable both in both a web-based and mobile application. Indicatively the following interfaces exist:

- ENGAGE Desktop – Main Application for Desktop PCs (Java based + Map component)
- ENGAGE Commander – Application for mobile ruggedized tablet PCs (Java Based + Map co)
- ENGAGE Light client – Web based app
- ENGAGE Mobile (& public) – Smartphone – Android app

During the last 9 years, MSG Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager (SEVIRI) satellite is being used for both real time fire monitoring and for the acquisition of historical fire maps. It can also provide information regarding fire outbreaks in remote areas or even before the respective fire department of the affected area is informed. Moreover, the FireHUB BSM Service application, which is provided by the National Observatory of Athens (NOA) is another tool, that can be exploited by first responders and a Memorandum of Cooperation between (NOA) and the National Coordination Center of Operations and Crisis Management has been signed since the beginning of 2020. The FIREHUB Service facilitates the exchange of data. National

Observatory of Athens has developed an early warning system to detect, monitor and access a fire spread.

AERIAL IMAGES

Aerial data is being used from long time, since airplanes and cameras become available. Aerial imagery explores imagery and video for multiple purposes, to detect and follow elements of interest position in the ground by using different sensors, from EO / IR / SR / AIS detector / etc, to generate maps from aerial orthophotography combined with LRF (Laser Range Finder), to spot hot signatures (IR sensor), and many other sensing applications (see Figure 46).

With the increase of UAV technology maturity, these long and dull flights are tendency being performed by UAV or RPAS, or other unmanned system (Class II and Class I drones, HAPS, and other similar platforms).

Over the past few years Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) have gained considerable interest as a remote sensing platform for various practical applications, such as traffic monitoring, search and rescue, precision agriculture, wildfire monitoring, Maritime surveillance, border surveillance, large horizontal infrastructures (e.g. Pipelines), anti-poaching activity, environmental monitoring, and many others. These UAVs are equipped with cameras and sensors are able to detect, monitor and analyse passive and active threats and hazards, providing real-time data of critical situation or provide wide aerial tactical and strategic information.

UAVs provide the capacity to first responders to patrol large areas in a limited time. They can be used for police and firefighters' operations, and specifically:

Police operations:

- Communication disaster service
- Monitoring in a human disaster
- Patrolling of an area
- Traffic congestion documentation
- Monitoring of mass events
- Supporting pursuit actions, searching and other actions
- Obtaining evidence

Firefighters' operations:

- Detect, monitoring and patrol in cases of wildfires, floods, roads, rails and air disasters
- Thermal imaging of fire sources and speeding
- Monitoring and tracking the sources in situations of pollution
- Supporting the safer way to operate in an area
- Detect and save human lives (79)

Maritime operations:

- Perform wide maritime area search for MOB (Man Over Board), or small vessels
- Perform maritime pollution detection and monitoring (Service provided by EMSA)
- Identify potential polluters
- Classify oil spills

- Map coastal areas for Environmental monitoring
- Illegal fisheries detection and monitoring

Mountains and remote areas operation

- Perform wide mountain area search for people lost
- Map remote areas to spot for life signs

Infrastructure Monitoring

- Powerlines inspections
- Pipelines monitoring
- Prevention of fire and mitigation of fire by inspection the forest cleaning area (Land strip line distance to forest for safety issues)
- Open Mining measurement and mapping

Environmental monitoring

- Forest mapping, Ice areas mapping
- Forest foliage area and biomass measurement
- Contaminated soils mapping (Possibly detection of contaminant substance)

Search people lost in mountains

Inspection of pipelines and power lines

Inspect and monitor natural events and their impact

Search and track lifeboats adrift

Figure 46 - Relevant uses for aerial images.

The data gathered is transmitted to the operational command where is displayed, stored and analysis, to provide valuable intell and awareness to the decision makers.

With the increasing number of data stream, it becomes necessary to select the relevant information to display and to automate the analysis process in order to timely generate actionable intell. AI and ML algorithms are now a major development area that integrates the aerial imagery process chain.

Figure 47 - Application scenario for use of UAVs that utilize algorithms based on deep learning models that analyze video footage in real-time to characterize the current situation and alert in the presence of any damage (80) .

UAVs are able to operate in disaster areas even when communication to cloud services is difficult to achieve and high – end infrastructure is not available. As a result, a higher level of autonomy is required to ensure operational efficiency and real-time analysis. In such cases an autonomous UAV relies heavily on its on-board sensors and microprocessors to carry out a given task without requiring the feed to be sent to a central ground station. Some there is some pros and cons on onboard processing vs ground processing:

	Pros	Cons
Onboard processed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better raw data quality • Lower processing delay • Requires less ground Tx data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower processing capability
Ground processed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher processing capability • Easier integration and fusion with other data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality degradation due to the transmission process • Data delay

Table 24 - Pros & Cons of Onboard processed or ground processed.

Depending on the purpose of the operation and the available and the capacity of the platform + sensor performance, and the processing capability of the platform, de processing may be done onboard or at ground.

The function to perform mission may also require specific end-to-end processing performances, which will push the decision for onboard or ground processing. As an example, when a mission required a very high real-time location precision, usually the function is performed onboard, in order to ensure less procession error due to tx transmission and time elapse from the data gathering until the process ends.

However, in more typical usage of aerial imagery in MCI event aims at having a good overall aerial picture and understanding the situational status and evolution, and the Real-time air data gathered is transmitted to ground.

The data collected from aerial platforms follows than a several transformations until it becomes actionable, as presented in Figure 48.

Figure 48 - Procedure for data processing in aerial images.

- 1) Collect:** The sensors carried by the aerial platform, collect the raw data and generate the data file or data stream that contains the information
- 2) Air store, tag and transmit:** The data is stored and tagged with time stamp and other metadata of origin. The data is then encapsulated for transmission. The transmission of data in real-time may degrade the raw data generated by the sensors in order to fit the downlink pipeline and to comply with potential compressed data protocol
- 3) Analyse:** Once the data is available at ground station it is processed with algorithm to perform multiple actions: clean data; extract data from the image (features extraction); detect, classify and identify elements of interest; detect ground behaviour patterns; etc. This function typically uses image processing algorithms, and more recently this encompasses technological techniques such as ML and AI
- 4) Fusion:** The data extracted or the raw data received is the 2nd level processing to correlate the data with other elements: Example are: compare vessel image and AIS signal to perform control; Merge EO and IR imagery to generate a composite image and have a simple vision of the global process

Steps 3 and 4 are the richest for generating valuable and decision-making data, where major developments are ongoing. However, the quality results of these algorithm may be very dependent on the raw data quality, and the algorithm processing are usually trimmed to a specific data processing chain (81).

- 5) Dissemination:** The data generated and the raw data are distributed to the data consumers. Again, this process may encompass some critical elements to consider: the bandwidth to distribute the data, the distributions protocols, networks delays, etc. may compromise the quality of the data received by the final consumer.

AERIAL SENSORS

First responders mainly use UAVs that are equipped with virtual and infrared (IR) sensors. IR sensors are mostly used to detect fire. According to Akhoufi M., et al (82), there are the following spectral bands (see Table 25):

Spectral Band	Wavelength (_ m)
Visible	0.4-0.75
Near Infrared (NIR)	0.75-1.4

Spectral Band	Wavelength (μm)
ShortWave IR (SWIR)	1.4-3
Mid Wave IR (MWIR)	3-8
Long Wave IR (LWIR)	8-15

Table 25 - Spectral bands and wavelengths.

In room temperature, the wavelength is located within the thermal infrared band, with ranges between $0.7 \mu\text{m}$ to $1000 \mu\text{m}$. As a wildfire can reach 1000°C , for fire perception it could be used a mid-waved infrared sub-band (MWIR). Although because of their high price, recent fire detection systems are still using NIR, SWIR or LWIR sensors, which is possible due to the fact that, because of the high temperature there is also a shifting of the distribution of the object radiation in shorter wavelengths. See Figure 49.

Figure 49 - Thermal cameras (83).

Some type of IR sensor, such as MWIR, can be used to perform the identification of wildfire hotspot, were can be better used at night to locate potential rekindle points and help the commanders to select where positioning the firefighters on the aftermath (in Portugal, between 2012 and 2017 the rekindle was between 10% and 20% of the fire causes (84). An example of hot spots MWIR satellite imagery is presented in Figure 50.

Figure 50 - Fire Hot spots MWIR cameras from ITER satellite. (85)

An example of hot spots MWIR Airborne imagery is presented in Figure 51.

Figure 51 - Airborne Fire Hot spots MWIR cameras. (86)

EO sensors

Visible spectrum cameras have a wide variety of resolution and forms, and are unique for UAVs due to their light weight. They provide images in grayscale of RGB format, allowing to develop multiply digital techniques with different colors, shapes and temporal changes. Although infrared spectrums sensors are useful in day light operations, in the night in cases of low light conditions, many of them present limited performing.

Multi/Hyper spectrum sensors

In some UAVs there is the capability to combine multispectral cameras, in order to get better results in cases of complex situations and different lighting conditions. There has been developed multispectral camera operating in the LWIR, NIR spectral cameras and visible spectrum mounted on a UAV.

Multi and Hyper spectral cameras cover a wide range of bands. For forest and vegetation red edge band, a band that cover the frequency range where the vegetation reflectance changes rapidly to the condition of the plants, can be used to identify some of the forest and trees characteristics, biomass, and forest vigour.

Commonly used Multispectral bands for the forest characterisation are: G + R + NIR + Red-Edge

Hyperspectral camera explores a much wider number of bands, >100 bands with smaller wavelength interval range. Hyperspectral sensor requires a good stabilization of the sensor. The hyperspectral sensors usually work as reflectance measurement; therefore, a known light source is required to proper calibration for a good data collection (see Figure 52).

Figure 52 - Hyperspectral data cube (87).

Hyperspectral sensors generate a very high number of raw data that is required to be onboard processed to generate the hyperspectral cube.

Multi and Hyperspectral camera usability are more tailored to be used at the planning and post event assessment phases, and less as a tactical or Operational tool.

LIDAR

Lidar, which stands for *Light Detection and Ranging*, is a remote sensing method that uses light in the form of a pulsed laser to measure ranges (variable distances) to the Earth. These light pulses combined with the airborne system Inertial and navigation data enables the reconstruction 3D model and maps.

Because Lidar are active sensors (they carry their own RF source) do not depend on the environmental luminosity,

There are different types of LIDAR wavelengths operated addressing different purposes, for which two most functions are presented:

- Near-Infrared wavelength LIDAR is very useful for mapping the terrain from aerial platforms. Lidar can also penetrate forest canopy and help detecting elements under

the forest canopy. By fusion the Lidar data with Hyperspectral data, additional and very rich information can be used to characterize and classify forest status

- Green Wavelength LIDAR (sometime also Blue) used to bathymetric mapping, due to its water penetration capability. The penetration depth depends on the water turbidity, between 10 to 30 m, which is very useful for mapping shallow waters, transition of the sea to land region, or map underwater areas in cases of flood

LIDAR sensor usability is more tailored to be used at the planning and post event assessment phases, and less as a tactical or Operational real-time tool.

SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) sensor

SAR is a type of active remote sensor that generates an energy pulse and then records the amount of energy reflected back after interacting with the Earth. The spatial resolution of radar data is directly related to the ratio of the sensor wavelength to the length of the sensor's antenna. For a given wavelength, the longer the antenna, the higher the spatial resolution. To obtain a very high resolution it would require a very length antenna, which is not practical. So, SAR uses a synthetic aperture, which is obtained by using the reception of a sequence of smaller antennas to simulate a larger antenna. SAR frequency usage is introduced in Figure 53.

Band	Frequency	Wavelength	Typical Application
Ka	27–40 GHz	1.1–0.8 cm	Rarely used for SAR (airport surveillance)
K	18–27 GHz	1.7–1.1 cm	rarely used (H ₂ O absorption)
Ku	12–18 GHz	2.4–1.7 cm	rarely used for SAR (satellite altimetry)
X	8–12 GHz	3.8–2.4 cm	High resolution SAR (urban monitoring,; ice and snow, little penetration into vegetation cover; fast coherence decay in vegetated areas)
C	4–8 GHz	7.5–3.8 cm	SAR Workhorse (global mapping; change detection; monitoring of areas with low to moderate penetration; higher coherence); ice, ocean maritime navigation
S	2–4 GHz	15–7.5 cm	Little but increasing use for SAR-based Earth observation; agriculture monitoring (NISAR will carry an S-band channel; expands C-band applications to higher vegetation density)
L	1–2 GHz	30–15 cm	Medium resolution SAR (geophysical monitoring; biomass and vegetation mapping; high penetration, InSAR)
P	0.3–1 GHz	100–30 cm	Biomass. First p-band spaceborne SAR will be launched ~2020; vegetation mapping and assessment. Experimental SAR.

Figure 53 - Frequencies usage (88).

SAR can be down looking or side looking. Side looking SAR provides a wider swath and allows disambiguation of elements at the same distance (on the Left and on the Right) faced by down looking SAR.

SAR sensor present some advantage:

- Can work in a frequency transparent for the clouds, so it can work day, night and in adverse weather and cloudy conditions
- The ground spatial resolution does not depend on the altitude of the sensor. So, the higher altitude of the sensor the wider the area covered keeping the same spatial resolution
- Generates a 3D geo-referenced map

On the down size, it has the disadvantages:

- Requires a high peak energy pulse
- Weight and antennas size
- Requires a very high pre-processing onboard capability
- Required platform moving

SAR images can be used for several emergency events. As an example, SAR imagery is widely used for environmental oil spill detection and characterisation. See Figure 54.

Figure 54 - Oil Spill SAR image (89).

ELINT /SIGINT sensors

A brief example of ELINT sensors is the sensors that can detect and process the RF emission of the GSM protocol, to detect the cell phone source and location of the signals. Examples like Life seeker sensor is used for Search and Rescue Operations, and to detect potential loss people in mountains

Other sensors

Many other sensors are currently already market available to be used from aerial platforms, such as:

- AIS (Automatic Identification System) transponder detection, used to detect and track Vessels AIS signals
- EPIRB (Emergency Position Indicating Radio Beacon) sensors, a EPIRB signal receiver to detect emergency beacons and its location, or bearing, from people /vessels lost/ at drift in the sea
- LRF (Laser range finder), an active Laser sensor to collect high precision distance measurements which help performing SaR operations

USE OF UAV/DRONES IN EMERGENCY OPERATIONS

UAVs are one of the most significant tools to provide rapid, live and accurate imagery of a disaster area, facilitating damage assessment. For first responders, firefighters, SaR teams, UAVs

re equipped with thermal cameras and Sensor measurements, have with integrated algorithms, that can detect fires or detect persons in distress through smoke, dust, light or in the darkness.

The rapid development of UAVs and their ever-increasing use in several domains, one of which is the disaster management domain, is also facilitated by the development of standards directly related to unmanned systems. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has a dedicated Technical Committee, ISO/TC 20/SC16 - Unmanned Aircraft Systems, which has already published 7 standards and is at the process of developing 26 more. Additional organizations e.g., the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, "IEEE", the American National Standards Institute "ANSI" and the International Telecommunication Union "ITU" among others, have dedicated committees and study groups related to unmanned systems (90). (90)

With the increasing adoption of drones as a tool to assist in patrolling specific areas, or to monitor real time emergency events, to detect human presence and perform patrolling operations areas that present higher risks. There are new skills sets required, and the process of detecting can be performed either on board the UAV or by a computer or a human operator that is located at a Ground Control Station.

This requires an experience and well planning of the UAV Flight plans to combine the path planning algorithms with automated on-board visual processing to optimize the UAV exploitation to cover a larger area in less time (81). This planning refers not only to a single UAV flight but to a combination of multiple UAV plans to provide a global emergency observation service.

Moreover, some UAVs are of a small size, high velocity and capability to access dangerous areas enhance SAR operations, while concurrently protecting first responders from unexpected threats. While others can be large platforms carrying multiple sensors package with very long autonomy.

A Major Gap identified is the need for a better spatial and temporal UAVs flight emergency event planning tool, to enable the planning based on the Emergency data type and quality required.

5.3.2.3. HUMINT

NATO defines HUMINT as "a category of intelligence derived from information collected and provided by human sources"(91). Although this definition usually refers to the defence sphere (Diplomatic, military information gathering, etc.). In a broad sense it refers to any area where Human information and data gathering can play a relevant role to feed the decision-making process and the situational awareness, which is also applicable to MCI event.

In the context of MCI, where the HUMINT do not plays the role of getting advantage, but to generate a better understanding of the situation, this data source is increasingly relevant:

- As an MCI event area grows, the more HUMINT data becomes relevant to account for the large area, to deal with the difficulty of covering the entire area;
- The faster the event develops (fast development events) the more relevant HUMINT becomes as a source of alerts. Fast development event tends to be difficult to keep the pace by responders, thus having a good update of the information is well changes in the context of the event is a valuable source of intelligence from HUMINT

- An increasingly complex an MCI event becomes, HUMINT data turns more critical to understand the development of the situation, establish link between the data and complement the understanding of the situation by adding information connections (connect the dots)

In MCI we can classify HUMINT sources in three categories:

- First Responder
- Victims
- Citizens (General public and societal stakeholders)

FIRST RESPONDERS

First aid responders have their primary functions based on their expertise like paramedic, firefighting, safety and security. Regardless of these functions they have the possibility to provide information up the chain of command to build a common operational picture or receive information vital for the solving of the task in hand.

First Responders widely use the METHANE acronym to build a report for alerting others about a major incident.

METHANE stands for:

- Major Incident Declared
- Exact location
- Type of incident
- Hazards
- Access
- Number and type of casualties
- Emergency services present and require

Is used during the assessment phase to provide an initial report to C&C.

They can provide valuable information:

- Context data: from body cameras, audio
- Victims' data: voice and camera data from the victim; registration of victims (First triage level)
- First responders' data: wearables Location; direction, health status
- Intell / Insight / situational analysis data: voice information to the C2

VICTIMS

Another source of data are the victims, either directly via voice services, like 112, or in field imagery / voice collected or provided via smartphone. Victims can provide a very insight and valuable information:

- Victims' health status and geolocation
- MCI event context: present and past (fill-in the gaps)
- Alert for the presence of other elements /victims
- Information to assist / guide rescuers

CITIZENS

Which repercussion has as a citizen regarding Human Intelligence in a catastrophic environment as well as how it will be running in the C&C applications.

Citizens are a major source of the initial information and alerts raise regarding MCI. The initial information about a catastrophic event often comes from human sources, by calling an emergency service (112 service). This is a well-recognized and trusted service, by citizens, to request assistance or report an alert. Or by providing verbal information about what the witness is seeing to the authorities.

In MCI, a particular category of citizens takes on vital importance; these are the relatives and the acquaintances of the victims, because through their testimony, lists of missing persons are created.

It is essential that standardized interview formats be prepared to gather information related to:

- Physical characteristics (including disabilities, past trauma, etc.)
- Presumed location (address, floor, room)
- Clothing, wearables
- Contact information (phone number, social accounts)

This information must be made available to the C&C to enable them, through careful intelligence work, to target searches in the area of most likely discover, in addition will become essential to any deceased victim identification procedures

Not only is information received by voice, but systems are gradually being established that allow real-time video transmission during the 112 calls, by sending an SMS with a link that activates the recording of the mobile phone camera (92).

Other sources of data from media can be broadcast networking TV or radio, and in the growing era of mobility, social media applications become also another source of human data.

Some of the Citizens HUMINT sources are:

- 112 emergency number
- Directly provide to First Responders / authority personnel (Voice)
- Phone and SMS channels
- TV/radio broadcast and news channels
- Social Media channels: 1) social media posting and analysis by civil protection services (Crawling tools on social media website and applications); or 2) dedicated social media channels enabling registered citizen to report data

This data sources can provide information of different Nature:

- Tactical / operational data (MCI internal related): picture and video geo-tagged of people in distress, fire location, etc.
- Contextual (MCI external related): information of escalation of incidents, concurring incidents, political decision

Internet open data information

- Social Media Mining aims at automatically (crawlers) records, collects and processes data from social network that can provide valuable information to the Decision makers. Although of relevance, this data can only be used if it is publicly shared
- Other open data channels sources, such as youtube, generally internet, is also part of the new context of social HUMINT source to turn the data into actionable knowledge and intelligence

Emergency Social Media channels

Another source of actionable data is the use of open data platforms that are managed by the Emergency entities where citizens can register and post emergency data, while also receiving guidelines, direction and orientations, issued by the emergency, civil protection and other governmental forces entities, to prevent massive casualties due to panic or hear saying event.

5.3.2.4. Geographic information system (GIS)

Geographic information is vital for facilitate decision making in Emergency Response. Close integration of spatial information with operational systems will provide clearer insight into asset performance and improve the efficiency and safety of operations (incident response, environmental management...).

Geographic information and the technologies that acquire, interpret, and disseminate such information (GIS, remote sensing, Galileo, GNSS, etc.) are clearly essential in all aspects of disaster, from preparedness, prevention, and protection through detection to response and eventual recovery. Geographic information and technology (GI&T) provide the basis for estimating and mapping risk, for planning evacuation routes and shelters, for determining areas where human populations are most likely to have been impacted following a disaster, and for assigning resources during recovery, among many other vital and important tasks.

In this context every aspect of a GIS project needs careful examination, from training and preparation to data gathering and product dissemination, to see whether critical bottlenecks can be removed. Even though the locations, scales, and intensities of events are almost impossible to anticipate, it is still feasible to build many elements of a GIS response in advance. Data models can be constructed, ready for population as soon as details are known. Methods and scripts can be designed and programmed, based on databases that are yet to be populated but implement carefully constructed data models.

A **geographical information system (GIS)** should be identified as the basic information systems used for solving problems on the NIS (Natural and Industrial System) scale. This system provides storage and graphical representation of objects that have a certain position on the ground. For each object, the database stores its **coordinates, dimensions, display rules, name, and code** for linking to other databases that contain additional information about the objects. It is known that currently 80% of decisions are related to spatial reference to the area. An instrumental GIS includes tools for creating and **editing new thematic layers, individual objects, selective visualization of layers, measurements and calculations, and programming tools** for new analytical tasks. It also provides **solutions** to the problems of input and digital encoding of images directly from primary source of visual data, problems of vectorization of raster images combining layers of a spatial model in a single coordinate system, etc. Most modern GIS have **three-dimensional modelling tools**.

The GIS solution usually has a base map, that could be complemented with multiple specific GIS layers (base layers) and data sets from other private and public organisms that provides an enriched spatial database.

GIS is the powerful tool for this phase. This technology can provide answers to the following questions, such as:

- How many Emergency Service units are required and where should they be dispatched?
- What evacuation routes should be selected if a toxic cloud or plume is accidentally released from a plant or storage facility based on different wind patterns?
- How will people be notified?
- Traffic information: Which are the congested roads, bridges /roads damaged?
- Will the road networks handle the traffic? (Possible road/bridges damaged)
- What facilities will provide evacuation shelters?
- What quantity of supplies, bed space, and so forth, will be required at each shelter based on the number of expected evacuees?
- How many victims require critical assistance and where are they located?

The main objectives for implementing the geographical information system solution are, among others, the following:

- Ensure that the information required by the users for their work is provided within a georeferenced environment and to make sure that such information is enough in quantity and available on time
- Availability of the power of the analysis and query tools in order to strengthen the system geographical dimension, and result in great benefits for the activity of the emergency situation
- Better interoperability with other internal and external systems, more accurate and intuitive results, and better exploitation of the available information in order to optimize efficiency and results
- Sharing information of interest with each of the agencies involves in the emergency. This will be achieved by means of data unification and uniformity of representations
- Ensure that the geo-referenced information is kept at the origin where it is produced. Avoiding the establishment of tedious data migration procedures among applications
- Centralization of Geographical Information Services in order to obtain more efficiency in the effort in the treatment of GIS solutions
- Creation of a Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) with the capacity to meet the objectives identified with this system by the Information Systems Management of the company.
- Give the Information Systems Management the possibility of integrating cartographic representation solutions and services in the emergency processes

RASTER

“In its simplest form, a raster consists of a matrix of cells (or pixels) organized into rows and columns (or a grid) where each cell contains a value representing information, such as temperature. Rasters are digital aerial photographs, imagery from satellites, digital pictures, or even scanned maps” (93).

Advantages:

- From a structural point of view, the raster model is a simple and basic model, but it is not very compact and has many difficulties to represent information when there are very large files
- Raster models can more reliably simulate reality three-dimensionally, while vector files have a flat character and are not able to be represented in the same way in space
- Graphically, raster models represent reality in a better way. So, that graphical outputs under a raster model allow a somewhat more realistic representation of reality than vector models

VECTORIAL

Vector formats are very common in geographic information systems. They are ways of representing the special objects of the real world by means of geometric figures (point, line and polygon). Each point feature is represented as a single coordinate pair, while line and polygon features are represented as ordered lists of vertices. Spatial objects are any object or phenomenon that occupies a place in space.

Advantages:

- Great capacity to compact information using the smallest possible volume of GIS data.
- Surfaces and Distances calculations are more accurate than Raster
- Lines and points of easy definition and distribution, favouring the closest relationships between elements and making these files in a most optimal when you want to perform an analysis between spatial units which allows more precise limits
- In commercial terms, vector files are more widely used and shared, while raster files are more difficult to generate and obtain, and therefore are expensive
- Vector files are easier to build topological rules and conditions for than raster files, but on the other hand, they more easily generate topology problems (overlaps between elements of the same layer) (94)

It's usual to convert and transform both vector and raster geospatial data to various formats, there are many ways to convert GIS data and the conversion may use special conversion programs. Simply, it may involve complex data exporting or importing procedures.

Some of the Most Common Conversions are:

- KML to SHP
- KML to DXF
- KML to GeoJSON
- KMZ to KML
- KMZ to CSV
- KMZ to CSV
- KMZ to GPX
- FileGDB to SHP
- FileGDB to KML
- SHP to KML
- CSV to SHP
- CSV to KML
- TAB to KML
- GeoTIFF to AAIGrid

5.3.2.5. GIS software

ArcGIS Pro is a complete suite of GIS tools and probably the most popular GIS software, ArcGIS Pro is Esri's latest professional desktop GIS application. With ArcGIS Pro, it's possible to explore, visualize, and analyse data, create 2D maps and 3D scenes, and share cartography work with ArcGIS Online or an ArcGIS Enterprise portal. These details can be observed in Figure 55.

Figure 55 - ArcCatalog view. (95)

OPEN SOURCE GIS SOFTWARE

QGIS is an open-source Geographic Information System (GIS) and is one of the more popular and use friendly open-source GIS. The appearance of the software can be seen in Figure 56

Platforms: Linux, Unix, Mac OSX, and Windows.

Figure 56 - QGIS view. (96)

Grass is a GIS that provides powerful raster and vector capabilities as well as a geospatial processing engine in a single integrated suite. See Figure 57.

Platforms: Linux, Macintosh, Sun Solaris, Silicon Graphics Irix, HP-UX, DEC-Alpha, and Windows OS

Figure 57 - Grass view. (97)

uDig GIS is a free, open-source GIS desktop application designed to use OGC's OpenGIS standards such as WMS, WFS and more. Some aspects of the view of the program can be seen in Figure 58.

Platforms: Windows, Linux, Macintosh

Figure 58 - uDig GIS. (98)

GvSIG is known for its friendly user interface as well as being able to access the most widely used vector and raster formats today. The acronym gvSIG abbreviates the name Generalitat Valenciana Geographic Information System. See Figure 59.

Platforms: Windows, Macintosh, Linux, UNIX

Figure 59 - GvSIG view. (99)

Kosmo Desktop is a friendly desktop GIS application that allows to explore, edit, and analyse spatial data from a variety of databases, vector formats, and raster formats. Kosmo complies with OGC standards and provides excellent topological integrity. See Figure 60.

Platforms: Windows, Linux

Figure 60 - Kosmo Desktop view. (100)

OpenJUMP is a powerful and easy-to-use desktop GIS that allows users to edit, analyse, combine, save, and visualize geographic data. It is also an excellent platform for quick testing of custom GIS developments. See Figure 61.

Platforms: Windows, Macintosh, Linux, UNIX

Figure 61 - OpenJUMP view. (101)

MapWindow GIS is an open-source GIS application that can be extended through plugins. The application is built using Microsoft's .NET. For a visualisation of the software see Figure 62

Platforms: Windows

Figure 62 - MapWindow GIS view. (102)

FlowMap is a freeware application designed to analyse and display flow data. This application was developed at the Faculty of Geographical Sciences of the Utrecht University in the Netherlands.

Platforms: Windows

WEB SERVERS

GeoServer is a Web Server that allows to serve maps and data in different formats for Web applications, whether they are thin Web clients or desktop GIS programs. GeoServer is the reference implementation of the OGC standards: WFS and WCS, and is certified as a high performance implementation of the WMS standard. GeoServer is one of the core components of the Geospatial Web.

MapServer is an open-source platform for publishing spatial data and interactive mapping applications to the web. Originally developed in the mid-1990's at the University of Minnesota, MapServer is released under an MIT-style license, and runs on all major platforms (Windows, Linux, Mac OS X).

Deegree is a solution for Geographic Information Systems and Spatial Data Infrastructures (IDE's) based on both Web and desktop. It is composed of a set of Java Application Interfaces (APIs) and powerful object-relational mapping for simple and complex spatial schemas.

QGIS Server offers a web map service (WMS) based on the QGIS desktop application library.

WEB CLIENTS

OpenLayers is a lightweight web client with no dependency on specific map servers. It offers a simplified user interface that attacks WMS and WFS services in a transparent way for the user and developer. The characteristics for which OpenLayers has stood out in its diffusion in the community are the simplicity of use, the support of tiles and cache and the access to Google or Bing maps. See Figure 63.

Figure 63 - OpenLayers view (103).

Leaflet is designed with simplicity, performance, and ease of use in mind. It works efficiently on all major desktop and mobile platforms, taking advantage of HTML5 and CSS3 in modern browsers. See Figure 64.

Figure 64 - Leaflet view (104).

Cesium is an open-source JavaScript library for creating world-class 3D globes and maps with the best possible performance, precision, visual quality, and ease of use. Developers across industries, from aerospace to smart cities to drones, use CesiumJS to create interactive web apps for sharing dynamic geospatial data. Built on open formats, CesiumJS is designed for robust interoperability and scaling for massive datasets (105). See Figure 65.

Some of the main features of Cesium are:

- **3D tiles.** It's possible to design, and interact with 3D buildings, photogrammetry, and point clouds using the open 3D Tiles specification
- **3D models.** It can display 3D models using glTF, the runtime format for WebGL.
- **Terrain layers and images.** CesiumJS allows to stream global terrain images and layers using open standards and custom tile schemes
- **Vector layers and geometry.** It can be loaded KML, GeoJSON, and CZML, or use the API to draw a wide variety of geographic objects and geometries
- **Dynamic time display.** Leveraging world-class support for performing dynamic time simulation, transmitting real-time telemetry, and creating 4D visualizations

Figure 65 - Cesium view. (106)

OPEN-SOURCE GEODATABASES

PostGIS provides spatial support for the popular PostgreSQL object-relational database. Thus, it can be used as the underlying database for geographic information systems (GIS) and web mapping applications in the same way that Oracle Spatial does with the Oracle database. PostGIS is stable, fast, standards-compliant, has hundreds of spatial features, and is currently the most widely used open-source spatial database.

SpatiaLite is an SQLite database engine with spatial features added. SQLite is a very popular, simple, robust, easy to use and really lightweight engine. Each database is simply a file, which can be copied, compressed, sent over a network or the web without any complications.

MySQL spatial allows the generation, storage and analysis of geographic data, geometries such as points, lines or polygons. It includes functions that allow to work with spatial formats and perform spatial operations.

CARTOGRAPHIC TOOLS

GDAL is a translator library for vector and raster geospatial data formats that is released under an MIT-style open-source license by the Open Source Geospatial Foundation. As a library, it presents a single raster abstract data model and a single vector abstract data model to the calling application for all supported formats. It also comes with a variety of useful command line utilities for data translation and processing.

It provides a complete, consistent, and robust implementation of the fundamental algorithms for processing linear geometries in two-dimensional Cartesian spaces.

Java Topology Suite (JTS) is an open-source library of spatial functions for geometry processing that provides a complete, consistent, and robust implementation of the fundamental algorithms for processing linear geometries in two-dimensional Cartesian spaces.

GeoTools is an open-source Java library (LGPL) that provides tools for manipulating geospatial data, using data structures based on the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) specifications.

Sextante is a spatial data analysis library written in Java. The main objective of SEXTANTE is to provide a platform for easy implementation, deployment and use of rich geoprocessing functionality. It currently contains over three hundred algorithms for processing vector or raster data, as well as table analysis tools. SEXTANTE integrates perfectly with open-source Java GIS (such as gvSIG or OpenJump), proprietary GIS (ArcGIS) and tools that are not properly GIS (such as the WPS 52N server or the Talend ETL spatial distribution).

5.3.2.6. Database for cartographic Systems

A geo spatial database or geodatabase is a general-purpose database that has been enhanced to include spatial data that represents objects defined in geometric space, and tools for querying and analysing that data. The geodatabase is provided with:

- Storing a rich collection of spatial data in a centralized location
- Applying sophisticated rules and relationships to the data
- Defining advanced geospatial relational models (e.g., topologies, networks)
- Maintaining integrity of spatial data with a consistent, accurate database
- Working within a multiuser access and editing environment
- Integrating spatial data with other IT databases
- Easily scaling your storage solution
- Supporting custom features and behaviour
- Leveraging your spatial data to its full potential

Standardized geo-database design is based on a common set of fundamental GIS design steps. GIS design involves organizing geographic information into a series of data themes—layers that can be integrated using geographic location. So, it makes sense that geo-database design begins by identifying the data themes to be used, then specifying the contents and representations of each thematic layer.

Geographic representations are organized in a series of data themes (sometimes referred to as thematic layers). The characterization of each thematic layer will result in a specification of standard geodatabase data elements such as feature classes, tables, relationship classes, raster datasets, subtypes, topologies, domains, and so on. When identifying thematic layers in the design, each theme must be characterized in terms of its visual representations, its expected uses in the GIS, its likely data sources, and its levels of resolution. For example, at what scales and extents will we need to use this information, and how will its elements be represented at each scale? These characteristics help describe the high-level contents expected from each theme.

Once the key thematic layers are identified in the design phase, it's necessary to develop specifications for representing the contents of each thematic layer in the physical database:

- Map scales and extents that we'll need to work with.
- How the geographic features are to be represented (for example, as points, lines, polygons, raster, surfaces, or tabular attributes).
- How should the data be organized into feature classes, tables, and relationships?
- How will spatial and database integrity rules be used to implement GIS behaviour?

5.3.2.7. Spatial Analysis Services

Spatial analysis is the process of examining attributes, locations, and relationships between features of spatial data, by means of uses analytics, computational models, and algorithms is possible for instance to calculate the distance between geographic elements, the areas that overlap, calculate the areas affected by a possible flood etc. Some examples of how spatial analysis can be used in emergency management:

- Find the fastest route to the emergency site, including online traffic information.
- Find the fastest route in cities with narrow streets for large vehicles, such as firefighters, excluding streets where vehicles cannot circulate
- Modelling for emergency situations, such as tsunamis, hurricanes, chemical incidents, oil spills, and wildfires, and training emergency management teams to prepare for such incidents
- Mobilize rescue teams and send real-time alerts to a population at risk of being impacted by a hurricane, tsunami, forest fire, earthquake or a flood
- Combining multiple sources of information such satellite images, critical infrastructures' location, nearest hospital location, rescue teams' location to analyse what's going on during an emergency in order to come up with a cohesive response plan

5.3.2.8. Three-dimensional model

“Three-dimensional visual geographic information system is an important component of enterprise information system, which extends the manager's vision and hearing, so that manager can be faster and better grasp of enterprise information to adjust management decisions. Factories using information technology services in manufacturing, business management, decision support, will speed up and standardize corporate governance better, promote development of productive forces, which greatly enhance the core competitiveness of enterprises in order to simulate the real scenario in view of the effect of making the viewer through the visual impact to the immersive experience.” (107)

Three-dimensional visual geographic information system could be adjusted for the control and monitoring of **critical structures**. 3DVS could be an extension that provides tools to create, visualize and analyse GIS data in a three-dimensional (3D) context.

Especially for firefighters, in case of fire in facilities or buildings, it would be very useful if they could access 3D cartography of the facility.

It might be useful for other uses to be able to see in 3D the terrain where the emergency is occurring, possibly to make predictive models of fire progress or deploy personnel more efficiently.

SYSTEM DATABASE

“Including the fundamental database: integration of the plant based on the geographical terrain database; three-dimensional model database: three-dimensional model of the plant database including model and texture information) Pipeline, pipe network database: water, electricity, gas and other pipelines and other graphic and attribute information. Other Information Database: including the establishment of other databases such as post-video surveillance, firefighting facilities management database; provide basic data services.” (107)

SYSTEM PLATFORM

“System should establish a unified platform, to provide application services on this basis. The platform should have built a unified spatial data engine module, the data exchange module (for example, two-dimensional and three-dimensional model data, based on the exchange of graphic data), while taking advantage of three-dimensional GIS platform features integrated visual roaming browsing platform.” (107)

SYSTEM APPLICATION

“Developed based on a unified platform for the various application subsystems should have different rights management to serve different users, the various subsystems into a user object should be to provide different services.” (107)

Exploiting 3D models

3D model of the event locations can play an important role in planning the operations. Elaborating digital mapping 3D after an event and compare to the situation prior to the event (such as in earthquake MCI) can provide insight of the structure damage and help designing action plans.

3D DTM (Digital terrain Model) can be generated from satellite or from aircrafts with assistance of LRF (Laser Range Finder) to perform Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS). This can be performed also by drones, as presented in Figure 66.

Figure 66 - Example of a LiDAR use (108).

3D DTM models are generated from the Laser cloud points, by generically following the process presented in Figure 67.

Figure 67 - Process for 3D DTM models generation (109).

The result is a 3D mesh map with Z elevation, subsequently presented in Figure 68.

Figure 68 - Example of a 3D mesh map with Z elevation (110).

By collecting LRF data from the event site in a continuous way and generating the 3D DTM models, allows the identification of potential damages/impacts on the terrain, or in the city frame.

The same principle can be used by having smaller drones mapping specific areas of a city or other critical infrastructure for later compare and assess the damages.

3D maps provide valuable insight and information to:

- Have a Tri-dimensional understanding of the geographical situation
- To compare different time maps to assess the differences and impacts
- Include the tri dimensional parameter in the decision process, optimization and decision making
- Place the georeferenced assets in a 3D context in the COP (mitigate location errors)
- Use the 3D maps to support events simulation: fire propagation, earthquake damage, water/floods impacts

5.3.3. Data analysis and standard procedures (orient)

Information integration is about making sense of data in an agile and effective manner in the midst of uncertain or ambiguous situations. It is the ability to "orient" to continuously sensed data.

In emergency management, this integration takes place at various levels of the emergency response, both at the scene and at more distant C2 centres.

The human element remains undoubtedly the most important element in the orient Boyd's OODA LOOP process, integrating all the perceived information, but it is also one of the areas where new technological capabilities can provide the greatest impetus.

Visualisation technologies that integrate text, graphics, video and sound provide real-time situational awareness that support high-level C2 functions rather than data mining and other methods that reduce data streams to meaningful components (111).

In order to collaborate and create a framework that will in cooperate all the aforementioned technologies that will enable OODA Loop, there should a methodology on how the technologies interact with each other. The overall loop can be achieved through a process of data sharing and mining. In order to go through every step of OODA, we have first to analyse the data sharing between multiple parties and collecting relevant information. The OODA Loop is a critical decision making machine that needs access to specific data starting from QIS data for monitoring and mapping for the areas depending on the use cases. Units that are available on site and close. We should be responsible for the decision, what variable should take into consideration for the decision.

A set of rules must be regulated in order specific persons and authorities have the capabilities to make the right decisions.

The best way for the acting approach is to first validate the data and then move forward with the acting plans.

5.3.3.1. Big Data Analytics

The inputs to the system correspond to the thousands of data from use cases scenarios, victims, survivors, casualties, decisions that were taken.

Those are some of data that will be involved into the platform. So, as to how we could better make use of such data, we could establish databases that will be used for data mining and future models.

The appropriate algorithm must be in cooperate to the framework, to establish connectivity with all the data that are being transferred through the platform.

Also, blockchain can used as a method to interact with specific datasets and create statistical analytics and won't be altered, providing a better insight to the interactions, the parties involved and decision making opportunities based on the smart contracts deployed on the platform.

INTRODUCTION

Big data technology refers to the advanced technology of collecting, storing and using data by using software tools in a certain period of time. Big data technology has five characteristics, namely volume, velocity, variety, value and veracity.

A new "v" of value has also recently been added: data by itself, even if there is a lot of it, does not provide value to a company or organization. It is their **treatment**, through a process of hypothesis formulation, creation of statistical and semantic models, and the definition of short- or long-term algorithms, which makes it possible to discover the meaning hidden in these large volumes of data. See Table 26 and Table 27.

Data collection characteristics	
1	A loss of competitiveness, by devoting resources to low-value tasks
2	Delays in value-generating activities as time is wasted in other activities
3	Limitations in the information to a few emergencies' functional areas
4	Poor integration between data
5	In most cases, the information provided is very detailed and not very aggregated, making it difficult to obtain "global visions"

Table 26 - Data collection characteristics.

Business Intelligence (BI) advantages	
1	Reduction and even elimination of the resources needed to obtain information. In this way, users can focus on their main activities and others that add value to the Emergency system
2	Cost reduction. Repetitive tasks for obtaining information are eliminated
3	Reduction of errors. A greater anticipation in decision making (due to a faster availability of information) implies a reduction of errors caused by hasty decisions and without information elements
4	Reach to all users. Although with its limitations and restrictions by user profiles, BI allows reaching all functional areas of the organization
5	Multiple dimensions and metrics. Allows end users to define their own ad hoc queries
6	Great interaction among data: aggregation, disaggregation, segmentation, etc. This will provide many different views than those offered by a traditional reporting system
7	Unification in a single system of all the information of interest to the organization through the consolidation of the various existing transactional sources. This single repository avoids redundancies and duplications, as well as a unique and understandable environment for users

Table 27 - Business Intelligence (BI) advantages.

Current C2 applications are divided by agencies. Each Emergency Service has their own applications as well as there is a complex interoperability issue in terms of data sharing. While each agency needs to visualize its most relevant data to optimize care resources, there is no platform to visualize data from other agencies in other countries. Nevertheless this applications are currently running on the Emergency Services are complying with their requirements. Otherwise rescue coverage for the injured could not be guaranteed.

DATA GOVERNANCE AND EXPLOITATION

Data governance is the management of the availability, integrity, usability, and security of data used in an enterprise in order to support business objectives. Data governance must ensure that data is authorized, organized, and with the necessary user permissions in a database, with as few errors as possible, while maintaining privacy and security.

An organization needs to change from traditional data management to Data Governance when any of these situations are given:

- The organization has become great and traditional management is not able to deal with multifunctional activities related to the data.
- The organization's data systems have become so complicated that with traditional management it is not possible to deal with multifunctional activities related to the data.

- Organization's data architects or other groups need the support of a multifunctional program that has the vision about the concerns and data preferences throughout the company.
- Regulations, norms, compliance or contractual requirements require a more formal data.

Below are the principles of Data Governance:

- **Integrity:** Participants in Data Government will practice integrity in their relationships with others. They will be truthful and communicative when involved in discussions, restrictions, options, and impacts for data -related decisions.
- **Transparency:** Data Government processes will exhibit transparency. It should be clear to all participants and auditors, how and when the decisions related to the data were introduced in the processes.
- **Auditability:** Decisions related to data as well as processes and controls subject to Data Government will be auditable and will be accompanied by the documentation that can support the requirements based on audit.
- **Responsibility:** Data Government will define responsibilities for multifunctional decisions related to processes and controls.
- **Management:** Data Governance will define responsibilities for management activities, which are the responsibilities of individual contributors as well as the responsibilities of the group of data administrators.
- **Control and balance:** Data Government will define responsibilities as a way to introduce controls and balance between business and technology, and also among those who create and collect information, those who manage it, those who use it, and those that introduce the rules and rules and Requirements for compliance.
- **Standardization:** Data Governance will enter and support the company's standardization.
- **Change management:** Data Governance will support proactive and reactive activities for change management, for reference data values, master data and metadata.

Data Governance seeks to create policies that outline data ownership, responsibilities, and delegations. By developing standard data formats and definitions, the goal is to create a unified understanding of each data store in the system. Data Governance attempts to enable safe judgments based on trusted data assets. Key Benefits of Data Governance tools are listed below:

- As data and apps have grown more important to businesses, Data Governance Tools and Technologies have become more important to ensure the integrity of data assets. Let's have a look at some of the benefits of Data Governance Tools.
- **Creates a Standardized View:** In business terminology and concepts, inconsistencies are common as various users employ different phrases to describe the same concept. Hence, a business dictionary is included in Data Governance Tools to guarantee that all terminology is standardized and that everyone is on the same page.
- **Effectively Collaborate Business Information:** Data Governance Tools organizes all of a company's data into an easy-to-navigate data catalogue, allowing people with the appropriate rights to view and collaborate on data in minutes. This is accomplished through self-service, hence, reducing the workload on data teams.

- **Increased Data Literacy and Understanding:** Everyone in your organization must be data literate to leverage data assets to make better business choices if you want to succeed as a data-driven firm. A Data Governance Tool is a simple platform that allows corporate users to locate and collaborate on data assets. As practically every operation can be completed through self-service, this allows users to become more literate while also relieving the burden on data teams.
- **Compliance and Regulation:** Every sector has its own set of rules, and non-compliance with these regulations may result in hefty penalties. Hence, Data Governance Tools ensure compliance with regulations while also safeguarding security and privacy.

Below there are listed some recommended steps when creating a Data Governance plan:

- **Granular Data Access and Authorization.** At the lowest level, to protect sensitive data by hiding it and have confidential contracts for data scientists and BI analysts. This can be done with data masking capabilities and different views where raw data is blocked as much as possible and gradually more access is provided until, at the top, administrators are given more visibility.
- **Perimeter security, data protection and integrated authentication.** It is important to build a good perimeter and put a firewall around the data, integrated with existing authentication systems and standards. With authentication, it's about looking at how to integrate with LDAP [Lightweight Directory Access Protocol], Active Directory, and other directory services. Tools such as Kerberos can also be supported for authentication support. But the important thing is not to create a separate infrastructure, but to integrate it into the existing structure.
- **Data Encryption and Tokenization.** Ensure files and personally identifiable information (PII) are encrypted and tokenized from end to end of the data pipeline.
- **Continuous Audit and Analysis.** This level of visibility and accountability at every step of the process is what enables IT to "govern" the data instead of simply setting policies and access controls and hoping for the best. Continuous audit is a method to perform control and risk assessments automatically on a more frequent basis, allowing business leaders and/or their advisors to monitor and improve data continuously.
- **Unified data architecture.** Enterprise data management strategy, you need to think about the details of granular access, authentication, security, encryption, and auditing. But it must not stop there. Rather you should think about how each of these components fits into your overall data architecture. It reformulates how information is obtained ingested, managed, circulated and persistent. It is designed to accommodate new and emerging information use cases including established practices such as reports, dashboards, and dashboards; business analysis, analytical discovery and advanced analysis; and (of course) big data analytics.

Data Governance goals can be achieved more quickly and easily with the right tool. Some of the widely used Data Governance Tools are listed below:

- **Alation Data Catalog** offers users a single point of reference for numerous data sources, making it easier to identify and locate the information. The Alation data catalog aids in the automation of Governance operations such as updating data dictionaries and training users about good Governance principles, as well as offering collaborative options for information sharing.

- **Ataccama** is a Platform-as-a-Service for self-driven Data Management and Governance. It makes data administration simple with AI-driven automated capabilities. With a “self-driving” strategy aimed to automate, increase efficiency, and convenience of use, Ataccama ONE automatically analyses data quality and classifies data to help firms prioritize and concentrate. All essential data assets can have security and privacy regulations automatically enforced, making data available to those who need it.
- **Collibra** is a Data governance tool for enterprises that automates data operations and keeps cross-functional teams on the same page. It provides Natural Language Search, Data Governance Automation, and Data Stewardship. Users can use Collibra’s interactive data lineage diagrams to graphically understand data elements like regulations, problems, relationships, and flow. It has its own data catalog powered by Machine Learning, that can be connected to the business glossary and governance standards.
- **SAP Master Data Governance (SAP MDG)**, is accessible on-premises or in the Cloud. It is developed to perform effective enterprise data management, decrease risk, improve compliance, and lower the total cost of ownership. SAP MDG consolidates master data, automates replication and syndication of master data throughout the system landscape. It also measures, monitors, and improves master data quality and workflows.
- **Informatica** offers Data Governance and Compliance services. Its enterprise Data Governance solution is available in the Cloud or on-premise. It is the most tried-and-true solution, allowing business and IT to work together seamlessly. Informatica creates a data catalog by scanning across many Cloud platforms automatically. It allows for data lineage tracking to be done automatically. It keeps track of data migration, from high-level system views to granular column-level lineage, and analyses the impact. Informatica dismantles silos and brings together IT, security, and business teams to guarantee that data is compliant with regulations such as GDPR (General Data Protection Legislation).
- **IBM Data Governance** assists in locating data objects, as well as their physical location, definition, attributes, and application. It works with both structured and unstructured data. It can assist you in reducing compliance risks. IBM Data Governance offers features such as a flexible Data Governance plan, Data Cataloguing, and acquiring valuable data for Big Data initiatives. It also enables privacy and security features, such as the ability to secure personally identifiable information, predictive consumer intelligence, and personal health data

Within organizations, different levels of data use can be recognized:

- **Operational level:** Information systems are used to monitor the elementary activities and transactions of the organization. They are systems that have gained a significant boom in the last decade as a result of organizational development oriented to the global market.
- **Knowledge level:** At this level we find knowledge and data workers, covering the core of traditional massive data capture operations and basic data processing services, with predefined tasks.
- **Administration level:** Intermediate-level administrator tasks are carried out, supporting analysis, monitoring, control and decision-making activities, querying information

stored in the system, providing reports and facilitating the management of information by the intermediate levels.

- **Strategic level:** Its objective is to carry out long-term planning activities, both at the management level and the objectives that an organization has.

Big Data is a term that describes the large volume of data, both structured and unstructured, that floods businesses every day. But it is not the amount of data that is important. What matters with Big Data is what organizations do with the data. Big Data can be analysed for insights that lead to better decisions and strategic business moves.

On-Line Transactional Processing systems (OLTP) are the operational systems that capture business transactions and persist them in relational structures called Databases. OLTP systems applies to operational and knowledge level. The main characteristics of OLTP systems are:

- OLTP systems carry out real-time transactions of a business process, with which the stored data changes continuously. OLTP systems in their transactions drive essential business processes.
- OLTP systems are responsible for data maintenance, either adding data, performing updates or deleting it.
- Data structures must be optimized to validate their input, and reject them if they do not meet certain business rules.
- For decision making, it provides limited capabilities since it is not its objective, therefore it is not a priority in its design. It is not a good idea to obtain certain historical information related to the business by querying an OLTP system, because it would have a negative impact on the operation of the system.

On-Line Analytical Processing systems (OLAP) provide an alternative to transactional systems, offering an analysis-oriented view of data and fast and flexible data navigation. OLAP systems applies to the administration and strategic level of data. OLAP is the technology for business intelligence systems, The following are characteristics that OLAP technology possesses:

- OLAP databases have a schema that is optimized so that questions asked by users are answered quickly.
- The questions that are asked to an OLAP must allow an interactive use with the users.
- OLAP cubes store multiple levels of data made up of highly optimized structures that respond to the company's business expectations.
- An OLAP system is prepared to make complex reports in a simple way.
- OLAP provides a multidimensional view of data. Cubes provide a multidimensional view of data that extends beyond the two-dimensional analysis that can be provided by a simple spreadsheet used as such.
- Users can easily change the rows, columns, and pages in OLAP reports, being able to read the information in the way that is most convenient for analysis.

Business Intelligence (BI) refers to the use of strategies and tools that serve to transform data into knowledge, with the aim of improving the decision-making process in an organization. BI applies to the administration and strategic level of data, tools and disciplines listed below are used to support the decision-making task:

- **Data Warehousing:** Data Warehouses are based on multidimensional structures (cubes) in which information is stored by previously calculating all combinations of all levels of all analysis openings. It is, to put it bluntly, a Cartesian product that stores all combinations. It can be said that this method is exaggerated or wild and in part this statement is true. What should not be lost sight of is that this "savage" is the price paid by the organization to be able to make correct decisions. The cost of acquiring SW or HW will always be cheaper than the cost of a decision made at the wrong time.
- **Data Mart: (DM)** is a data warehouse oriented to a specific area of the organization such as Sales, Human Resources or other sectors in an organization.
- **Data Mining:** It is associated with the Strategic Level of an organization and aims to eliminate the errors made by people when analysing the data due to prejudices and let the data show the underlying models in them. Data Mining helps to create new models not perceived by the analyst until that moment but that really exist in the data.

Data exploitation is understood as the process that tries to discover patterns in large volumes of data sets, using business intelligence systems, machine learning, statistics and database systems. The general goal of the exploitation process is to extract information from a data set and transform it into an understandable structure for summarize all relevant information and make it available to decision makers.

For the construction of a BI system, the following stages must be covered:

- Identification of needs and requirements.
- Recognition of the original data sources and their structures.
- Based on the requirements, define the auxiliary tables and the data selection, transformation and import processes.
- Build the multidimensional scheme. It must be checked that this schema agrees with the requirements and the auxiliary tables, as a first form of testing.
- Access to the system from the analysts' workstations, obtaining the information identified in the requirements stage.

To convert data into information, it is necessary to understand how the data stored in operational systems can be interpreted, determining:

- How the facts that we want to measure are related to the data that we can obtain.
- Understanding how this data reflects goals and objectives that encompass the business involved.

Data that feeds a BI system comes from different sources, these sources are from different operational systems that an organization has, generally these data sources are heterogeneous, so it will be necessary to make all the pertinent adaptations.

ETL is a type of data integration that refers to the three steps (extract, transform, load) used to mix data from multiple sources. It is often used to build a data warehouse for a BI system. During this process, data is taken (extracted) from a source system, converted (transformed) into a storable format, and stored (loaded) into a data warehouse or other system. Extract, Load, Transform (ELT) is an alternate but related approach designed to funnel processing to the database to improve performance.

BI TOOLS can be necessary to convert data into valuable information for the organization, below there are list the best-known BI tools:

- **MicroStrategy** is business intelligence software that has a wide range of data analysis capabilities. It has high performance and advanced features such as data discovery, advanced analytics, data visualizations, built-in business intelligence, reporting, real-time reports, predictive analysis, etc. See Figure 69 for the interface of this software. Some of its main features are:
 - ROLAP Multi-source, which allows you to access and analyse the information stored in various data sources regardless of their origin and format.
 - ROLAP In-memory, technology designed to get better performance from 64-bit based architectures and capable of creating an intermediate level database.
 - Friendly web interface, which has been improved to offer users faster and more powerful access to functions.
 - Automatic distribution of messages, both at the level of reports and dashboards or alerts, which allows the IT department to be relieved of manual tasks.
 - Improved SQL engine, which allows you to reduce SQL commands and statements by up to 66% to increase platform performance.

Figure 69 - MicroStrategy view. (112)

- **PowerBI** is a Microsoft data analytics service aimed at providing interactive visualizations and business intelligence capabilities. It has connectors that work together to turn unrelated data sources into visually compelling, interactive, and consistent information. Data source can be an Excel spreadsheet or a collection of hybrid cloud-based and on-premises data stores. Power BI makes it easy to connect to data sources, visualize and discover what's important, and share it with anyone or as many users as you want. See Figure 70 for details of its interface. Power BI consists of several elements that work together:
 - Windows desktop app called Power BI Desktop.
 - Online SaaS (software as a service) service called Power BI service.
 - Power BI mobile apps for Windows, iOS, and Android devices.

- Power BI Report Builder, to create paginated reports and share them in the Power BI service.
- Power BI Report Server, a local report server where it is possible to publish Power BI reports after creating them in Power BI Desktop.

Figure 70 - Power BI view (113).

- **Oracle Analytics** provides a comprehensive suite of business intelligence solutions designed to meet the data processing, data presentation, and visualization needs of an organization. Oracle Analytics also offers tools for reporting and interactive self-service dashboards for performing deep analytical tasks needed for the day-to-day functioning of an organization. Oracle analytics uses machine learning technology, natural language processing, and other AI technologies to power data analytics practices across an organization. The platform can be deployed in the cloud or on-premises which makes it a fast and easy path to increasing data-driven productivity across an organization (see Figure 71). Oracle provides a range of products:
 - Oracle Analytics Desktop makes it possible for users to run their data exploration and data visualization tasks directly on their PC with no server or cloud required. This is a simple software that enables quick exploration of local datasets and can be used for simple data analytics and investigation.
 - Oracle Analytics Cloud is an all-in-one cloud-based business intelligence platform. With OAC, users can connect data from multiple sources and perform various data processing operations on the data set from the convenience of a web browser on any preferred device.
 - Oracle Analytics Server is designed for organizations that want to make use of Oracle Analytics capabilities but would prefer to have the framework deployed on-premises.
 - Oracle Fusion Analytics Warehouse (FAW) is a framework built upon the Oracle Analytics Cloud system and powered by the Oracle Autonomous Data Warehouse. Enterprises that make use of FAW start by deploying Oracle Application Clouds which they then expand by rapidly personalizing and extending it.

Figure 71 - Decks view. (114)

- **Qlik** is a Business Intelligence platform that allows to collect, process and extract the value of a company's data so that this data is accessible by all the personnel of an organization. It allows augmented intelligence on the data through associative indexing that automatically generates knowledge about the data so that it can be explored by users. See Figure 72 for details. Qlik is composed of the following components:
 - Qlik Sense uses AI to help users understand and use data more effectively, minimizing cognitive bias, amplifying discovery, and increasing data literacy. The main features of Qlik sense are:
 - Analysis and insights generated by AI
 - Automated creation and data preparation
 - Search and interaction in natural language
 - Machine learning and predictive analytics
 - QlikView is as such a BI solution that allows to analyse and use information from different data sources. Qlik view allows to do the following tasks:
 - Creation of User Interface (UI) to work with Data Warehouse.
 - Elaboration of presentations through the data.
 - Carrying out statistical analyses on the data.
 - Construction of expert systems.
 - Obtain the relationships between the data and what they represent for the company.
 - Creation of dynamic graphics.
 - Obtaining new tables through the integration of different data sources.

Figure 72 - Qlik view. (115)

- **Pentaho** is an open source solution-oriented, process-focused Business Intelligence (BI) platform that includes all the components required to implement process-driven solutions such as data mining, ETL, reporting, etc. (See Figure 73). Pentaho offers a number of useful products such as the following:
 - Pentaho Reporting: It is a presentation engine capable of generating programmatic reports based on an XML definition file.
 - Pentaho Dashboard: It is an integrated platform to provide information about organization data, where it's possible to view reports, graphs, etc.
 - Pentaho Data Mining: It is a software suite that uses machine learning, automatic and data mining strategies. It has the necessary tools to support descriptive analysis tasks.
 - Pentaho for Apache Hadoop: It is a low-level connector to facilitate access to large volumes managed in the Apache Hadoop project.
 - Pentaho Analysis Services: Supports MDX, and the XML behaviour language for analysis and interface specifications.
 - Pentaho Data Integration (PDI) provides the Extract, Transform, and Load (ETL) capabilities that facilitates the process of capturing, cleansing, and storing data using a uniform and consistent format that is accessible and relevant to end users and IoT technologies.

Figure 73 - Pentaho view. (116)

DATA EXPLORATION AND VISUALIZATION TOOLS (DASHBOARD AND REPORTS)

Data visualization is today a key area in the world of data, where we have ever larger volumes of data that are growing faster and that are of very varied natures and structures.

For organizations that aspire to be data-driven, it is essential to have the ability to interpret and extract knowledge from these huge amounts of data, and here visualization plays a fundamental role.

Well-designed dashboards are tools that help to synthesize the situation in an emergency, so it is important to know the possibilities that currently exist. The most popular tools for dashboard design are listed below:

Kibana (Elasticsearch)	
Introduction	<p><i>“Kibana is a data visualization and exploration tool used for log and time-series analytics, application monitoring, and operational intelligence use cases. It offers powerful and easy-to-use features such as histograms, line graphs, pie charts, heat maps, and built-in geospatial support.</i></p> <p><i>Kibana supports only Elasticsearch data and no other data source. But it has a feature-rich and well-developed integration with Elasticsearch. It provides excellent data searching and exploration functionalities for Elasticsearch source” (117).</i></p>

Kibana (Elasticsearch)	
Interface	<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 74 - Kibana view (117).</p>
Dashboards	<p><i>“The best way to understand your data is to visualize it. With dashboards, you can turn your data from one or more data views into a collection of panels that bring clarity to your data, tell a story about your data, and allow you to focus on only the data that’s important to you. Panels display your data in charts, tables, maps, and more, which allow you to compare your data side-by-side to identify patterns and connections. Dashboards support several types of panels to display your data, and several options to create panels.” (118)</i></p>

Table 28 - Tools for dashboard design - Kibana

Grafana	
Introduction	<p><i>“Grafana is a multi-platform open source analytics and interactive visualization web application. It provides charts, graphs, and alerts for the web when connected to supported data sources. A licensed Grafana Enterprise version with additional capabilities is also available as a self-hosted installation or an account on the Grafana Labs cloud service. It is expandable through a plug-in system. End users can create complex monitoring dashboards using interactive query builders. Grafana is divided into a front end and back end, written in TypeScript and Go, respectively.” (119)</i></p>
Interface	

Grafana	
	<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 75 - Grafana view (119)</p>
Dashboards	<p><i>“Not only do Grafana dashboards give insightful meaning to data collected from numerous sources, but you can also share the dashboards you create with other team members, allowing you to explore the data together. With Grafana, anyone can create and share dynamic dashboards to foster collaboration and transparency. Flexibility and versatility Translate and transform any of your data into flexible and versatile dashboards. Unlike other tools, Grafana allows you to build dashboards specifically for you and your team. With advanced querying and transformation capabilities, you can customize your panels to create visualizations that are actually helpful for you.” (120)</i></p>

Table 29 - Tools for dashboard design - Grafana

Splunk	
Introduction	<p><i>“Splunk Inc. is an American software company based in San Francisco, California, that produces software for searching, monitoring, and analysing machine-generated data via a Web-style interface. Its software helps capture, index and correlate real-time data in a searchable repository, from which it can generate graphs, reports, alerts, dashboards and visualizations. Splunk uses machine data for identifying data patterns, providing metrics, diagnosing problems and providing intelligence for business operations. Splunk is a horizontal technology used for application management, security and compliance, as well as business and web analytics.” (121)</i></p>

Splunk	
Interface	<p>The screenshot displays several Splunk dashboard panels. At the top left, 'Application Incident Management (Last 24 hours)' shows a bar chart with categories: Moderate (310), Critical (36), High (0), and Resolved (1,637). To its right, 'Performance Metrics (Last 24 hours)' shows line graphs for Latency (5ms), Response Time (310ms), 4xx Errors (310), and 5xx Errors (4,109). Below these are panels for 'Single Values (by month)', 'Account Management & Custom Logins (Last hour)', 'Current Running Processes' (a table with columns for ID, PID, PROCESS, and SUBMIT_STAGE), 'Content Distribution Network Health' (a horizontal bar chart), and 'Populated Health (Last 24 hours)' (a donut chart showing 92% populated health).</p>
	<p>Figure 76 - Splunk (121).</p>
Dashboards	<p><i>“Dashboards are views that are made up of panels. The panels can contain modules such as search boxes, fields, charts, tables, and lists. Dashboard panels are usually connected to reports. After you create a search visualization or save a report, you can add it to a new or existing dashboard. There is also a Dashboard Editor that you can use to create and edit dashboards. The Dashboard Editor is useful when you have a set of saved reports that you want to quickly add to a dashboard.”</i> (122)</p>

Table 30 - Tools for dashboard design - Splunk

Apache superset	
Introduction	<p>Superset is a multi-platform open source enterprise-ready business intelligence web application for data exploration and data visualization, it is able to handle data at petabyte scale (big data). It is fast, lightweight, intuitive, and loaded with options that make it easy for users of all skill sets to explore and visualize their data, from simple line charts to highly detailed geospatial charts.</p> <p>It supports a lot of data sources, it can connect to any SQL based datasource through SQLAlchemy and python driver, including modern cloud native databases and engines at petabyte scale.</p>

Apache superset	
Interface	<p>The screenshot displays the Apache Superset dashboard interface. At the top, it shows 'Superset Community Metrics' with a 'Pub.Liked' status and an 'EDIT DASHBOARD' button. Below this, there are several visualization widgets: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 90D PRs Source: A pie chart showing 'Present' (27%), 'Other' (18%), and 'Active' (12%). 30D PRs Source: A pie chart showing 'Present' (49.72%), 'Other' (25.13%), and 'Active' (19.9%). PRs by organization: A line chart showing PR counts over time from 2016 to 2020. PRs % by Org: A stacked area chart showing the percentage of PRs by organization over time. Leaderboard: A table listing users and their metrics (PRs, comments, reactions, reviews). 2BD Leaderboard: A table listing organizations and their metrics (PRs, comments, reactions, reviews). Top 25 Contributors Stream: A stream chart showing the activity of top contributors over time. </p>
Dashboards	<p>Superset ships with a wide array of beautiful visualizations. Its visualization plug-in architecture makes it easy to build custom visualizations that drop directly into Superset.</p> <p>Superset has tools to explore the data, a SQL lab to design queries and analyse response times, and a complete library of visualizations like charts, tables, detailed geospatial charts, etc.</p>

Figure 77 - Apache superset (123).

Table 31 - Tools for dashboard design - Apache superset

ArcGIS Dashboards	
Introduction	<p><i>"ArcGIS is a family of client software, server software, and online geographic information system (GIS) services developed and maintained by Esri. ArcGIS was first released in 1999 and originally was released as ARC/INFO, a command line based GIS system for manipulating data. ARC/INFO was later merged into ArcGIS Desktop, which was eventually superseded by ArcGIS Pro in 2015. ArcGIS Pro works in 2D and 3D for cartography and visualization, and includes Artificial Intelligence (AI). Esri also provides server side ArcGIS software for web maps, known as "ArcGIS Server"."</i> (124)</p>

ArcGIS Dashboards	
Interface	
Dashboards	<p><i>“ArcGIS Dashboards enables users to convey information by presenting location-based analytics using intuitive and interactive data visualizations on a single screen. Every organization using the ArcGIS platform can take advantage of ArcGIS Dashboards to help make decisions, visualize trends, monitor status in real time, and inform their communities. Tailor dashboards to your audiences, giving them the ability to slice the data to get the answers they need. Dashboards are essential information products, like maps and apps, providing a critical component to your geospatial infrastructure.” (125)</i></p>

Table 32 - Tools for dashboard design - ArcGIS Dashboards

Power BI Report Server	
Introduction	<p><i>“Power BI Report Server is an on-premises report server with a web portal in which you display and manage reports and KPIs. Along with it come the tools to create Power BI reports, paginated reports, mobile reports, and KPIs. Your users can access those reports in different ways: viewing them in a web browser or mobile device, or as an email in their in-box.” (126)</i></p>
Interface	

Power BI Report Server	
	<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 79 - Power BI Report Server (126).</p>
Reports	<p><i>“Paginated reports (.rdl) are document-style reports with visualizations, in which tables expand horizontally and vertically to display all their data, continuing from page to page as needed. They're great for generating fixed-layout, pixel-perfect documents optimized for printing, such as PDF and Word files.</i></p> <p><i>You can create paginated reports using Report Builder or Report Designer in SQL Server Data Tools (SSDT).”</i></p>

Table 33 - Tools for dashboard design - Power BI Report Server

Pentaho Report Designer	
Introduction	<p><i>“Pentaho Report Designer is a sophisticated report creation tool that you can use standalone, or as part of the larger Pentaho Business Analytics distribution. It enables professionals to create highly detailed, print-quality reports based on adequately prepared data from virtually any data source. Report Designer is one of several ways to create reports with Pentaho software. Through the Pentaho Server's Web-based Pentaho User Console, you can also use the Interactive Reporting interface, or you can integrate the Pentaho Reporting engine (on which Report Designer is built) into your own software.” (127)</i></p>
Interface	

Figure 80 - Pentaho Reporter Designer (128)

Table 34 - Tools for dashboard design - Pentaho Report Designer

5.3.3.2. Standard Operating Procedures (SOP)

A standard operating procedure (SOP) is a series of step-by-step instructions developed by a company to assist employees in doing everyday tasks. SOPs are designed to increase efficiency, quality output, and performance uniformity while reducing miscommunication and noncompliance with industry laws.

Because a military SOP refers to a unit's specific processes, which are not necessarily common to another unit, the military occasionally uses the term standing (rather than standard) operating procedure. The term "standard" can imply that only one (standard) technique should be followed by all units.

SOPs are "precise, written instructions to achieve uniformity of the performance of a specific function" in clinical research, according to the International Council for Harmonisation (ICH). SOPs are commonly used in pharmaceutical manufacturing and related clinical trials (129).

There, the emphasis is always on the consistent implementation of unchanging processes and procedures, as well as the documentation of such processes and procedures, so ensuring the separation of origins, causes, and effects. Triage is a further use, in which restricted resources are used based on a ranking, urgency, and staffing capacity assessment.

SOPs are mostly the responsibility of the study director. Individuals in the Quality Assurance Unit are in charge of ensuring that the study report and testing adhere to the SOP. New employees can utilize a SOP to answer inquiries instead of interrupting supervisors to inquire about how an operation is carried out.

ISO 9001 is an international quality standard that essentially requires the identification of processes (recorded as standard operating procedures) used in any manufacturing process that may affect product quality. Procedures are used extensively to aid in working safely. Safe work methods statements (SWMS, pronounced 'Swims') are another name for them (130).

They are frequently preceded by various techniques of analysing tasks or jobs to be performed in the workplace, such as a job safety analysis approach, in which dangers are identified and control measures are specified. Procedures must be tailored to the user's literacy levels, and readability is a crucial component of this. A successful standard operating procedure defines the processes required to execute a task and warns employees about any potential risks. The handbook should be concise and easy to follow, with a focus on how to accomplish things rather than what must be done. The SOP should be reviewed and updated every six to twelve months to ensure that it stays relevant to the organization's standards and requirements; any changes should be documented.

Organizations should develop a list of all their business processes to determine which operations may benefit from a SOP. Managers should talk about their staff' daily responsibilities and tasks to ensure that all procedures are covered. SOPs should be created for any tasks that are performed by many employees

Deploy Standard Operational Procedures concepts in terms of technologies regarding emergencies such as suggestions for coordinator for an increasing of decision-making. I.e., which questions are suggested by C&C application depending on incident typification. Artificial Intelligence chapter could be added as well as decision trees as.

SOPs are the way of improving preparedness and response in incident managing. SOP must include the vast majority of situations that may occur when managing a security or emergency incident, thus avoiding any delay and errors that may happen when taking decisions under stress situations.

Different types of SOPs are defined that should help decision-making at different situations during the life cycle of an incident. The different situation types of SOPs that could be proposed described below:

- During the process of receiving an incident.
 - Call takers:
 - List of actions that the operator must carry out depending on the type and location of an incident, these actions may be recommendations or questions that must be asked to the caller or manual actions that the operator must carry out related to the incident
 - Proposal of emergency and security agencies to be activated based on the type and location of an incident
 - Supervisors:
 - Supervision of available operators and generation of alarms when few operators are available
 - Supervision of call queue and generation of alarms in case of call flooding
 - Activation of customized messages with Text to Speech and possibility of Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR)
- During the process of incident dispatching
 - Dispatching operators:
 - Recommendation of most appropriate operative teams or first responders to be assigned to an incident, according to the following rules:

- Resource status. Operative teams may have several tasks to attend to, the system will take into account when is calculating the most appropriate resource proposal if team is available, initially proposing those that are available (not working in an intervention at that time)
- Suitable skills of operative teams, as defined in the Action Plan. Based on the type of incident, the most appropriate type of resources (human and material) to deal with. Thus, the types of vehicles for the intervention can be defined or if special skills are required for certain types of incidents (for example, in the case of a gender-based violence incident, the suitability of the equipment could be established based on if it has a female component)
- Area of action and proximity. The resources whose area of action includes the location of the incident are initially proposed (in the case that, for example, operative teams are defined by districts, neighbourhoods or similar). In addition, the system automatically calculates the distance to the place of the incident and first proposes those resources that are closest
 - In some incidents generate a list of recommended actions to be carried out by the operator
- Dispatching operators and supervisors:
 - Supervision of the response time in the intervention of an incident with the possibility of generating alarms if the pre-established times are exceeded
 - Supervision of the number of resources available in each area of influence with the possibility of an alarm if the pre-established thresholds are exceeded
- Supervisors
 - Supervision of the number of incidents assigned to each dispatch operator with generation of alarms in case of exceeding the pre-established thresholds

In the context of emergency, a definition of a **major emergency** is any event (happening with or without warning) causing or threatening death or injury, damage to property or the environment or disruption to the community which, because of the scale of its effects, cannot be dealt with by the emergency services and local authority as part of their day-to-day activities.

Major emergencies or incidents may fall within one or more of the following categories:

- Severe weather conditions/flooding
- Major structural collapse
- Major fire or explosion
- Threats to public health
- War or terrorism
- Major public disorder or criminal activity

In addition to regular incidents SOP, in the context of major emergency there are additional SOP to take into account.

- Automatic proposal of action plans based on the type and magnitude of the emergency.
 - Within the action plan:
 - Automatically creation of incidents to recognize the situation in the emergency from the health, emergency and security aspects. Estimating measures such as number of injured, area affected by fire or floods, possible affected populations.
 - Automatically creation of one or several new radio groups for the emergency, in order to separate radio conversations from regular incidents and join operative resources from different agencies in the same radio channels.
 - List of actions to be carried out depending on the type and severity of the emergency. This list should be constantly updated depending on the emergency situation.

TOOLS

It could be interesting to use a business rules engine in order to centralize and make configurable the business logic that triggers Standard Operational Procedures. A business rules management system allows to separate business logic from applications and a centralized management that can be perform by business experts and not by technical staff. Business logic can be very changeable, the rules management system is perfect, since it allows changes to be made in a really agile way through: the creation of new rules, their modification, or rule flows. See Figure 81 for details of the software interface.

DROOLS

Drools is an open source business rules management system developed by JBoss, quite mature and with excellent documentation. Its main characteristics are:

- Rules engine: based on the Rete algorithm that allows the rules to be executed very efficiently, JBoss call it "Drools Expert."
- DRL language: which allows the creation of rules in a simple way. It also allows the creation of rules in specific language using DSL. It allows the treatment of spreadsheets.
- BRMS (Guvnor): allows centralized management of rules with a web interface.

The components of drools are listed below:

- Drools Engine: Drools Expert is the rule engine, and Drools Fusion performs Complex Event Processing (CEP). Contains JAR-type libraries.
- Business Central Workbench (KWB): It is a web application and repository for managing all jBPM software and assets. It consists of a WAR file to deploy on the application server.
- jBPM tools: They are Eclipse plugins that provide support for Drools, jBPM and Guvnor. Contains JAR-type libraries.
- KIE Execution Server (KES): It is a stand-alone execution server for executing rules using REST and JMS. It consists of a WAR file to deploy on the application server.

Figure 81 - Drools view. (131)

MACHINE LEARNING

Machine learning algorithms have various types depending upon the approaches, types of input data and sophisticated output results, and the type of the problem statement. The major methods are:

- Supervised learning
- Unsupervised learning
- Semi-supervised learning
- Reinforcement learning
- Self-learning
- Feature learning
- Robot learning
- Decision tree learning

Decision-making is involved in reinforcement, self, and decision tree learning approach. Decision tree learning operates on a predictive model. It starts with observation and concludes on a specific decision or target value. Decision trees used data visualization and represented decisions in decision analysis. Decision making is an integral part of everyday life. Decision making difficulty level fluctuates based upon various options given and their importance. But now technological advancements are helping millions of users with intelligent decision-making systems.

Machine learning algorithms could be used to train models with data from previous emergency situations, in order to make recommendations depending on the type, severity and situation of the emergency. These recommendations will be constantly updated, helping to make decisions at any time during the emergency situation.

5.3.4. Decision making (decide)

The decide step, according to Boyd, is the "component in which actors choose among action possibilities created in the Orientation phase." Figure 82 presents a representation of the OODA loop.

Figure 82 - John Boyd's OODA loop. (132)

When we make a decision, we're simply putting our best estimate - our best "informed guess" - about which mental model will work forward. We must next test our hypothesis to see if it is right, which leads us to the following step, taking action.

Our unconscious decision-making process is made apparent with the OODA Loop. By making it clear, Boyd gave everyone from military generals and corporate executives to coaches and political campaigners an unrivalled strategic tool for better managing their own decision-making processes.

It also allows us to influence and manipulate our competitors' decision-making processes (133).

Once the orientation process occurs, as a result of the integration of data and the composition of reality, a decision is made that is understood to be the most suitable. This is the "decide" step of Boyd's LOOP, which will ultimately lead to action.

For decision making, the sharing of information from different sources is necessary. For this purpose, different techniques are used to condense and compress information, such as video or audio. On the other hand, due to the rise of social networks in recent years, obtaining relevant information from them has become a very viable option for this type of systems. Finally, the decision-making tools applied in this step of the loop are studied.

5.3.4.1. Encoding

Encoding is the process of converting the data or a given sequence of characters, symbols, alphabets, numbers, etc. into specific format for efficient transmission or storage. This data converted into a specified format for the secure transmission over a network. Encoding is the process of using various complex patterns to represent 1s and 0s of the digital signals on the transmission link. Many types of communications uses encoding for the relation connection, including computing, data communications, programming, digitalization and human communication. Encoding converts content format for the transmission or storage optimization.

We need to note that encoding and encryption is not the same thing and should not be confused, which encryption focus on hiding and securing data while encoding transforming data. We can

encrypt data without modifying the code or encode the data without deliberately concealing the content.

The foremost significance of encoding a signal/message is to reduce the transmission cost. The two basic characteristics of any communication system are bandwidth and power consumption. In order to improve the quality of transmission keeping the bandwidth and power requirements low and encoding the signal. Besides, reducing the bandwidth and power requirements, encoding also helps in providing robustness to the system. For a data/information to be appropriately transmitted on a network, it needs to be converted into the best and the most reliable way of transmission. For this reason, data is encoded in a way that is best understood by computer language.

For the transmission of information, it is necessary to maintain the same coding that allows all devices in the system to receive it. In addition, it is necessary to take into account other parameters such as the sending rate or length of the data when encoding them, as well as the type of data being sent, differing between sending a video and an audio.

A data packet to be transformed into the best and most reliable way of transmission before it can be properly sent across a network. As a result, data is encoded in a form that only computers can understand. There are multiple encoding techniques some of them are: non return to zero level, non return to zero, non return to zero inverted, bi-phase encoding and block encoding.

The encoding process in communication is required. The data in a message should be beneficial to the receiving process. The program object structure should be preserved while transmitting data from the sending process's address space to the receiving process's address space. However, in the case of a heterogeneous system, this is not possible since the transmitting and receiving procedures are carried out on computers with different architectures. It is also a difficult problem in homogenous systems for the following reasons:

When moving from one process address space to another, an absolute pointer value loses its significance. As a result software objects that employ the value of absolute pointer cannot be transferred in their original form and must be represented in some other manner.

The amount of storage taken up by different software objects varies. A message should generally comprise a variety of program objects, such as a variable-length character strings, large numbers, tiny integers, and so on, in order to be meaningful. For the message to be relevant to the receiver the receiver must be able to distinguish which program object is stored into the message buffer and also determine space use by each program object.

Because of these issues, encoding and decoding performed in the communication process. Message buffers are used to hold program objects after they have been converted to the proper stream format for the transmission. The name for this conversion step that occurs on the sender's side is encoding of message data. Before the received message can be used, it must be transformed back to the original program objects from the stream form on the receiver side. As a result, decoding refers to the receiver's reconstruction of program objects from message data.

VIDEO ENCODING

Video encoding is the process of converting raw video files to digital files so that they are not saved as individual images but as fluid videos. That process reduces the size of video files and

streams as well as converting them into different formats to make them more manageable as a different chunk.

There are two types of videos encoding live and file-based. Live video encoding is the process of compressing large, raw video and audio files so that they use less network bandwidth. When it comes to transporting uncompressed raw video, this can mean a huge amount of data to send over any connection. When working with video files, encoders are used to compress and reduce the size of video content so that it can take up less storage space and be easier to transfer from one part of a video workflow to another.

Why video encoding is important?

Video encoding is an important part of getting videos ready to the output source to be delivered to viewers and give them as high quality as it can be. In video streaming is crucial because the compressing of the raw video reduces bandwidth making it easier to transmit, while still maintaining a good quality of experience for end viewers

Digital encoding of video samples for transmission or storage requires the use of some form of compression techniques. This is due to the large number of bits needed to represent all the information contained in the video sequence.

Video encoders can be classified according to the average bit rate able to deliver, as presented in Table 35.

Bit rate encoders	Very low	Less than 64kbps
	Low	From 64kbps to 300 kbps
	Medium	Between 300 kbps and 1 mbps
	High	2 mbps or higher

Table 35 - Classification of video encoders based on bit rate.

The most common formats for video encoding are presented in Table 36.

Formats	H.263	Video coding for low bit rate communication
	H.263+	H.263 version 2
	H.263++	H.263 version 3
	MPEG-1	Thus, encoders such as MPEG-1 and MPEG-2 are more oriented to the encoding of high-rate streams (from 1.5 Mbps) for applications such as Video-CD and Video-CD, storage, TV digital satellite and DVD in the case of MPEG-2. Both offer high image quality at the cost of high bandwidth consumption.
	MPEG-2	
	MPEG-4	MPEG-4 developed by the Motion Pictures Experts Group (MPEG) which allows for low bit rates with an acceptable CPU consumption and error protection.
		Codification
Media multiplexing		

		Interactivity
		Virtual Reality
		Management of property rights management
		Recovery mechanisms in case of errors
		Content-based interactivity
		Random access capacity
		Objects manipulation in a video scene
		Object-based. Each scene is composed of several Video Objects (VOs) that are encoded individually.
	H.264	H.264 which corresponds to MPEG-4 part 10 of 2002 allowing very low bit rates but with higher CPU consumption and error protection
		Very low binary rates
		A fairly acceptable level of quality quite acceptable increasing CPU consumption
		Smaller block sizes
		Greater flexibility in block shapes
		Greater precision in the motion vectors
	Multiple frames of reference	
H.265	Same quality video as H.264 but the bit rate is quite lower.	

Table 36 - Most common formats for video encoding.

Some of the most common techniques for video encoding are presented in Table 37.

Formats	Radio channels 802.11	On the other hand, for C&C architectures to be used in environments with very adverse transmission channel, radio channels such as 802.11, WiMAX, mesh networks or satellite channels, all of them with high and/or unpredictable delays, high packet loss and error rates, etc.,
	WiMAX	
	Mesh networks	
	Satellite channels	

Table 37 - Common techniques for video encoding.

It is necessary to use **codecs** that provide error protection and recovery mechanisms and are well suited to these adverse channels. Codecs should be used that provide error protection and recovery mechanisms that are well suited to these adverse channels. These techniques are based on adding redundancy to the information flow to detect and correct errors. They can be found in source coding (encoder and/or decoder) or in channel coding.

In the first case, two approaches stand out:

- Techniques for robustness of the encoded video to errors, basically the use of synchronization words, intra frames and RVLC (Reversible Variable Length Coding) codes
- Error concealment techniques, located in the decoder that try to alleviate errors in the received information, for example by carrying out some kind of spatial and/or temporal interpolation with the correct data (135)

AUDIO ENCODING

Speech coding is an application of data compression of digital audio signals containing speech. Speech coding uses the estimation of specific speech parameters using audio signal processing techniques to model the speech signal, combined with generic data compression algorithms to represent the resulting modelled parameters in a compact bitstream.

Speech coding differs from other forms of audio coding in that speech is a simpler signal than most other audio signals, and much more statistical information is available about the properties of speech. As a result, some auditory information that is relevant in audio coding may be unnecessary in the context of speech coding. In speech coding, the most important criterion is the preservation of intelligibility and "sympathy" of speech, with a limited amount of transmitted data.

Some voice coding applications are mobile telephony and voice over IP (VoIP). The most widely used voice coding technique in mobile telephony is Linear Predictive Coding (LPC), while the most widely used in VoIP applications are LPC and Modified Discrete Cosine Transformation (MDCT) techniques.

Modified discrete cosine transform (MDCT), a type of discrete cosine transform (DCT) algorithm, was adapted into a speech coding algorithm called LD-MDCT, used for the AAC-LD format introduced in 1999. ² Since then, MDCT has been widely adopted in Voice over IP (VoIP) applications, such as the G.729.1 wideband audio codec introduced in 2006, ³ Apple's Facetime (using AAC-LD) introduced in 2010, ⁴ and the CELT codec introduced in 2011. ⁵

Opus is a free software speech coder. It combines both the MDCT and LPC audio compression algorithms. It is widely used for VoIP calls in WhatsApp. The PlayStation 4 video game console also uses the CELT/Opus codec for its PlayStation Network system party chat. Codec2 is another free software speech coder, which manages to achieve very good compression, as low as 700 bits.

Wideband audio coding

- Linear predictive coding (LPC)
 - AMR-WB for WCDMA networks
 - VMR-WB for CDMA2000 networks
 - Speex, IP-MR, SILK and Opus for voice-over-IP (VoIP) and videoconferencing
- Modified discrete cosine transform (MDCT)
 - AAC-LD, G.722.1, G.729.1, CELT and Opus for VoIP and videoconferencing
- Adaptive differential pulse-code modulation (ADPCM)
 - G.722 for VoIP

Narrowband audio coding

- LPC
 - FNBDT for military applications
 - SMV for CDMA networks
 - Full Rate, Half Rate, EFR and AMR for GSM networks
 - G.723.1, G.728, G.729, G.729.1 and iLBC for VoIP or videoconferencing
- ADPCM
 - G.726 for VoIP

Why audio encoding is important?

The audio quality for any streaming video is so important as much as the video quality. Audio encoding offers less storage space. Audio encoding offers faster data transferring over a network, removes redundancies from data, so the size of the files is a lot smaller. This results in a faster input even with bad internet connection. Also, another specification of audio encoding is the resources consumption which is too low. Finally audio encoding is adaptable, for example the AAC codec can use different frequency ranges with the help of joint encoding to achieve higher quality, a smaller file size, or both.

5.3.4.2. Social Media

“In an increasingly complex and rapidly changing operational environment, commanders, decision makers, and personnel rely on accurate, timely, and relevant information that can be stored and maintained securely and accessed quickly at headquarters and in the field. In today’s world, and in the future, our ability to exploit (find, manipulate, combine, purposely use and share) the huge stores of data and information will be a key contributor to mission success.

Overwhelmingly these initiatives rely on the machines and algorithms to sort through the mass quantities of information and do not specifically include power of peer production, social networks formed in most SM platforms, and the concept of the long tail to attack the problem of information overload.” (136)

Blockchain technology can evolve to give solution to the information overload problem. Big data on blockchain is beneficial since it is well structured, plentiful and compete, making it the perfect source for further analysis. Thinking of how big blockchain is and massive data lakes of blocks containing the complete history of every transaction all of which can be analysed.

Blockchain guarantees the ledger’s integrity, but not its accuracy. Big data and the associated analytical tools will be useful in that situation. By using blockchain technology to store big data, businesses could be able to save money and time. Massive volumes of data can be kept on a blockchain forever.

With a blockchain based big data solution, providers might exchange records with any interested industry without worrying about the risks associated with a network of different data silos. In this scenario data may be kept on a blockchain network.

The biggest advantage that blockchain technology offers to big data is probably the data security. Because the system is decentralized and cannot be modified without the agreement of all stakeholders, no one person has control over it. This makes the system more transparent overall and lowers the likelihood of fraud.

Big data can benefit from blockchain in part through improving data access. The blockchain may be expanded to include users from different corporate divisions, providing them with access to the data required for analysis. As a result, work is completed more quickly and data collection and analysis require less time.

By using blockchain in place of conventional storage methods, businesses may increase the quality of their data since it is comprehensive and well-organized. This enhances accuracy and encourages through analysis, producing rich and reliable business insights. When the data gathered by large enterprises is secure, reliable and accessible it will be simpler for firms to make decisions based on their insights.

Technology is revolutionizing with blockchain technology and big data to be a great combo.

SOCIAL MEDIA ON C2 SYSTEMS

C2 Concepts and SM

This subsection will discuss the connections between key C2 concepts and possible SM connections. Regardless of the implementation details (an internal vs open internet use of SM tools), there are many SM tools that could be used to enhance current C2 processes. The next tables identify the C2 concepts or principles and the corresponding SM concepts that apply.

ArcGIS – Public Information Map	
Introduction	This application is something that ArcGIS has developed over time to include live mapping in support of their Disaster Response Program website. The Public Information Map is available as a template that is able to download and configure (137).
Interface	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 83 - ArcGIS – Public information map (138)</i></p>

Table 38 - Tools to enhance current C2 processes - ArcGIS – Public Information Map

ArcGIS – GeoViewer	
Introduction	<p>GeoViewer, a web-based mapping app that visualizes the results of the geotagged social media analyses performed by HDMA. Its geospatial functions are easy to use and include the ability to display hot spot and cluster data layers; store multimedia images, including photos and videos; and map historic and real-time social media data.</p> <p>“The metadata collected by social media platforms includes quite a bit of information, such as the identity of the author, when the post occurred, a geotagged location of the post, the content of the post itself, number of reposts, and so on”</p> <p>While all that data is incredibly useful, it also brings up concerns about privacy.</p> <p>“Our research at HDMA is concerned about privacy issues, and we try to protect the users’ privacy as much as we can,” he said. “For example, our GeoViewer software includes geomasking techniques to randomize the actual geotagged locations of users within a 100-meter radius, even though this may slightly reduce the accuracy of our spatial analysis results.” (138)</p>
Interface	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 84 - ArcGIS - Geoviewer (138)</i></p>

Table 39 - Tools to enhance current C2 processes - ArcGIS – GeoViewer

ArcGIS – Social Media Widget	
Introduction	<p>Social Media is on a path to evolve to become another critical source of situational awareness just like weather. A Social Media Widget has been developed to be able to bring in Social Media into C&C applications, such as the Common Operational Picture Template. (138)</p>

ArcGIS – Social Media Widget	
Interface	<p>The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying an ArcGIS map titled "New Madrid Seismic Zone Earthquake - National Level EXERCISE". The map includes a "Layer List" on the left with checkboxes for "Airport States Assets", "Fire EMS Assets", "Military Assets", "Police Assets", "Search Rescue Assets", "Transportation Assets", "Incident Points", "Shelters", and "Exclusion Hot Zones". A "Social Media" widget is overlaid on the map, allowing users to search for tweets by keyword (e.g., "nie11") and location. A specific tweet is highlighted: "NYEM HLE11 (Aleta Morak) Just landed in Greenville, KY for our stop at Wendell".</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 85 - ArcGIS – Social Media Widget (138)</i></p>

Table 40 - Tools to enhance current C2 processes - ArcGIS – Social Media Widget

ArcGIS – Tweet Mapping Template	
Introduction	<p>As described in this previous ArcGIS Online blog, you can add Twitter to your ArcGIS.com map. Simply create your ArcGIS.com web map and then share using the Azure Twitter template. Here’s an example from the #EsriUC and the 5K Fun Run/Walk (138).</p>
Interface	<p>The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the "Twitter ArcGIS.com Template". The map shows a city area with numerous blue location pins representing tweets. A tweet overlay is visible: "Watching #esriuc 5km run finishers...good work. http://t.co/gSMMAC7". The interface includes a "Description" panel on the left and a "Share Map" button on the right.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 86 - ArcGIS – Tweet Mapping Template (138)</i></p>

Table 41 - Tools to enhance current C2 processes – ArcGIS – Tweet Mapping Template

5.3.4.3. *Decision making tools*

EMS in the EU already to a considerable extent nowadays use smartphones or tablets for support and documentation of their performance. However, these systems are generally more focused on individual attention and to a limited extent allow documentation in MCIs with a limited set of options for input and exchange of relevant information in this more critical context.

There are also in some cases management systems for tablets or laptops available in the command vehicles that have similarities with the systems in the control centres. However, in the same way that information is recorded on paper, almost all information has to be manually entered and managed in them, and decision support information is generally limited and presented in the form of tables or simple graphs.

Therefore, the literature points to the added value of filtering and sorting functions, the exchange of data with multiple users and the appropriate aggregation of data.

The essential components in a disaster management chain for EMS are triage and casualty evacuation. A review of the literature allows us to point out some lines of application of decision support tools for EMS first responders at the scene of an MCI:

RESCUE: Algorithms are developed from social network data collected during a disaster to better respond to victims' requests during a catastrophe. Using multi-agent reinforcement learning with social network data, this model can respond to dynamic requests and maximise performance in space and time with limited resources in large-scale areas for various conditions (139). In another example, in flood disasters, the driving routes of the rescue team must be adaptively adjusted. Based on a model to predict the distribution of possible requests on each road segment, a reinforcement learning method is used (140) (141).

TRIAGE: Through smart pens, smartphones, tablets, smartglasses, etc. connected to a decision support system, it reliably collects patient data and makes it easier for the first responder to triage patients as they go about their work (142; 143).

THERAPEUTIC DECISION SUPPORT and recording of medical information in the advanced medical post: In the treatment units in the scene user mobility is less necessary than in the chaotic phase and documentation is much more complex. Treatment is closer to routine missions, so documentation can be done with tablet systems in a routine way and consistent with known schemes (144) (145).

AMBULANCE MANAGEMENT AND EVACUATION of casualties: in a mass casualty situation, evacuation of severely injured patients to the appropriate health care facility is of critical importance. Casualty evacuation without effective coordination may lead to overcrowding at hospitals and result in an increasing number of casualties. Thus, guidance for rapid transportation is needed according to triage categories, needed/available ambulances, human resources, and destination hospital capabilities. The use of spatial decision support system SDSS in the prioritization of MCI evacuation decision making is potentially valuable in cases of mass casualty. The key to this model, Mass Casualty Patient Allocation Model, is the utilization of pre-calculated driving times from each hospital in the region to each point on the road network. The incorporation of real-time traffic and hospital capacity data would further improve this model (146; 147; 148).

SUMMA112 – Emergency medical services experience

Although many tools are available, many emergencies medical services do not use such applications in MCI cases, or are currently being implemented. SUMMA 112, for example, uses a very rudimentary decision support tool called "Crisis Management". This application basically allows at a very early stage of a disaster to decide and give advance warning to a hospital or a group of hospitals, depending on the affected area, the predominant type of pathology and the capacities of the destination hospitals. Once the decision has been made, the alert is sent to a terminal in each of the destination hospitals, where an alarm sounds and a message appears with the initial information provided by SUMMA 112. The hospital can respond with the number of beds available in each of the specialised areas.

5.3.5. Intervention (act)

5.3.5.1. Deployment platform

The Incident Command Post will execute the instructions of the Emergency Management Plan when it is activated. In any case, it will coordinate the actions of the material and human resources intervening on emergency place and will act as a liaison with the Plan Director through the Operational Coordination Centre, closer to the emergency location.

The physical infrastructure for the forward command post in multi-casualty incidents is a deployable platform with the objective of deploying the necessary infrastructure to manage the FR mission. The ecosystem of the forward command post platform is intended to cover the communication requirements between the wearables and the FRs. Figure 87 presents an example of a forward command post coordination truck. Table 42 presents a list of characteristics of a forward command post, while Table 43 indicates their main functions.

Figure 87 - Example of a forward command post coordination truck (149)

Incident Command Post	
ID	Characteristics
1	Safe location as close as possible to the emergency, but located outside the possible effects of the emergency.

Incident Command Post	
2	Located in the area where there is sufficient radio coverage to allow access to different telecommunication networks
3	Electrical sources accessibility.
4	Easy access and ample space for parking and reception of vehicles.
5	Members: The Head of the ICP. The designated commanders of each of the teams involved (intervention, security, sanitary and logistical). Representatives of those organisations or entities whose actions are decisive for the achievement of the objectives.

Table 42 - Incident command post characteristics.

Incident Command Post	
	Functions
1	Carry out a permanent evaluation of the emergency and transmission the Territorial Plan for Transboundary Emergencies.
2	Define the strategy of action to be taken in the emergency.
3	Propose the activation of ordinary and extraordinary resources.
4	Coordinate the interventions of the intervening means.
5	Define the planning zones, adapting them to the evolution of the emergency.
6	Communicate permanently the Territorial Plan for Transboundary Emergencies, through the Operational Coordination Center, all the incidents arising in the intervention against the emergency, and to all the Action Groups constituted, the decisions of the Territorial Plan for Transboundary Emergencies Management.
7	Propose the change of Situation in Emergency Phase.
8	Propose the deactivation of the Territorial Plan for Transboundary Emergencies.
9	Resources demobilization.
10	Evaluate the emergency effects and propose the Territorial Plan for Transboundary Emergencies Directorate, through the Operational Coordination Center, the end of the emergency.
11	Others assigned by the Territorial Plan for Transboundary Emergencies Directorate.

Table 43 - List of functions of an incident command post (150)

5.3.5.2. Localization Systems

Localization in wireless networks is the automated technique of locating a physical location using wireless communication. It can be used as a stand-alone application (for example, inventory tracking in a distribution center) or to support the network service (e.g., routing) (151).

Localization systems can have various classifications:

They can be classified as range based or range free, depending on the distance measurement technique used. The former use range-based measurements to determine absolute distance/angle, whereas the latter employs procedures that determine relative object position.

Techniques for localization can be characterized as centralized or dispersed. The centralized technique relies on sensor nodes transmitting data to a central server, which performs the computation to establish each node's location.

Another technique to assess location systems is to consider the type of coordinates they produce. Because it is aligned to popular coordinate systems used as commercial and military references, such as GPS, an absolute coordinate system has global coherence and is desired in

most cases. Relative positioning establishes positions that are relative to a system that is local to the network and can be arbitrarily defined while yet maintaining network coherence.

Distance measurement to anchors or beacons, position estimate, and position refining, which is an optional step, are the three processes in any localization system. The granularity and accuracy of location data are influenced by the techniques and technology used.

To summarize, building a positioning system for a certain context might be challenging when it is applied to other situations. Despite the abundance of existing location technologies, there is no single location technology that can be relied on to deliver accurate location information in all environments. There may not be a single best technology since "no one size fits all." However, each technique has its own set of advantages and disadvantages. (152)

GALILEO

Galileo is a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) developed by the European Union that provides navigation services: positioning and timing. The Galileo system consists of three segments. The first segment is the Space Segment. It consists of thirty satellites located in Medium Earth Orbit (MEO). The approximate altitude is 23,000.00km with a path around the Earth every fourteen hours. The second segment is the Terrain segment. It is made up of measuring stations, two control centres, stations for transmitting information to the satellites and tracking, telemetry and telecommand (TT&C) stations. In turn, it is divided into two sub-segments of ground control and mission control.

Finally, the service segment supports the provision of the following services:

- GNSS Service Centre (GSC)
- Geodetic Reference Service Provider (GRSP)
- Time Server Provider (TSP)
- Galileo Monitoring Security Centre (GSMC)
- Galileo Reference Centre (GRC)
- Competent PRS Authorities (CPAs)

GPS

The Global Positioning System (GPS) is a U.S.-owned utility that provides users with positioning, navigation, and timing (PNT) services. This system consists of **three segments**: the space segment, the control segment, and the user segment (see Figure 88 and Table 44).

GPS Control Segment

Figure 88 - Example of GPS control segment (153).

GNSS segments	<p>The GNSS space segment consists of a constellation of satellites transmitting radio signals to users. The United States is committed to maintaining the availability of at least 24 operational GPS satellites, 95% of the time. To ensure this commitment, the U.S. Space Force has been flying 31 operational GPS satellites for well over a decade.</p>
	<p>The GNSS control segment consists of a global network of ground facilities that track the GNSS satellites, monitor their transmissions, perform analyses, and send commands and data to the constellation. The current Operational Control Segment (OCS) of the US system GPS includes a master control station, an alternate master control station, 11 C&C antennas, and 16 monitoring sites. The locations of these facilities are shown in the map below.</p>
	<p>The user segment includes the equipment of the military personnel and civilians who receive GNSS signals. Military GNSS user equipment has been integrated into fighters, bombers, tankers, helicopters, ships, submarines, tanks, jeeps, and soldiers' equipment. In addition to basic navigation activities, military applications of GNSS include target designation, close air support, "smart" weapons, and rendezvous.</p>

Table 44 - List of GNSS segments (154) (155)

GPS Disadvantages

While GPS is very useful outdoors (even better if they are open spaces without too many mountains and/or tall buildings or trees). It is of no use **indoors** where there is no direct view with at least 3 or 4 satellites. There are recent techniques that rely on the signal levels of the underlying communications technology to determine the position of the various nodes within an indoor environment (see Table 45).

Disadvantages	<p>Direct visibility with satellites. <u>Indoor environments the system does not work and solutions have to be provided</u></p>
	<p><u>Accuracy</u> of the base system is not very good</p>
	<p><u>Interference</u> through electromagnetic countermeasure techniques</p>

Table 45 - Disadvantages of GPS (156)

DGPS

DGPS is based on the existence of stations with fixed position (e.g. located in cell phone stations) that send information to the system with conventional GPS receiver with respect to measurements from their own GPS receiver. The differential estimation allows, by means of techniques, to improve the accuracy of the mobile GPS. Its use is recommended for situations such as adverse weather conditions or scattered obstacles where the signal is not extremely high. Where the signal is not extremely degraded, in which case the use of AGPS techniques is recommended (157).

Figure 89 - Graphical representation of a DGPS (157).

AGPS

AGPS (Assisted Global Positioning System) is a system to improve the performance and accuracy of the GPS system when the satellite signal is not very degraded. The system is based on the use of specialized GPS receivers that perform very specific processing on the residual signal. Very specific processing on the residual signal that may be being received. The parts that are not received correctly and/or cannot be reconstructed with the processing are complemented with information received from stations that have reference GPS via channels such as GPRS (157) (see Figure 90).

Figure 90 - Graphical architecture of a GPS system (157)

5.3.5.3. Data synchronization in case of network failure

Through the use of message brokers, the exchange of messages between applications can be implemented, this exchange of messages would be in an asynchronous way and decoupled, in addition, applications that exchange messages could be implemented in different programming languages, the only requirement for the programming language is that there has a client that supports the protocol spoken by the broker.

Communication through brokers could be used as the only way to exchange messages between one or more applications, or it could even be considered as a failover strategy to store messages in case of loss of communication, to communicate them once communications are restored.

MESSAGE-ORIENTED MIDDLEWARE (MOM)

This is a software-based infrastructure that supports the interchange of messages in asynchronous way between systems. It allows module-be Communication through brokers could be used as the only way to exchange messages between one or more applications, or it could even be considered as a failover strategy to store messages in case of loss of communication, to communicate them once communications are restored. Sed applications to be distributed over a heterogeneous platform, reducing the complexity of multiple operating systems and communication networks (see Table 46).

Advantages	Interoperability
	Reliability
	Security
	Scalability
	Performance
Disadvantages	Adding an additional component, messaging broker
	The whole system is more complex
	More costly to maintain
	In a synchronous system, it may lead to poor performance, although it offers the possibility of grouping messages and providing a single pseudo-synchronous response.

Table 46 - Advantages and disadvantages of MOM

MESSAGE BROKER

It can be defined as a message-oriented middleware acting as a message transfer agent exchanging messages between different applications, these applications can have both producers and consumers, in this way bidirectional communication is achieved. Messages are elements that have been formally defined between the different communicating applications, in this way the involved applications can decode them. Brokers also can provide validation, transformation, and routing of messages.

In addition, brokers act as a mediator between the communications of the applications, minimizing the degree of knowledge between them. In this way, an effective decoupling is obtained.

For data exchange with third applications VALKYRIES proposes a model of message exchange through a message broker. It has the following advantages:

- If communications are cut off, the broker in the sender side retains the message (optionally, even if the machine shuts down)
- When communications are restored, consumers receive messages pending to process
- Message processing is done asynchronously, so the sending agency does not have to wait for the message to be processed

BROKER FEDERATION

Federation of brokers allows messages to be exchanged between two or several clusters or stand-alone installations. Messages sent by one of the clusters or stand-alone servers are replicated to the consumer clusters, in case of loss of communication the messages will remain in the producer broker until communications are re-established.

Most popular open-source message brokers like Active MQ, Rabbit MQ, Apache KAFKA (called mirror maker) or ZeroMQ supports federation.

The proposal scheme for VALKYRIES is based on broker federation, in order to ensure the transmission of dataset in case of a network disconnection. In the following image a RabbitMQ federation is proposed as message interchange between C&C applications:

Figure 91 - Broker federation.

5.3.6. Interoperability

Interoperability is the ability of diverse systems and organizations to work together. Related to a single-entry point, it is the ability of single-entry point to route queries for objects carrying unique identifiers (UIDs) to the responsible authoritative source for trusted verification function (TVF). Interoperability is also defined as the ability of systems, personnel, and equipment to provide and receive functionality, data, information, and/or services to and from other systems, personnel, and equipment, between both public and private agencies, departments, and other organizations, in a manner enabling them to operate effectively together (158).

Interoperability gives public safety personnel and first responders the ability to communicate across state and local agencies, on demand, and in real time. Interoperability is essential in order to reduce the risks to law enforcement and emergency services personnel, alert first responders to any immediate hazards, and support decision-making at an individual level or as a collective group.

5.3.6.1. Standards and Protocols

As one can easily guess from the wide range covered, there are many standards regarding interoperability and information exchange. Table 47 presents some of the most relevant standards concerning data interoperability and information exchange (159):

Geographical Information	<i>OGC (160) and ISO/TC 211 (161) family of standards</i>	<p>The scope of the joint collaboration of OGC and ISO/TC 211 is the standardization in the field of digital geographic information. Some relevant examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GML (162) (GML 3.2.1 = ISO 19136:2007): The Geography Markup Language (GML) is an XML grammar for expressing geographical features • WMS (163) (WMS 1.3 = ISO 19128): The Web Map Service Interface Standard (WMS) provides a simple HTTP interface for requesting geo-registered map images from one or more distributed geospatial databases. Data is provided as web service. • WFS (164) (WFS 2.0 = ISO 19142): The Web Feature Service (WFS) Interface Standard offers direct fine-grained access to geographic information at the feature and feature property level. Data is provided as web service.
	<i>CEN/TC 287 (165) geographic information standards</i>	<p>The scope of CEN/TC287 Geographic Information is standardization in the field of digital geographic information for Europe. Some relevant examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEN ISO/TS 19139:2009 defines Geographic MetaData XML (GMD) encoding, an XML Schema implementation derived from ISO 19115 • CEN/TR 15449: It is a report in 5 parts dealing with Spatial data infrastructures.
	<i>ShapeFiles (166) (ESRI)</i>	<p>Shapefiles is a widely used de-facto standard format for vector data. A single shapefile archive (zip) can contain multiple physical files and depending on the tools used there might be other accompanying files too.</p>
	<i>GeoPackage (167) (OGC)</i>	<p>GeoPackage is a universal file format for geodata; it is an open, standards-based, platform-independent, portable, self-describing, compact format for transferring geospatial information. The GeoPackage specification describes a set of conventions for storing data within an SQLite database.</p>

	<i>GeoTIFF</i> (168)	GeoTIFF is a public domain raster image format which provides geographical metadata. It is widely used for aerial/ satellite image, but as GeoTiff files tend to be very large, this format is rather used for transmitting small and limited images (using WMS for large images such as satellite or aerial images of a wider area).
	<i>INSPIRE Directive</i> (169)	The INSPIRE directive aims to create a European Union (EU) spatial data infrastructure (it uses CEN/TC 287, ISO/TC 211 and Open Geospatial Consortium standards and specifications)
	<i>GeoRSS Encoding Standard (OGC)</i> (170)	The scope of this standard is to develop a simple strategy for geo-enabling RSS feeds with location information. This standard facilitates and simplifies the encoding of locations and is interoperable with other formats as well, such as the OGC Geography Markup Language (GML).
	<i>SensorThings API Standard (OGC)</i> (171)	This standard provides a unified and open way for the interconnection between different devices (IoT) by managing observations and metadata from different sensors.
	<i>IndoorGML Standard (OGC)</i> (172)	This standard is mainly used for indoor navigation purposes complementing other similar standards related to the mapping of the interior of buildings e.g., CityGML, KML and others.
	<i>GeoTIFF SWG Standard (OGC)</i> (173)	This standard is used for geolocated images and to share coverage data across platforms and software environments. The standard is being used by a large number of members of the Open Geospatial Consortium.
	<i>Open Modelling Interface (OpenMI) Interface Standard (OGC)</i> (174)	This standard has been designed to facilitate interoperability between independent modelling components. Its scope is to enable the exchange of data, not only between process simulation models, but also between these models and other databases and visualization apps.

Table 47 - Standards and protocols for data synchronization (175)

Report Interoperability Standards

Reports	<i>ISO 2235 EMSI Standard</i>	This standard is developed by the Technical Committee 292 "Security and Resilience". The scope of this standard is to develop a message structure, which can facilitate data and information exchange between first responders in case of an emergency, thus called EMSI (Emergency Management Shared Information). It is built using the Extensible Markup Language (XML), which is widely used for storing and transmitting data. This standard can be used by C&C centres of first responders' organizations and facilitates the accomplishment of a common
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		operational picture between different organizations, thus enabling cross-sector and cross-border cooperation and response.
	<i>OASIS SitRep</i> (176)	This XML-based Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) Situation Reporting specification describes a set of standard reports and elements that can be used for data sharing among emergency information systems, and that provide incident information for situation awareness on which incident command can base decisions.
	<i>OASIS CAP</i> (177)	<p>The Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) provides an open, non-proprietary digital message format for all types of alerts and notifications. It does not address any particular application or telecommunications method. The CAP format is compatible with emerging techniques, such as Web services, as well as existing formats including the Specific Area Message Encoding (SAME) used for the United States" National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Weather Radio and the Emergency Alert System (EAS), while offering enhanced capabilities that include:</p> <p>Flexible geographic targeting using latitude/longitude shapes and other geospatial 10 representations in three dimensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multilingual and multi-audience messaging; • Phased and delayed effective times and expirations; • Enhanced message update and cancellation features; • Template support for framing complete and effective warning messages; • Compatible with digital signature capability; and, • Facility for digital images and audio. <p>Key benefits of CAP will include reduction of costs and operational complexity by eliminating the need for multiple custom software interfaces to the many warning sources and dissemination systems involved in all-hazard warning. The CAP message format can be converted to and from the "native" formats of all kinds of sensor and alerting technologies, forming a basis for a technology-independent national and international "warning internet."</p>

Table 48 - Report interoperability standards.

Multimedia	IMS (3GPP) (178)	The IP-Multimedia Subsystem (IMS) specification has become the core component within 3G, cable TV and next generation fixed telecoms networks. Session Initiation Protocol (SIP) was selected as the signalling mechanism for IMS, thereby allowing voice, text and multimedia services to traverse all connected networks. 3GPP works closely with experts in the IETF to ensure maximum re-usability of internet standards, preventing fragmentation of IMS standards. Specifically 3GPP TS 22.101 (179) and TS 23.167 (180) form the base for emergency service access from 3GPP services.
	Total Conversation	The Total Conversation (TC) standard was defined in ITU-T recommendation F.703 (181) as "an audio-visual conversation service providing bidirectional symmetric real-time transfer of motion video, text and voice between users in two or more locations. The ETSI TS 101 470 (182) specification by EMTEL describes conditions for using TC for ES and makes access of emergency services possible to people with disabilities. IMS as well as IETF SIP implementations are covered.
	WebRTC (W3C & IETF)	Web Based Real-Time Communications (WebRTC) is a standardization project to enable real-time media transport (Voice, Video and Data) between browsers, with current focus on mobile. Work was initiated by Google in 2010, and is now split between IETF (RTCWEB (183)) and W3C (WebRTC (184)); in late 2015, WebRTC1.0 is hoped to be final in IETF & W3C. However, no emergency service specifications are yet created for WebRTC, although it is generally seen as an important topic because the system may attract many users.

Table 49 - Multimedia standards (185)

5.3.6.2. Current Capabilities

Existing applications for C&C of emergency services are currently developed based on the agency needs. The functionalities and layers deployed within the emergency coordination centre GIS are not the same as the capabilities present in the respective emergency organizations such as firefighters, police, civil protection, sanitaries, etc. One of VALKYRIES' objectives is to standardize these technologies to link their needs and provide an orderly, clear and accurate response. The aim is locating the emergency vehicles deployed in disaster situations in adverse situations by trying to harmonize and standardize as much as possible these graphic potential tools.

Basically, we have identified that the cartography is distributed by layers. Each layer allows us to identify certain relevant information from each agency. The effort required to cross-reference

cross-border data does not exist today. There is no data gateway in a common system to visualize resources between agencies in different countries. Therefore, VALKYRIES will propose a conceptual standardization framework based on SIGRUN to be able to aggregate all these needs required by emergency services to facilitate the work in their respective tasks.

The most important features that have been identified in GIS systems are using several different types of cartographies in the application. Depending on the incident type each cartography will be run. From cadastral maps to cartographies based on orthophotos whose objective is to observe the environment of the disaster from a high level such as the type of vegetation on the terrain, natural environments, wooded areas, etc.

VALKYRIES does not intend to change the way of work for each C&C applications deployed on the Incident Command Post. Based on the needs of the first responders, the technologies that enhance the personnel adaptability, operational decision-making and course of action planning has been studied.

The **interoperability** of a Geographic Information System (GIS) is based on information sharing principle from one system to another between existing channels and protocols such as: WMS (Web Map Service), WMTS, WFS, etc. Those are internet-like protocols (i.e., https) for autonomous information sharing. The system is kept up to date without the need for human intervention. Interoperability focus on the ability to communicate one system with another. One problem is that both systems must have access to the network. If one of the two systems does not have network coverage, is not connected, the information cannot be accessed.

Share file it is a protocol or service for consulting georeferenced images of maps through a web browser that are generated by a map server from GIS databases. They are usually classified by thematic groups according to the user's interest. With the Geographic Information System application geoviewer, the user connects to the link of the WMS file to visualize from the tool an image of the information (Raster or Vector). It is possible to interact with the map according to the type of data exported to the geoviewer.

The harmonization of geographic information systems will consist of deciding since incident typification which set of files, such as WMS, are recommended to improve decision making by agency coordinators between countries. Firefighters in both countries will likely need to view very similar information. However, police and health care agencies will probably not need to view too many common items. The research of the consortium countries, so far, does not contemplate interoperable geographic data visualization systems between countries.

5.3.7. Analysis of T4.3 questionnaire

Moving to the third task of the work package, the key aspects solicited to first responder agencies are the following:

- Infrastructure of the Incident Command Post of the organization (e.g., rack, servers, equipment)
- Preparedness of the infrastructure to operate in heavy humidity conditions
- List of C&C communication technologies (e.g., TETRA, xG)
- Capabilities that must support a GIS
- Advantages of using GIS for increasing situational awareness
- Integration of social networks with GIS

- Digital format (vectorial, raster) used in your GIS
- Use of a tri-dimensional representation tool (3D GIS)
- Database systems supported by GIS
- Use of GIS based on open-source solutions.
- Localisation systems used by C&C
- Uses of location systems
- Use of vehicle or people location system for C&C
- Video compression techniques installed in the C&C application
- Audio compression techniques installed in the C&C application
- Use of modern encryption in the C&C application
- Mandatory information for data governance and exploitation
- Tools used in C&C application (e.g., big data analytics, advanced simulation environments)
- Back-up storage in the C&C system
- Database synchronisation between applications (e.g., between the incident command post and the coordination command post)
- Essential information to share with other agencies
- Technology used to link external sensoristic integration data
- Use of multiplatform C&C applications
- Ability of the C&C application to communicate data with the cloud
- Management of critical infrastructures on GIS
- Interconnection of C&C applications between agencies

After presenting the aspects asked to first responders, we subsequently present the most common answers for each one of the questions presented above.

	Most common answer in the Survey
Infrastructure of the Incident Command Post of the organization.	Command vehicle, rack, Internet, servers
Preparedness of the infrastructure to operate in heavy humidity conditions.	Yes
List of C&C communication technologies.	TETRA, mobile network, DMR, VHF radio
Capabilities that must support a GIS.	Geolocation, advanced mobile location, distance measurement, spatial analysis
Advantages of using GIS for increasing situational awareness.	Unified and real-time view
Integration of social networks with GIS.	No
Digital format (vectorial, raster) used in your GIS.	Vector and raster layers
Use of a tri-dimensional representation tool (3D GIS).	Yes, No
Database systems supported by GIS.	Private database
Use of GIS based on open-source solutions.	Yes, No

	Most common answer in the Survey
Localisation systems used by C&C.	GPS, Advanced Mobile Location, POSIC
Uses of location systems.	Caller location, personal car location, emergency vehicles tracking
Use of vehicle or people location system for C&C.	Yes, No
Video compression techniques installed in the C&C application.	H264, No
Audio compression techniques installed in the C&C application.	Yes, g729, g711
Use of modern encryption in the C&C application.	IPSec, N/A
Mandatory information for data governance and exploitation.	Security Ang transparency
Tools used in C&C application.	Big data analytics, None
Back-up storage in the C&C system.	Storage of all communications, None
Database synchronisation between applications.	Voice instruction, real-time synchronization, police online intranet network
Essential information to share with other agencies.	Dangerous zones, number of victims, information about responders, dangerous substances, relevant locations.
Technology used to link external sensoristic integration data.	None
Use of multiplatform C&C applications.	Yes, No
Ability of the C&C application to communicate data with the cloud.	No
Management of critical infrastructures on GIS.	N/A
Interconnection of C&C applications between agencies.	No

Table 50 - Results obtained for Task 4.3.

Attending to the answers provided by first responders, we first identify multiple ways to manage C&C procedures, both from procedural and technological perspectives. This highlights a clear need for harmonization between partners at both national and supranational levels.

Moreover, there is a lack of communication between C&C applications in both national and cross-border scenarios. In this sense, the management of an emergency is performed locally with the data is transmitted to centralised coordination posts without implementing automatic communication mechanisms between applications. This also indicates a lack of harmonisation that is essential for C&C procedures. There is an opportunity as well for first responders to include the use of GIS systems in their C&C posts and applications.

5.4. The digitalization on first aid actuations

5.4.1. Introduction

It is profitable to define the digitalization paradigm before exploring its capabilities and benefits. At its core, the digitalization (186) is the employ of digital technologies and information to

diverse industrial and social domains, apportioning new capabilities, unlike the digitization which is the process of encoding analogical information. The digitalization involves multiple processes, such as automation, simulations, digital education and training. It is up to every industry and organization to define a custom roadmap with the capabilities and processes to be applied in order to optimize its efforts and maximize the benefits of the digitalization.

In this context, the digitalization paradigm leads to the modelling, virtualization and simulations capabilities to be applied by the First Responders actuations, which seemingly will deeply impact the coordination during the actuations, the simulation of decisions and their consequent risk and impact analysis and the training of first responders.

5.4.2. Digitalization Capabilities to be applied by First Responders Teams

Digital transformation (187) is a continuous and complex process linked not only to technological factors, but also to social and economic factors. It involves rethinking all processes digitally in an integrated way, placing the patient at the centre of the transformation.

Some current challenges in the digitisation of emergencies are:

- Optimising the strategic management of resources, anticipating the distribution of demand
- Facilitating communication between the control centre, vehicles and first responders.
- Facilitate communication between the ambulance and the destination hospital
- Eliminate paper throughout the emergency process
- Enable access to patient clinical information
- Improve the processes of recording, analysing and sharing critical information in crisis response
- Facilitate analysis and decision-making processes in C&C
- Reduce on-site care and casualty transfer times, reducing costs in day-to-day operations and saving years of life in complex emergencies such as multiple-casualty accidents and disasters
- Facilitate traceability of victims in disaster response
- Increasing the safety of first responders in a disaster
- Improve the means of alerting and informing the population in crisis, taking advantage of the possibilities offered by social networks
- Take advantage of information sources available on the internet

5.4.3. Technological Scope

5.4.3.1. Modelling and simulation aggregation

Modelling and Simulation refers to the process of constructing and manipulating computer-based mathematical and algorithmic representations of real-world systems, with the purpose of conducting computer-based simulations to study, predict or optimize the behaviour of the system (188).

A computer model is a representation of a real-world event, system or phenomenon with complex mathematical equations and algorithms to recreate the behaviour of the system being modelled, whilst a simulation takes place when running the program that contains the model in order to assess the possible outcomes.

Using a model is beneficial as it allows, among many other things, to:

- Test a real-world system without having to create it
- Predict what might happen
- Train people to use it without putting them at risk
- Convey an in-depth investigation
- Generate what-if scenarios

Although there are several criteria that can be used to classify a computer model, some of the more common (189) are:

- Stochastic or deterministic (190). Stochastic models use random number generators to model chance or random events, and deterministic models have no randomness involved.
- Steady-state or dynamic (191). Steady-state models tend to be used in physical system simulations, using equations to define the relationships between the elements of the system, and aiming to find a state where the system is in equilibrium, while dynamic models model changes in a system in response to input signals
- Continuous or discrete (192). Continuous models perform numerical solutions of differential equations and uses the solution to change the state and output of the simulation, and a discrete model do not rely on equations, although it can be represented formally with an agent-based simulation, where the individual entities in the model are represented directly and possess an internal state and set of behaviours or rules that determine how the state is updated between time-steps
- Local or distributed (193). A simulation of a local model is run on the same machine, and a distributed one uses interconnected computers

The visualization of a running simulation used to consist in raw data, usually presented in matrices or other data structures that allowed end-users to see in real time the output of the simulation and how it was evolving. This information could be reflected on graphs to quickly perceive trends and behaviours.

Although useful, this kind of data output was not appropriate to every type of simulations and, as computer-generated-imagery (CGI) improved, more simulators began to embed this technology to offer a more photo-realistic representation of what was being modelled.

Extended Reality (XR) technologies are being used as well in the visualization of simulations, allowing the user to have a more in-depth experience of the model via Augmented Reality (AR) or Virtual Reality (VR).

5.4.3.2. Static Digitalization and BIM Modelling

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a collaborative working methodology for the creation and management of a construction project (194). Its objective is to centralise all the project information in a digital information model created by all its agents. Let's say that the life cycle of a BIM project starts with an idea and ends with the demolition - and, if possible, recycling - of the project into reality. This cycle can be divided into the 7 BIM dimensions (195):

- **1D or idea:** Parts of an idea with first estimates
- **2D** or sketch

- **3D Coordination:** The use of BIM methodology allows you to detect interferences between the models of the different specialities, allowing you to eliminate conflicts on the construction site
- **4D or site planning:** The use of BIM methodology also allows you to use the model to plan the work by adjusting the processes with the time variable. 4D modelling is a very useful visualisation and communication tool, which can give the project team a better understanding of project milestones and construction plans
- **5D o Measurement and budgeting:** The use of BIM methodology also allows you to use the model for cost control in each of the phases of the project, construction, operation and maintenance
- **6D o Energy certification:** The use of the BIM methodology also allows you to use the model for energy calculations, analysis and studies
- **7D o Asset management** (read about BIM use Model registration): Finally, the use of the methodology also allows you to dump the physical conditions of structural, architectural and MEP elements, as well as specific instructions for operations and maintenance, into the BIM model. And also, of course, to use it to manage the short- and long-term financial implications of any modifications to the asset, schedule those costs and establish its maintenance programme

5.4.3.3. Digital Twins

A Digital Twin is a digital representation of an object or process. These replicas are used to convey simulations before creating or implementing changes on their real counterparts, to collect data and predict how they will function.

The real object usually has sensors connected to it, sending the information to the Digital Twin and gathering this data of the product being modelled. This, alongside other technologies such as Internet-of-Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI) or Big Data enables the analysis and prediction of the real object via its Digital Twin.

First developed by NASA (196) in the 80s, Digital Twins have gained popularity and can now be found on a variety of cases, such as:

- Health Sciences
- Formation
- Emergency management
- Transport of hazardous substances
- Marketing
- Smart cities
- Urban planning and construction

Digital Twin Prototype (DTP)

The digital twin prototype is a type of digital twin that defines the prototypical physical artifact (197). This digital twin is created before the physical product, and it has all the information needed to create the physical version of an asset that clones the virtual one.

This is especially useful as it allows to implement a virtual artifact before having to physically create it and run tests over the model to ensure that it works as it is desired. If it does not function as it was supposed to, consecutive iterations will follow to enhance the performance

of the product, and only when everything works perfectly the real product will be created (see Figure 92).

Figure 92 - Digital Twin Prototype (DTP).

Although this doesn't fit every business, given that implementing a DTP is expensive, time consuming and it would be unwise to use it for simple products, DTPs are being used in a variety of applications, such as:

- Construction of buildings, bridges and drilling platforms
- Industrial environments
- Cars, jet turbines, airplanes
- Urban planning
- Designing of new medicines
- Power generation and transmission on the energy sector

Companies such as Porsche, BMW and Boeing are using DTP to test several products before creating the real object, leading to an improvement in first-time quality, saving development time and money.

Digital Twin Instance (DTI)

In contrast with the DTP, the digital twin instance is created from the DTP and exists when the physical product has been manufactured. This digital twin describes a specific physical product and it is used through its lifecycle to test different behaviours on different scenarios. It remains linked to an individual product throughout that products life (see Figure 93).

Figure 93 - DTI Scheme

A DTI allows to collect different types of data from that specific product to monitor its evolution and even take measures to ensure the correct functioning of that product or predict potential failures and help mitigate them.

This type of Digital Twins is widely used in aircrafts and aeronautics products, offering an in-real-time monitoring of the system and predicting future behaviours, and allowing the user to anticipate conditions that would lead the product to a fatal malfunction.

Digital Twin Aggregated (DTA)

The digital twin aggregate is a computing construct that has access to all digital twin instances, collecting data to determine the capabilities of the product, run prognostics and test operating parameters. Given that a group behaviour is not the sum of individual behaviour, a DTA might reveal unexpected insight of the products (see Figure 94).

Figure 94 - DTA Scheme.

Probably the best example of a DTA are those modelling smart cities, helping deliver dynamic models that show the real-life performance. This brings information about resource efficiency, cost savings, and an effective way of introducing sustainable practices to construction. In this instance, the DTA can also be used to simulate disaster planning and emergency responses during crises.

5.4.4. Reasoning of digitalization and decision making support

A decision support system (DSS) allows the digitization of data from different sources, in order to obtain representative metrics that help to make quality decisions based on them.

It has to be addressed that decision supporting mechanisms require different data and responses on

- Planning or Deploying Phase
- Reactions and decisions making during an incident

This type of systems must present the information in a graphical and statistical form, usually incorporating systems based on artificial intelligence. In this way, different errors can be avoided due to: 1) non-specialization in the field of study, 2) biasness, 3) reduced response time and 4) non-consideration of other alternatives. In this way, DSS can be divided into the following categories:

- **Model-driven DSS:** A model-driven DSS was based on simple quantitative models. It used limited data and emphasized manipulation of financial model
- **Data-driven DSS:** Data-driven DSS emphasized the access and manipulation of data tailored to specific tasks using general tools. It was able to support decision making in a range of situations
- **Communication-driven DSS:** uses communication and network technologies to facilitate decision making. The major difference between this and the previous classes of DSS was (198) that it supported collaboration and communication. It made use of a variety of tools including computer-based bulletin boards, audio and video conferencing

- **Document-driven DSS:** uses large document databases that stores documents, images, sounds, videos, and hypertext docs. It has a primary search engine tool for searching the data when required
- **Knowledge-driven DSS:** are human-computer systems that come with problem-solving expertise. These combine artificial intelligence with human cognitive capacities and can suggest user actions.
- **Web-based DSS:** Web-based DSS is considered the most sophisticated decision support system that extends its capabilities by using the world wide web and the internet

Decision support systems have gained enormous popularity in various fields including military, security, medical, manufacturing, engineering, and commerce (199). These can support decisions where accuracy is important. Furthermore, they provide access to relevant knowledge and support human cognitive deficits by integrating information in different forms and sources.

In a later version of this document, a more detailed description of needed decision supporting mechanisms will be defined based on the maturity of the results of other relevant WPs.

5.4.5. Implementing Digitalization

Digitalization has been identified as one of the significant developments that will impact society and industry in the near and long term. The “ability to adapt existing products or services into digital variations, and hence give advantages over real products” is another term for digitalization. Technological changes are currently transforming the structure and strategies of government agencies, with the goal of increasing efficiency and policy integration. Research on digital governance, on the other hand, has shown that implementing technology is not always a straightforward process, as it is frequently connected with conflict and negative feedback. ICTs differ in their impact on intra- and inter- organizational interdependencies that are necessary for them to function properly in their domain. The empirical evidence is utilized to investigate some implications regarding the tactics used to implement the programs and their transferability to other settings. Despite the fact that the necessity of digitalization is widely recognized, business frequently struggle to comprehend its potential impact and benefits. There are numerous roadblocks to digital transformation in practice (200).

Better efficiency, increased productivity, lower operating costs, improved customer experience, higher flexibility, improved staff morale, improved communication, increased transparency, improved competitive advantage, quicker and more effective decision-making are just a few of the benefits of digitalization.

Efficiency is described as the effective use of time, effort, and money in completing a task or achieving a goal. One of the most major benefits of digitization is that it cuts down on the amount of time it takes to accomplish a task, the amount of work required, and the expense of doing it correctly. When a business process is automated, one can count on consistent results. The corporation will achieve better transparency and fairness by automating procedures and related business rules.

Employees are freed from tiresome work activities when manual repetitive processes are automated, allowing them to focus on more complex and innovative efforts that will help the organization function more efficiently. Tasks can be completed faster and with fewer errors with business process automation tools. Employees can also make better use of their time at work thanks to process automation.

The most efficient and cost-effective utilization of core resources can be achieved through digitalization. The goal of every firm is to save time and, more crucially, money. Because manual tasks and processes are performed one at a time, they are inherently slower than automated activities and processes. When business procedures are performed manually, there is a far higher risk of wasting resources.

For long-term success, business operations must be transparent. Higher management will have more faith in how things are done if procedures and their status are digitally monitored. Critical metrics can be acquired and reported on to provide essential insights, depending on the process to be automated (finance, billing, collections, sales, and/or support). The visibility of an organization is boosted through well-documented processes and transparent workflow. Managers don't have to worry about employees forgetting what they're meant to do because everyone knows what they're supposed to do all of the time. Leaders may quickly discover bottlenecks and possibilities when they visualize processes.

When activities are automated, the chances of human error are greatly reduced. Humans are more prone to error than machines when it comes to doing jobs. Machines do not get tired and can operate continuously 24 hours a day. As a result, it has become commonplace to delegate to computers the activities we don't want to accomplish in order to focus on more difficult ones.

One of the most significant benefits of digitization is that it ensures that each activity is performed consistently, resulting in high-quality, trustworthy output. End users will receive the same level of help from the company if a customer care follow-up process is automated, for example. A corporation may begin designing higher-quality, more feature-rich goods with little or no increase in production time and costs because to the assurance of quality and consistency, as well as the time and efficiency savings.

Businesses must keep up with the fast-paced digital environment now more than ever. They must be able to react quickly to market changes, upheavals, and new opportunities. Organizations should be able to change directions quickly, and to do so, agile practices should be used across all departments. When business processes are automated, it allows for rapid modification and adaptation to changes.

Information management and digitalization go hand in hand; as data is processed, it becomes knowledge, and knowledge leads to better decisions.

One of the most important processes in emergency medicine is triage. The progressive increase in demand with material and human resources that are not increasing at the same rate, requires a more exhaustive selection of the patients who require the greatest effort and at the same time with the greatest probability of obtaining favourable results. This avoids both system collapse and futility.

Over the past two decades, tremendous research and innovation on digital health technologies has been done. Digitisation in patient triage, diagnosis, decision support, treatment and follow-up has been shown to significantly improve the care process. In Disaster Medicine, the shift from face-to-face triage to the use of digital aid tools such as artificial intelligence, machine learning technologies, wearable devices and tele-triage, are emerging to alleviate heavy patient traffic in those situations. The benefits of these technologies are numerous: improved process efficiency, increased patient safety, reduced time, improved traceability, and improved patient safety.

5.4.5.1. Human-centricity

Digital transformation is key to a competitive advantage in the modern business world. Is a human led, tech-enabled, customer-centric process of continuous learning. But what actually is Human-Centric Digital Transformation?

Human centric digitalization is an Evolution of any business into the digital space. Incorporating digital technologies into all kind of expertise and areas of any kind of business to leverage the value of their customers. Rearrangement of old structures and processes and changing how they work to become more agile, innovative and importantly, open to learning. In other words, is the share point between skills and capabilities, and the opportunity provided by digital Technology and tools to increase value for customers. It is a continuous process of learning.

Human centricity is about people and learning

These days knowledge is our greatest resource and our powerful weapon. Yet, digital transformation and technology in general is progressing faster than human capabilities. The tools and Technology at our disposal are becoming exponentially more powerful than humans' capabilities that results in a digital skills gap. In order to adapt to digital transformation process, we need to invest more time to research and learning. . You don't need to be ahead of the technology, you just need to be ahead of your business competitors to reap the benefits. Once you realise the people and deliberate are the foundation of digital transformation, then you are on the right path to success.

The importance of learning in business

Recent study of digital transformation with 4300 executives researched from MIT and Deloitte's shown that learning in business has noticeable impact in business ROI.

The research concluded that the most digitally transformed enterprises are distinguished by one featured: they've transformed the way individuals and organisations learn new capabilities and new skills. That means learning and researching every day is necessary for business growth. In other words, today's successful businesses are those who learn quickly, efficiently and continuously (201).

5.4.5.2. Digital Literacy

Digital literacy refers to the abilities required to live, to learn and work in a society where communication and information are increasingly provided through digital platforms such as the internet, social media and mobile devices. This century has seen a lot of development and progress, with media and communication being among the fastest-growing sectors. Theatre, the telegraph, and the newspaper entertained and enlightened us at the turn of the century. By the 1930s, movies had surpassed theatre as the most popular form of entertainment and telephones has surpassed telegraphs as the dominant mode of communication. In the 1950s, television took over cinema and later, newspapers. At the turn of the century, Web technologies are displacing all three, as our principal sources of information, entertainment, and logistics. The mindset of the consuming, enjoying, and learning public has changed in tandem with each of these advances in media and communication. As we rely more on the internet, there are many ways to take the advantage and the opportunities internet provides and adjust to new possibilities. Our own future will be determined by our ability to adapt to this kind of new technology features.

5.4.5.3. Resilience

Through investment in digital transformation, businesses can lay the foundation for long term resilience to future challenges.

Digitization strategies nowadays focus on increasing productivity and efficiency of a company. Companies should accelerate their digitalization strategies to increase resilience and optimize business processes at the same time.

From a resilience perspective, protecting critical infrastructure from cybersecurity threats will gain in importance as urban systems are becoming increasingly interconnected. In addition, sensitive data need to be safeguarded to prevent theft, unauthorized access or inappropriate use thereof. With the amount of data increasing exponentially, however, preserving individual privacy has become another major challenge in the era of digitalization.

5.4.6. Impacts

As previously said, digitalization is already having an impact on company settings, corporate working practices, emergency services and generally the society. Neglecting digitalization could result in a loss of market share in today's highly competitive marketplaces. Digitalization has the potential to change a whole operating environment and internal operations. Digitalization can also open up new opportunities, modify the responsibilities of value chain players, and put a stop to existing operations. Digitalization, for example may result in the creation of new intermediaries in the supply chain, rather than the removal of conventional intermediaries. This could be attributed to factors such as direct contract with customers and the rising use of mobile devices. As a result, the impact of digitalization and the aims of digitalization for an organization can be determined from three perspectives: 1) External opportunities, i.e., new business opportunities in existing company domains. 2) Internal efficiency, i.e., enhanced style of working using digital means and re-planning internal procedures. 3) Disruptive change; digitalization radically alters corporate responsibilities. These three digitalization impact perspectives can be given (200). See Figure 95 for a graphical representation of digitalisation impact.

Figure 95 - Digitalization impact (202)

5.4.6.1. Benefits for first aid actuations

The World Health Organisation published in 2018 a resolution on digital health (203), in which it recognises the potential of digital technologies to promote the Sustainable Development

Goals and, in particular, to support health systems in all countries in promoting health promotion and disease prevention, and by improving the accessibility, quality and affordability of health services affordability of health services.

Digitisation solves a number of existing problems during disaster relief. The first is the need to record information, both on the injured, the responders and the manoeuvres applied at any given moment. The possibility of recording this information not only by manual means allows more time to be devoted to interventions in the field. And secondly, the communication of these records to other bodies involved in disaster response, whether they are other intervention groups, commanders or destination hospitals. The application of machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques, analysing the data recorded by those involved, will also help to detect possible failures in the processes, with greater precision than human beings.

5.4.6.2. Benefits for first aid responders

The key benefit is increased productivity of first responders, reduced errors, and reduced costs. The digitisation of processes is able to impact very positively on the amount of work that first responders do. By freeing them from tedious processes that were previously done manually (data collection, communications, etc.), it allows more time to be spent on victim care and work directly related to disaster mitigation, improving the productivity and efficiency of first responders. Furthermore, the cognitive impacts (204) of these tedious processes is often identified as a potential reason of medical errors.

Medical errors have fatal consequences for a significant number of the patients treated. The digitisation of processes has also been shown to reduce the number of errors. For example, in communications, it is clear that as information is passed from one person to another, the content and quantity of the information deteriorates with each person in the chain.

Finally, the automation of administrative processes, the reduction of errors, the improvement in the decision-making process and the availability of information in real time have a positive impact on costs, both by reducing the need for human resources to carry out the same activities and by speeding up the tasks carried out during the disaster intervention.

5.4.7. Analysis of T4.4 questionnaire

Regarding task 4.4, the questionnaire asked for the following key aspects:

- Application used by first responders to represent emergencies in real time
- Usefulness of AI support on emergency situations (e.g., optimal evacuation routes, priority of evacuations)
- Common operational picture between all actors participating in the emergency
- Convenience of setting a virtual crisis room for management of the entire conflict, in addition to the forward command post
- Current literacy level of first responders is enough to face the digitalization of emergency actuations
- Use of wearables by first responders to track their actions or monitor their status during actuations
- Digital support for educational or training activities
- Usefulness of using virtual reality for educational and training purposes
- Convenience of using virtual reality for emergency actuations

- Usefulness of using virtual elements for drill purposes
- Other educational purpose to be identified
- Storage of training activities to evaluate the progress of first responders

Additionally, the most common answers for each of the previous aspects are presented below.

	Most common answer in the Survey
Application used by first responders to represent emergencies in real time.	Yes, None
Usefulness of AI support on emergency situations.	Yes
Common operational picture between all actors participating in the emergency.	Yes, No
Convenience of setting a virtual crisis room for management of the entire conflict, in addition to the forward command post.	Yes
Current literacy level of first responders is enough to face the digitalization of emergency actuations.	Yes, No
Use of wearables by first responders to track their actions or monitor their status during actuations.	Yes, No
Digital support for educational or training activities.	Yes, No
Usefulness of using virtual reality for educational and training purposes.	Yes
Convenience of using virtual reality for emergency actuations	Yes, No
Usefulness of using virtual elements for drill purposes.	Yes
Other educational purpose to be identified.	More specialization, No
Storage of training activities to evaluate the progress of first responders.	Yes, No

Table 51 - Results obtained for Task 4.4.

This analysis first concluded that first responders agree on the relevance and benefit of using AI and digitalization during emergency procedures, although some concerns were raised indicating that any decision-making process should be accepted by humans, not machines. However, they clearly highlight that a support system would be highly appreciated.

Moreover, they indicate that having a common operational picture and the definition of a virtual crisis room would be beneficial for easing the communication between partners intervening in the emergency, as well as making better decisions during the actuation.

Finally, formation is a key aspect for improving the assistance in these scenarios. Based on that, the inclusion of novel technologies for training, such as virtual reality, is widely agreed as important technologies to be considered.

5.5. Instrumentation and health support wearables devices

5.5.1. Introduction

The definition of wearables is smart electronic devices incorporated into clothing or worn on the body as implants or accessories that can act as an extension of the user's body or mind. Within this definition you can find numerous devices, from a wristband that allows you to measure biometric steps or heart rate, to a brain-computer interface (BCI) that obtains brainwaves and extracts different states of the users (205). Thanks to the large number of different devices that exist and the wide range of functionality they offer, there are many opportunities for these devices in this type of environment. However, there are certain functionalities that are prioritised over the rest. To classify these functionalities, three levels have been defined: minimum, medium, and optimum.

These functionalities allow the devices to adapt to the demands of the environment and prevent the system from crashing due to problems with coverage or similar. Therefore, the minimum functionalities must respond in any type of environment regardless of the adversities that exist. Some examples of these functionalities are patient identification, whereby means of a wristband or similar, you can identify patients and associate all the medical information related to them. Another minimal functionality is patient tracking, which allows a complete follow-up of the patient through each of the phases of patient evacuation. The second level of functionality is a medium level, within this level some features are applied that can help, but the scenario is not dependent on these. One of these features is automated triage using information obtained from biosensors. In this way, the devices would be able to identify what the patient's condition is in an automated way, although this results in certain battery, computing and connectivity needs for these devices. Finally, in an optimal situation, where devices have full computing and connectivity capabilities, unlimited functionalities can be added. Among these functionalities is continuous patient monitoring that would allow detection and alerting if patient stability changes, and with this information it would be possible to create intelligent models to maximise patients' chances of survival by optimising treatment. On the other hand, it opens possibilities such as the monitoring of first responders to study stress levels or other states that could negatively influence the decisions they make.

Once the different requirements are known, a search is made among the different technological solutions that currently exist to solve the different requirements. For this, the different devices are classified depending on their main characteristics, such as characteristics related to the location and connectivity they offer. There are also other points that must be considered, such as physical aspects like durability and resistance to external wear and tear. On the other hand, it is necessary to consider the security that these devices apply to the data, as their limited computation may cause them to dispense with certain security features necessary to process medical data that are a priori sensitive. Finally, it must be considered which biosensors these devices incorporate, as well as the certification required to deal with these types of signals.

5.5.2. Types of wearables

These devices are built around a central processing unit which will process and store the data in real time and will have mechanisms for outputting this information to which the people involved in the medical processes must be able to access for the functions of supervision, alert, and decision support. These output mechanisms may include auditory, visual, mechanical, or electronic and digital functions.

An issue to take into consideration is the protection of data generated through these wearable devices. To avoid the risk of manipulation and improper use of data, the general framework of the Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (206) requires users to know what data each application accesses. Manufacturers, due to the lack of 100% secure systems to protect data, rigorously follow “data protection by design and default”, with the intention of reducing the amount of data loss in cases of breach of GDPR and requires that the data processed are only those necessary for each specific purpose of the treatment.

Wearable devices are a constantly evolving technology that can be implemented to gather vital and critical information from people, in particular from victims and from First Responders. Wearables can be imprinted in the cloths, attached to the cloths or to the skin, or just carried (See Figure 96) (111).

- **Smartwatch:** A smartwatch is a wrist-worn technological device with functionalities that go beyond a watch and make it a multifunctional mobile device. The smartwatch functions can be synchronized with smartphones and tablets or independently (207).
- **Fitness Trackers:** This type of device is designed to monitor the user's physical activity parameters. The number of functions is reduced concerning the smartwatch, resulting in a longer operation autonomy (e.g., several weeks) (208).
- **Hearables:** These devices are similar to headphones, however, they incorporate some functionality that allows to give voice commands and get a result through it. They may also include monitoring of vitals, such as heart rate and physical activity (209).
- **Smart Clothing:** Smart garments are intended to monitor specific parameters related to the wearer, such as Galvanic Skin Response (GSR), respiratory rate, heart rate, or other environments params such as contaminations in the air. In this way, it is possible to study the current state of the wearer, such as stress (210).
- **Head-Mounted Displays:** This type of device has been used mainly to obtain a sense of immersion by the user for virtual reality applications. There are two main types of HMDs, monocular and binocular. Monocular head-mounted displays have a display in front of one eye. As for binocular HMDs, they have a presentation with a lens in front of each eye (211).
- **Glasses:** Smart glasses are devices that allow information to be displayed visually through the lenses, using them as floating screens. In addition, most of these glasses allow recording of what the user is seeing and send it to the cloud for processing (212)
- **Wearable camera:** This type of camera is specially designed to be easily transportable (attached to a helmet, vest, or similar) and have sufficient connectivity to transfer the data obtained to other devices (213).
- **Body sensors:** These sensors are usually attached to the skin to monitor vital signs, such as body temperature, heart-rate (incl. variability), blood oxygenation, blood pressure, blood sugar levels, electrocardiogram (ECG) or electroencephalography (EEG). These intelligent devices allow information to be transmitted to external elements to be processed (214).
- **Implantable Wearables:** Implantable wearables are appliances inside the body that transfer data to smartphones, computers, or devices. Medicine is the primary driver sphere for implantable wearables. Smart monitoring and healing chips track blood-sugar levels for people with diabetes. Cyber-pills are equipped with a microprocessor that directly contacts the doctor's smartphone application. In other words, implantable,

wearable devices simplify and speed up monitoring of the patient's state and accelerate the treatment process due to real-time tracking. Implanted RFID chips let track the location of people. Smart tattoos with the technology of Near Field Communication can interact with devices located at a small distance. A tattoo on the finger can unlock doors or enter codes by bringing the finger closer to the surface (215).

- **Localization Trackers:** Location trackers, or GNSS trackers, transmit the wearer's location to the synchronized device. They specifically have a small size, while other standard devices, such as some fitness trackers, are too bulky (216).
- **NFC ID wearables:** Such devices provide access to secured data bases through the available 4G/5G communication channels of a smartphone or a tablet.

Figure 96 - European Respiratory Society (111)

These wearables devices can collect many different types of data, being the most common (See Figure 97):

- **Health data:** body temperature; heart bit rate; blood oxygen levels; Blood pressure.
- **Person Location (if GNSS available):** GNSS/Galileo + coms for geographic coordinated, moving pace and direction; RFID for identification and tracking of personnel and victims inside the disaster area to map where they are, what they are doing, where they have searched etc. This information combined with updated maps at command centre can assist first aid responders in search in evacuation of causalities personnel.
- **Context data:** bodycams for live stream of pictures/ videos, other imagery sensors; chemical detectors, to build common operational picture at CC level.
- **Exchange data:** Padlets / mobile phones to exchange data, information, orders etc.
- **NFC wearables** that can be initiated in the triage phase and follow the victim throughout its handling. A good example would be that of NFC/RFID-equipped wristbands for tagging survivors, or victims, based on the use case. This technique can utilize said wristbands as gateways to information or other assets, once the chip inside a given wristband is activated. For example, a survivor or a victim that wears such a wristband, can be identified easily by using any type of mobile device, providing significant information as they are requested.

Figure 97 – European Respiratory Society (111)

Furthermore, one of the main objectives of wearable technology in the event of disasters is to first achieve response mechanisms such as the search and rescue of those affected and ending with the medical assistance of those affected, diagnosing and treating injuries or illnesses.

5.5.2.1. Value Chain

Wearable healthcare technology ranges in complexity: from simple smartwatches that monitor heart rate, to newer, more sophisticated ones like sensors in the form of skin patches. The purpose of the application that collects and processes the data will determine what type of sensors should be used: sensitive to light, vibration, sounds, even certain chemicals. Mechanical components must be precise, reliable, and strong, with minimal power consumption so as not to overcharge batteries (217) (See Figure 99).

The following diagram shows how wearable technologies fit into the IoT value chain. IoT is categorized into six different markets: home, automated, connected car, connected store, Industrial Internet, smart metering, and wearable technology. We will obviously focus on the latter. This value chain is further divided into four layers: the application layer, the connectivity layer, the data layer, and the device layer.

Figure 98 - Wearable Technology Within the IoT Value Chain (180)

A) Application Layer

The application layer is the seventh layer in Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) and is the one that is in direct interaction with the user. It's the layer that is very attractive for companies focused on services and is becoming a very profitable segment in wearable devices.

There are two types: applications designed for a single purpose, and platforms that are ready-to-use environments offering services to execute applications.

In the field of health control, applications focus on activity monitoring, disease monitoring, and support for treatment and for carers and clinical staff.

The number of digital health applications available in the market has increased significantly over the past three years. For example, in the UK, the National Health Service (NHS) currently hosts a Beta site Digital Apps Library, where it lists its 70+ "NHS approved" medical apps across

therapeutic areas from COPD to dementia (NHS, 2018). As more apps are developed, in turn, wearables can perform more functions, driving increased demand (217).

There are 3 main categories:

- Activity Tracking: monitor steps, sleep patterns, heart-rate and calorie intake
- Health Monitoring: supports medical diagnosis of people's health conditions: electrocardiograms, glucose control, etc.
- Therapeutic Wearable Medical Device: real-time monitoring of patient metrics related to their diseases. Apps often connect to individual monitoring sensors on patients for remote control.

B) Connectivity Layer

Until recently, most devices relied on a Smartphone for real-time communication, but today, wearable devices have become increasingly autonomous, attributed to advances in wireless communications technologies:

- BLE: Bluetooth Low Energy. Its consumption is much lower than traditional Bluetooth whose consumption is very high.
- RFID: Radio-Frequency Identification.
- NFC: Near Field Communication. Use lower power consumption.
- WiFi / WLAN: Wireless Fidelity / Wireless Local Area Network.
- ISIM band: 915 Mhz.

For those devices that do not need a real-time data stream, USB and Ethernet are used to connect to Laptops or SmartPhones.

C) Data Layer

It is the layer that describes where the storage and computation are located. This data storage is usually done in encrypted databases, previously processed by applications, which can use machine learning software to analyse this data.

D) Device Layer

According to the scheme above, it is divided into the following categories:

- Hardware communication: allows connectivity according to the technology you enable. The connectivity layer was discussed in the previous point.
- Batteries
- Microprocessor
- Sensors and microcontrollers. There are many types: gyroscope, accelerometers, temperature, proximity, humidity... In the next point these products are broken down by classifying them.

5.5.3. How to apply wearables in emergency scenario

Wearable devices are becoming increasingly popular among people. Through "smart" devices, it is possible to count how many steps we take in a day, how we sleep, our sports performance, and even how much we must drink. In addition, it is possible to obtain bio-signal data such as ECG or SpO2. All this information can be precious in an MCI (218). In a situation whereby definition, we have a disproportion between requests for help and available resources, any opportunity to automate specific actions and reduce the need for verbal communication becomes vital. The management of an MCI is necessarily centred on a small number of key

figures who must receive essential information in real-time to coordinate the resources belonging to their subsystem. This often creates "bottlenecks" that can delay, or even block, decision-making. Several wearables application functionalities in the emergency and disaster environment are described below.

5.5.3.1. Smartwatches

Smartwatches are probably the most popular of the devices. They possess the ability to capture multiple data ranging from location (either directly or via smartphone), movement, ECG, and SpO2. In addition to this they possess a display that can relay information to first responders and, most interestingly, they are configurable via software in potentially endless ways. These are the most interesting features for use in MCI:

Communication

The ability to transmit short text messages avoids the need for voice communication. This can provide information regarding the location of the event being deployed, a map of NO-GO zones, alert messages for different sectors or for different actors. In addition, if microphone and speaker are available, the smartwatch allows hand-free voice communication both locally and to the C&C structure. Since some smartphones are equipped with a camera, first responders can provide the C2 facility with first-hand information related to what they're seeing, what is essential during the assessment phase. Another interesting feature relates to second-level triage, in which a FR without health expertise can enlist the help of a physician/nurse practitioner who can remotely guide him or her through a medical assessment to define the victim's severity code (219).

Tracking First Responders

The ability to locate those working in an MCI setting is essential. First, it provides management information needed to know how many operators and of what type are present in the work area. This, combined with the ability to detect their location, allows resources to be dynamically placed where they are most needed. Secondly it signals those who, in case of aftershock, were unable to get away (220).

Patient's vital sign monitoring

Being able to detect parameters such as heart rate, skin temperature, and O2 saturation would be an advantage both in secondary triage and in monitoring patients waiting to be transported to the hospital. In the former case, it would increase the speed of execution of the process, while in the latter it would allow fewer healthcare personnel to be employed for surveillance. Continuous detection also would allow specific alarms to be set for specific parameters to alert operators by providing an indication of what the problem might be (221).

Detecting and locating trapped victims

Even considering the technical difficulties related to receiving a signal from a device placed under piles of rubble, the ability to accurately locate a buried victim would be very useful. All the more so if the victim were instead missing in the affected area or unable to walk but in an open environment. In these situations, the time factor plays a key role for the patient's survival and in relation to the number of resources used for extensive research (222).

Mobilization of first responders

The shortage of human resources, especially in the early stages of MCI, is a potentially critical problem. In adequately trained populations, the use of smartwatch activation message could

speed up the recruitment process (223). Figure 99 shows the best devices of recent years according to Globaldata:

Company Product	Function	Feature	Regulatory Clearance
AliveCor KardiaBand/Watch	ECG-monitoring equipment watch	KardiaBand with six-lead ECG to detect abnormal heart rhythm and AFib consistent with existing KardiaMobile products and wearable device	2019 US FDA 510(k); EU CE Marking
AppleWatch	Fitness and activity-tracking watch with ECG monitoring	Electrical heart sensor detects abnormal heart rhythm and AFib, along with fitness tracking, fall detection, and SOS	2018 US FDA 510(k); de novo (DEN180044)
Empatica Embrace 2	Wireless wrist watch for epilepsy management	Monitors physiological stress, arousal, sleep and activity; electrodermal response reaches a pre-set level (abnormal) alerts user/caregiver	2018 US FDA 510(k) (K172935); 2017 EU CE Marking
Garmin	Fitness and activity-tracking watch	Tracks and shares distance, pace, heart rate, and calories data	No
KinesiaU	Diagnosis of Parkinson's disease, tremor detection	Sensor measurement of tremor, slowness, and dyskinesia for movement disorders; tracks symptoms in real-time, in response to therapy and activities	2019 US FDA 510(k)
My SugarBEAT Watch by Nemauro	Continuous blood glucose monitor watch – diabetes	Sensor with daily disposable adhesive patch draws in glucose from the interstitial fluid and measures it at five-minute intervals; sends data to an application for analysis for diabetics, athletes, and intensive care	2016 EU CE Marking
Omron Heartguide	Clinically accurate blood pressure monitor and ECG – intended to prevent stroke and heart attack	Oscillometric blood pressure monitor provides clinically accurate heart data with a mobile app and Amazon Alexa Skill; blood monitors blood pressure, fitness and activity, and sleep patterns	2019 US FDA 510(k)
OnePulse Smartwatch	Health Monitor Watch	Monitors heart rate, activity, sleep patterns, and location with real-time alerts, medication reminders, and auto prescription refills; connects with EHR platforms	US FDA 510(k)
PKvitality	CGM Watch for Diabetes	Micro-points and biosensors detect glucose levels, track steps taken, distance, and calories	EU ETA 2022
Samsung	CardioBand ECG	Displays ECG rhythms and detects arrhythmias. Used for cardiac rhythm discrimination between normal/AFib/abnormal	2018 US FDA 510(k)
SmartMonitor	Watch Detects Repetitive Shaking Motion for Seizures	Monitors the wearer and detects repetitive shaking motions similar to those caused by seizures, alerting user and caregiver when necessary; detects heart rate, location, and activity	No
Study Watch by Verily Life Sciences	Wireless Monitor for Pulse, Heart Rate, Electrocardiogram (ECG) and Skin Temperature	Monitors pulse, heart rate, ECG, and skin temperature; tracks external changes the patient's body such as noise levels and light exposure, and provides a real-time data about a patient's activity and vital signs.	2019 US FDA 510(k) (K182456)
Viatom Checkme O2	Wireless Wrist Pulse Oximeter	Tracks and monitors heart rate, QRS duration, ST segment, and rhythm analysis; ECG SpO2, pulse oximeter, activity tracker, thermometer, and a sleep monitoring device	No
Withings	Fitness and Activity Tracking Watch with ECG Sensor	Heart rate and activity tracking with sensor measuring ECG for AFib	No
Xiaomi	Huami Amazfit Health Band with Heart Rate Monitor	Provides movement tracking and fitness analysis; screens heart rhythm and sends an alert if an arrhythmia including AFib is detected	US FDA ETA 2019

Figure 99 - Top Smartwatches. (217)

5.5.3.2. Fitness Trackers

For this type of device are valid the considerations expressed above regarding the functions of tracking first responders, monitoring vital parameters, locating victims, and, if the fitness tracker is equipped with a display, also transmitting text messages. The advantage in this case could be identified in the device's spread, its battery life, and smaller size compared to a smartwatch (224). Figure 100 shows the best devices of recent years according to Globaldata:

Company Product	Function	Feature	Regulatory Guidance
AliveCor KardiaBand/Mobile	AI Headphones	Records, stores, and transfers single channel ECG rhythms wirelessly through the AliveECG application.	2015-2017 FDA 510(k)
Brain Sentinel	Seizure Detection	Detects the onset of generalized tonic-clonic seizures and provides a warning signal to alert caregivers that a seizure is occurring; placed on the biceps to measure muscle activity through the skin.	2017 US FDA de novo
Everist Health AngioDefender	Diagnosis of CVD	Assesses FMD (Flow Mediated Dilatation) by measuring changes in the brachial artery in response to a temporary occlusion of the artery; measures arteries; ability to widen by using a non-invasive, non-imaging technique based on analysis of pulse waves before and after an increase in blood flow.	Global
FitBit	Fitness Tracking	Tracks activity, heart rate, exercise, and sleep stages every day	Global: US FDA 510(k); EU CE Marking
iHealth	Wireless Blood Pressure Monitor	Blood pressure and pulse measurement using portable cuff with intelligent display to provide assistance on optimal arm position for precise results, connects with app for smartphones.	Canada MDL; US FDA 510(K); Europe CE Marking
Misfit	Patient Monitoring	Tracks steps and distances swum or cycled.	2012 EU FDA Class II
MOCACARE MOCACuff	Wireless Blood Pressure Monitor	Wearable cuff corresponds with the AHA blood pressure categories to monitor changes in blood pressure, alerts on device's interface; synching with smartphone; MOCAheart for heart rate, bloody oxygen, and blood velocity.	No
PAI Connect application	Measures PAI Score: Fitness Tracking	Personal Activity intelligence (PAI) software provides a tracking metric based on heart rate data to manage health and prescribes exercise for optimal health	No
Spire Health Tag	Sleep Monitoring	Monitors the stress levels, sleep, heart rate, and breathing pattern; can be placed on clothes, is hypoallergenic and water-resistant.	EU CE Marking
Wavelet	Biostrap Wristband (shoe-pod and chest strap HRM)	Provides biometric insights using clinical-quality pulse oximeter. Heart rate, respiratory rate and in-depth sleep tracking synched to phone using cloud-based algorithms to analyze data.	No

Figure 100 - Top Fitness Trackers (217)

5.5.3.3. Hearables

This type of device has interesting features in relation to the ability to monitor the vital parameters of first responders and victims (225). They are lightweight, easy to wear and handle, minimally invasive, and discrete to favour long-term monitoring. Through the ear canal, heart rate, temperature and SpO2 can be measured with remarkable accuracy. In addition, the protected position is minimally affected by external weathering. Based on these data possible alterations in the vital parameters could be intercepted early (226). Figure 101 shows the best devices of recent years according to Globaldata:

Company	Function	Features	Regulatory Clearance
Bose SoundSport Pulse	In-ear Activity Tracker	Heart rate monitoring	N/A
Cosinuss One	In-ear Activity Tracker	Body temperature and heart rate monitoring	N/A
Halo Sport	Neuropriming Headphones	Neuropriming for athletes using electric currents to control movement	N/A
iRiver On	Heart Rate Monitoring Earbuds	Monitors heart rate, tracks distance traveled, and other biometrics	N/A
Jabra (GN Group)	Fitness Tracking	Waterproof, personalized audio coaching, race pace calculator and recovery advice	N/A
Kuaiwear Kuai	Multisport Biometric Headphones	Monitors heart rate, VO2 max, speed, distance, cadence, calories burned	N/A
LifeBeam	AI-powered fitness tracking	Heart rate sensor, connected Vi Trainer for immersive training experiences	N/A
Mymanu	Voice Translation Earbuds	Translates voice in real-time with advanced audio quality	N/A
Nuheara	Amplification Earbuds	Analyzes hearing to ID unique hearing profile, amplifies sound for optimum sound delivery	N/A
Vinci	Artificial Intelligence Headphones	Heart rate monitoring, 32 GB storage, noise-canceling	N/A

Figure 101 - Top Hearables devices (217)

5.5.3.4. Smart Clothing

This category of wearables has been developed in this last period mainly for the sports field as an aid to climbers. A number of sensors built into the fabric enable the detection of acceleration, skin temperature and heart rate data. This would make it possible to monitor the condition of first responders with a view to surveillance of their protection (227). This information is then sent to a processor (PC, tablet, smartphone) that will make it available to the C&C system. The main advantage is that the operator does not even have the perception of using external sensors. Figure 102 shown the best smart clothes in the market:

Company Product	Function	Feature	Regulatory Clearance
Bonbouton	Smart Insole-Diabetes	Monitors the skin's physiological signals to detect early signs of foot ulcers in diabetic patients.	US FDA 510k; ETA 2023
Hexoskin	Smart Clothing for Health Monitoring	ECG & heartbeat monitor, HRV (allowing stress monitoring, effort, load and fatigue assessments), QRS events, and heart rate recovery; breathing rate; activity.	No
LifeSense Group	Smartwear for urinary incontinence	Combination of smart textiles, wearable sensors, and tailored exercise programs.	No
NeoFect Rapael	Smart Glove for Rehabilitation	Sensor technology acts as variable resistor that changes as the glove is bent; 9-axis movement of 3 acceleration channels, 3 angular rate channels, and 3 magnetic field channels that measure movements for patients recovering from a stroke.	US 510(k); Europe CE Marking
NeuroMetrix Quell	Wearable Pain relief	Neurostimulation device for treating chronic pain is lightweight and can be worn during the day while active, and at night while sleeping; advanced sleep tracking.	Regulatory: 2016 CE Marking (93/42/EEC); US FDA 510(k)
Owlet Smart Sock	Pulse Oximetry for Infants	Tracks baby's oxygen and heart rate levels during sleep and wirelessly transmits data to a base station via Bluetooth.	US FDA 510(k)
Sensoria Smart Moore Balance Brace	Patient Activity	Detects patient adherence along with activity type, activity level, cadence, time on the ground, and gait speed; textile sensors, mobile application, and a cloud infrastructure for data analysis.	US FDA 510(k)
Siren Smart Sock	Monitoring - Diabetes	Tracks foot temperature and helps to find potential signs of diabetic foot ulcers; alerts users when inflammation is detected; fabric made with neurofabric and temperature sensors.	US FDA 510(k)

Figure 102 - Top Smart wear / clothing (179)

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5.5.3.5. Head-Mounted Displays

This class of devices is integrated within head protection systems, helmets essentially, worn by first responders during the conduct of rescue operations. They possess sensors and some kind of display placed in front of the eyes (228). They also have a tracking and communication system between operators and with the C&C centre. These smart helmets can improve vision in low light, integrate thermal imaging cameras and drone imaging, ensure hazard detection and also create a 2D map of the surrounding environment that can overlay an existing static datum with surveys taken in real time (229). This allows faster rescue when operating in confined and low-visibility environments. As a final function, the collection of vital parameters from first responders allows their condition to be monitored for protection purposes.

5.5.3.6. Glasses

Smart glasses, small computers that can project first person, point-of-view data to a remote viewer, can serve as an unobtrusive and simple technological conduit between first responders at the scene of an MCI and receiving operator in C&C center. In addition to the transmission of site images for assessment purposes an interesting function can be identified in the possibility of transmitting images to a doctor who can vicariously take over the activity of first responders.

Promising applications in the field of tele-medicine are the following. The possibility of **remote secondary triage** for the categorisation of victims (230). We have already mentioned this previously and it 'saves' personnel with medical expertise making it possible, for example, to use it simultaneously on several worksites. Another important aspect concerns the **recognition of victims who died** during an MCI (231). To date, for the presumptive identification of the deceased, it is often necessary, as part of post-recovery procedures, to acquire a photograph of the face of the body, upload it onto some kind of medium and then compare it with images of the missing or even show them to relatives. If it were possible, simply by looking at a face, to proceed to automatic recognition and perhaps immediately have a positive match with one of the missing, this would save time and above all avoid critical errors (232). A final possibility is the ability to transmit information on a larger scale to provide instructions to the population in the event of a disaster. This possibility, however, seems only applicable in certain realities and situations.

5.5.3.7. Wearable cameras

For this type of device, the reflections on image transmission set out above apply. The advantage of a bodycam could be identified in its wearability as part of rescue clothing, in being hand-free and, perhaps, in a discrete resistance to shocks and environmental conditions (233). One potential problem may be battery life when streaming. Due to their ease of use, these devices also find important use in the training of first responders

5.5.3.8. Body sensors

This type of wearables would basically allow the localisation and monitoring of the vital parameters of first responders by providing this information to the C&C centre (234). The aims are basically the localisation and protection of operators. The interesting development is their connection not only to GNSS or similar systems, but also to local networks (with different technologies) set up to cover worksites. This type of wearables would basically allow the localisation and monitoring of the vital parameters of first responders by providing this information to the C&C centre (234). The aims are basically the localisation and protection of operators. The interesting development is their connection not only to GNSS or similar systems, but also to local networks (with different technologies) set up to cover worksites.

5.5.3.9. Implantable Wearables

We believe that this technology has little scope for use in MCI. The functions of localising and monitoring the vital parameters of first responders could be performed by means of cyber-pills, but probably some of the above-mentioned solutions have greater communication range and accuracy (235). The same applies to the use on disaster victims. Figure 103 shows the best devices of recent years according to Globaldata.

Company Product	Function	Features	Regulatory Clearance
Biolinq	CGM	Intelligent Continuous Glucose Monitoring System is a needle free, wearable system intended for continuous glucose monitoring. It is designed to continuously monitor glucose levels by placing the sensor onto the skin. It is based on Micro-Array Technology.	FDA 510(k) ETA 2022
BioTelemetry	ePatch for CVD monitoring with ECG	Patch and sensor Technology incorporates detection capability into a lightweight, easy-to-use patch sensor. It adheres to the skin and is easily read out to a PC via a USB interface cable; the cardiac monitor is intended for cardiovascular monitoring.	E02018 FDA 510(k) (K171410); CE Mark
Eccrine Systems	Remote Patient Monitoring: Depression, CGM, Infectious Disease, Diabetes	Monitors sweat biomarkers; sends the data to a remote system through a transceiver. Sensors and arrays analyze sweat rate and other biomarkers. It features proprietary sensors, data processors, and management systems that can detect and manage sweat-sensor data including real-time data of glucose levels by absorbing sweat from a porous material.	FDA 510(k) ETA: 2023
Epicore Biosystems: Sweat Sensor	Remote Patient Monitoring: Sweat Analysis	Non-invasive, skin-like wearable fluidic sensor that is designed to measure prognostic biomarkers in real time, characterize skin hydration, and monitor patient response. It helps healthcare professionals to provide personalized treatment regimens for patients. It is capable of analyzing small droplets of sweat directly from the skin.	FDA 510(k) ETA 2024
Gentag	Diabetes Monitoring, Glucose Monitoring Patch	Pain-free diabetes monitoring patch is a smartphone-based diabetes patch intended for type II diabetes management. It is designed to facilitate pain-free measurement of glucose levels using tiny wireless battery-less glucose sensors placed on the skin.	FDA 510(k)
iRhythm	CGM and ECG	Water-resistant, single-use, wearable electrocardiogram patch intended for cardiovascular monitoring; data is sent to iRhythm's clinical app, which relies on algorithms to deliver results.	FDA 510(k); CE Marking
Kenzen	Health Monitoring	Sensors continuously monitor sweat, heart rate, and body temperature; sensing platform linked by custom algorithms via a companion mobile app that provides contextual insights about an individual's body when they are at work (under extreme conditions).	No
Medtronic Enlite Sensor	CGM Patch- diabetes	Guardia 2 Link transmitter uses Enlite glucose sensors to power the SmartGuard "suspend before low" feature within the MiniMed 640G insulin pump.	CE Mark
Nemaura	My SugarBEAT patch: Diabetes	Draws a small amount of selected molecules, such as glucose, into a patch placed on the skin for diabetes (glucose monitoring) and intensive care (glucose monitoring and oxygen depletion).	Approved
PKvitality	Diabetes Management, Glucose Monitoring	SkinTaste Technology patch equipped with K'apsul which contains biosensors to test glucose levels when it comes into contact with the skin. It inserts tiny micro-needles into the skin to probe interstitial fluid.	CE Mark ETA 2022
Theranica Nerivio Migra	Pain relief- migraine	Single non-invasive unit composed of ENS/NMES electrodes, a safe, low-powered battery, and a smart chip; Maximum Effectiveness (ME) mechanism collects and evaluates EMG (Electromyography) signals from the treated muscle, as a response to the stimulation; information is processed in a chip, providing guidelines to optimally adjust the location of the electrodes and/or the level of the stimulation intensity in order to maximize muscle stimulation efficiency to reduce migraine pain.	FDA de novo ETA 2019; CE Mark ETA 2021
Vista Solutions	Real-time Patient Monitoring	VitalPatch biosensor signal processing capability and a set of biometric software algorithms that enable it to read, monitor, and sense the patient's vital signs provided by VitalPatch on a continuous basis.	2018 FDA 510(k)
VivaLNK	Human Vitals Monitor: ECG and heart rate	eTechnology wireless, waterproof, multi-sensor, flexible, electronic circuit patch intended for stress and physical health monitoring; attached to chest with medical grade adhesives (72 hour use before recharging its battery); alerts Scout mobile app to notify when stress levels are high; body, sleep quality, tension and stress levels are measured by monitoring heart rate variability.	2019 FDA 510(k)

Figure 103 - Top skin patches (217)

5.5.3.10. Localization Trackers

The function of these devices is solely localisation (236). Given their small size and acceptable cost, one possible use could be to report the location of victims, certainly in the phase following triage and prior to evacuation, but also to track them during the subsequent phases of rescue. In this case, however, it would be necessary to associate the device with the patient's ID in a secure and permanent manner by devising a way in which the victim is not separated from the tracker (237). With the same limitations, this solution can also be used for first responders.

5.5.4. NFC/visual code ID wristbands

These low-tech devices basically consist of wristbands with a system that makes their identification unique. They are placed on MCI victims usually during sweeping triage and then, via a QR code/barcode or via RFID/NFC technology, associated with a patient via a smartphone. This information is integrated into an IT solution that allows victims to be counted in real time

and to record the evolution of the clinical condition and the medical procedures performed. Of all the solutions proposed so far it is the "poorest" of information but the most used in real MCIs.

5.5.5. Functionality depending on the scenario

In this section we aim to classify the most important functions among those defined in the previous paragraph within three levels of importance three levels: minimum, medium, and optimal. When we talk about the minimum, we refer to functionalities necessary for first responders, which should be possible to execute in any scenario. When talking about average functionality, we think of functionality that most of the time will be available and will help first responders, but if it is not available, it will not make the correct operation impossible. Finally, the optimal function is the one that would be executed in scenarios where we have full coverage and resources and would be covered once all the previous ones have been covered, adding an extra to the operations performed.

5.5.5.1. Minimum

- **Disaster victims ID:** Sweeping triage is the first action performed by first responders on victims. It is the act that allows us to take care of the patient from the health point of view. It is usually a process that globally quantifies the number of patients and their severity through a color code. If it were possible instead to immediately assign an ID to the victims, this would allow to trace their clinical evolution in real time and in the continuation of the rescue operations
- **First responders tracking:** the location of personnel engaged in rescue operations is essential. First of all, for a management reason as the command and control center must know moment by moment how many, what resources it has available and where they are located in order to be able to respond in a rapid manner to the changes that occur in the worksite but also, and not least, for a protection function of the first responders, since their stay in a NO-GO area in the event of an aftershock must trigger the rescue mechanism and medevac
- **First responders' communications:** the congestion of the local network due to the need to transmit information via voice communications creates bottlenecks that can slow down or even interrupt the coordinated progression of rescue operations. From this point of view, the possibility of acquiring data automatically from the various devices acquires a paradigmatic importance
- **Disaster victims tracking:** the main activity during an MCI, that is the rescue of victims, follows a progression that moves not only in successive phases, but also on a timeline. In an initial phase the victims will be mainly in the crash area, then they will be evacuated to the first treatment area and then to advanced medical treatment. Once stabilized, they will be assigned a destination and will be taken over by the transport system. It is important to know in real time where the various patients are in order to be able to adequately position our resources. Finally, if all patients could be located, we would have the certainty that no one is left behind

5.5.5.2. Medium

- **Patient' vital signs monitoring:** usually the detection of quantitative elements relating to the clinical condition of the patients is placed during the medical or secondary triage. The purpose of this operation is to define the priority of treatment and evacuation of patients. In most cases it must be carried out by an operator with the use of medical

devices, forcing us to deal with the scarcity of resources and the use of time. The ability to automatically acquire patient vital signs could speed up the process, allow remote transmission and allow virtually continuous monitoring of clinical conditions

- **Victims' triage support in disasters:** different emergency systems employ different professional figures. Often in MCI we see a relative abundance of rescuers with basic skills at the expense of personnel with more medical skills. The execution of the secondary triage is obviously left to the operators with greater expertise who must physically reach the patient. The ability to remotely transmit images and vital parameters to a healthcare professional would allow the same to perform triage on patients at different sites. This scenario also opens up interesting prospects for the development of AI systems which, properly trained, can, on the basis of the parameters detected, help healthcare professionals in the categorization of patients
- **First responders protection during crisis response:** the rescue activity carried out during an MCI presents by definition an inevitable share of risk. Normally, the assessment of external hazards is entrusted to the technical rescue personnel (firefighters, emergency technicians) who make use of their expertise and some measurement devices. If it were possible to automatically acquire information relating to hazards through wearables, continuous protection would be guaranteed to all operators, as well as extending the detection range and rapid sharing of information.
In addition to this, the detection of some vital parameters of the rescuers (for example temperature and heart rate) could allow us to trigger warning messages in situations in which we are all inclined not to listen to the messages that our body sends us
- **Detecting and locating trapped victims:** the time factor is of fundamental importance in some types of MCI, especially in the case of extreme environmental conditions or victims buried under the rubble. To date, research activities are carried out with the help of dogs, with intelligence activities, with phonographs or with the deployment of many people. In some cases (for example in the 2017 Rigopiano disaster) some attempts were made to triangulate the cell phones of buried people, but with no definitive results and long timescales. If it were possible to acquire the location data from wearables of buried victims, search and rescue operations could be concentrated with much more precision and, above all, speed

5.5.5.3. *Optimum*

- **Disaster fatality identification:** The recovery and identification of deceased victims is the last, in chronological order, task in the management of an MCI. Although definitive identification is a medico-legal act that is carried out by the authorities in charge in subsequent times, for the C&C structure it is of vital importance to be able to assign a presumptive identity to all the victims recovered to be sure that no one is yet to be rescued. The process is often complicated, involves different actors (technical rescue, medical rescue, and police) and takes a long time. If it were possible to acquire the image of the deceased person's face in real time and transmit it to an expert system capable of rapid recognition, it would be an important development
- **Telemedicine in disasters:** The remote transmission of images and vital signs of a patient can be of reasonable use especially in the final phase of the rescue when the hospital's doctors are awaiting the arrival of the injured person. This will allow them to better prepare the facility for the patient's priority clinical needs, as well as manage the flows

of incoming victims in a more orderly manner. Another opportunity is to be able to carry out a tele consultation to support the medical personnel on the site

- **First responders training.** the work that underlies managing an MCI is mostly preparation and planning and only a small part execution. This means that a high level of professional training is required of personnel dealing with disaster medicine. On the other hand, and fortunately, the relative reduced frequency of major events causes the experiential process to proceed slowly. From this point of view, the opportunity to use AR tools to train first responders in a controlled and safe environment appears very interesting

5.5.6. Landscape wearables

Once the possible applications of first responders for the different wearables are known, we will study the current technological solutions to meet these needs. For this purpose, three main characteristics that the devices must meet are defined for their comparison. The first of these needs is whether it is possible to track patients using the device under study. Thus, it will be necessary to review those devices that incorporate RFID, visual or sound signals, proximity sensors, GNSS signals, or any other feature used for user tracking. The second point to consider for these devices will be their connectivity and how they would fit into a multiple victim scenario. Following this methodology, we will study which technologies for wireless connections are incorporated into the different devices and if they work in the scenario, they are being considered. Finally, other aspects will be considered, such as the number of biosensors they incorporate, the security they apply to the data, or the physical characteristics of durability and permeability.

5.5.6.1. Tracking

When a crisis strikes, especially when it is about a multi-victim incident, emergency responders carry out tasks such as search and rescue, recovery, and clean-up. Several frameworks have been proposed and developed for ensuring emergency responders' safety and health integrity by tracking their location and monitoring their vital signs using wireless wearable devices. Novel wireless wearable tracking and monitoring systems utilize iterative localization-based approaches to provide the exact position of each responder and monitor vital signs like skin temperature, heart rate, blood oxygen level, etc. Any change in vital signs may be effectively noticed and tracked by biomedical sensors, and this information might be used to provide early warnings both inside and outside of key-events occurrences. Such systems can be used to send out early warning warnings and allow emergency personnel to better communicate with one another in the field.

By using localized nodes, the localization approaches predict the location and the distance between neighboring emergency responders. Because network traffic is limited to only those emergency responders who are within communication range, distance estimation can operate efficiently, considerably lowering network traffic. The location information of the emergency responders can be easily tracked by employing such quick and effective localization techniques.

Such systems can play a key-role in the achievement of main goals towards providing emergency responders with a cost-effective and care-efficient context aware monitoring solution, which are cost-effective and use little power when compared to its operation, and it is simple to implement from a hardware point of view. Therefore, approaches like these aids disaster relief efforts while also ensuring the safety of emergency personnel that operate in the field (238).

5.5.6.2. Connectivity

As described before, wearable devices can perform several important functions in the context of a mission. However, their utility and application's domain depend on their ability to connect and exchange data with other components and systems. Wearable devices need to be lightweight and small, thus have inherently limited capabilities on processing power and operational autonomy. In what concerns communications, this constrains them to rely on low power protocols exhibiting limited data rate, limited range or both.

Several technologies are available for connecting wearable devices, where a brief list of the most common is presented herein:

Personal Area Network (PAN)

A PAN is a network of interconnected devices within a person's area (i.e., a few meters). For example, a PAN can be used to connect a smart watch, body sensors (e.g., medical devices) and a head mounted display. Typically, a gateway solution is then used to transmit data gathered in a PAN to a larger network.

Connecting devices in a PAN can consist of wired connections (e.g., USB and I2C) and wireless connections (e.g., Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) and ZigBee).

Low-Power Wide-Area Network (LPWAN)

A LPWAN is a wireless network of connected devices operating over large distances (i.e., several kms) however, being designed for low power, supports low data rates (order of few kbps).

A LPWAN can be used to connect deployed devices (e.g., RF detector) and responder gateways to remote control centres.

Common protocols include "long range" (LoRa) and Wize.

Infrastructure-based

Wearable devices can also directly connect to infrastructure-based networks, following the principles of the Internet-of-Things, not requiring gateway solutions as intermediary components.

VALKYRIES considers widely used networks like local Wi-Fi (thus depending on a local Wi-Fi access point within communications range) and cellular (4G or 5G). These networks provide high data rates, however their power requirements are higher than for PAN and LPWAN.

Passive Mode: Radio-frequency identification (RFID)

Wearable devices should also support RFID to support automatic identification and tracking. An example consists of a patient bracelet tag that is used to identify a victim of a MCI.

A device should contain passive RFID "tags" that are powered by RFID interrogation devices. When interrogated, the device tag responds by transmitting data containing its identification.

The use of RFID is important to maintain minimal required functions even if the device battery has been fully depleted.

Table 52 summarises common communications technologies recommended for wearable devices to be used in VALKYRIES, together with their characteristics.

Characteristics	BLE	LoRa	4G/5G	Wi-Fi	RFID
Dependence on infrastructure	No	No	Yes	(*)	No
Congestion control	Partial	Partial	Yes	Yes	No
Quality of Service	Partial	No	Yes	Partial	No
Mobility	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partial	No
Inter-operability and heterogeneity	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Security and privacy	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Robustness and flexibility	Yes	Yes	Partial	Yes	No
Data transfer rate	Low	Low	Medium, High	Medium High	Low
Power requirements	Low	Low	High	Medium	N/A

(*) In the context of wearables, a Wi-Fi access point (AP) should exist providing a local network to where wearable can connect to.

Table 52 - Common communications technologies for wearable devices

5.5.6.3. Others

Other characteristics of such devices need to be considered when selecting one for a particular purpose. Some of these parameters are, if it allows user tracking, as it is one of the main ones that need to be supplied. On the other hand, some factors such as the connectivity they offer, the toughness against adverse elements in this type of situation, or the security they implement for the type of data they process, must be taken into account.

Signals

All the above-mentioned wearables: smartwatches, fitness trackers, smart clothing, etc. Have a communications module to transmit the data obtained: temperature, positioning, EEG (electroencephalogram), ECG (electrocardiogram), SpO2 (blood oxygen level). Due to their small size, they use a short-range transmission technology, typically Bluetooth 5.1. Low space requirement and low power consumption. In some cases, they may have Wi-Fi connectivity or an internet of things (IoT) communication protocol (Zigbee or Z-Wave). To have global communication, all these wearables need to be linked to a mobile phone.

The mobile phone, using GSM technology (Global System for Mobile Communications) compatible with 2G, 3G, 4G and in the future 5G, provides the necessary connectivity, but, perhaps, does not provide the security needed for an emergency system. The data channel in 4G mobile communications is shared among all users connected to the same antenna that provides coverage. This means the following: if many users accumulate in one place, access to data may be temporarily limited. In the case of emergency communications, this would not be acceptable. The GSM mobile telephony standard reserves a specific bandwidth for railway communications: GSM-R (GSM-Railway). Perhaps, the data generated by these wearables should use a specific and secure bandwidth.

Data Security

For wearable devices, data security is critical. Wearable gadgets can be hacked in close proximity by utilizing sound waves to tamper with the legitimacy of health data, or even used to compromise the position of key military locations via a publicly available heat map.

The most frequent vulnerabilities of these wearable devices are:

1. Inadequate authentication: Wearable gadgets are frequently shipped without built-in security mechanisms, such as user authentication or PIN system protection.
2. No encryption: Wearable data is extremely important, but some third-party apps fail to follow basic security guidelines and communicate or store information that isn't secured.
3. Insecure wireless internet access: Bluetooth, NFC, and WiFi protocols are used to link wearable gadgets to smartphones wirelessly. However, against persistent hackers, the security of these wireless channels may be insufficient.
4. Insecure cloud infrastructure: Data synchronized to cloud storage is also exposed to risks including distributed denial of service (DDoS), SQL injection, back door assaults, and other threats.

If no proper care is taken, these flaws can pose a point of entry for attackers who can use valid company credentials or medical records to steal sensitive data or demand a ransom. Wearable device privacy and security should be built in rather than an afterthought, so it's critical to choose gadgets that are developed with a "security by design" approach. Some important steps towards that, are:

1. Ascertain that the equipment is capable of defending itself. This means that manufacturers should include security features such as secure boot, secure chipsets, and secure data storage functions in their devices.
2. Create a system for detecting and isolating harmful devices. Manufacturers could strengthen device weaknesses by including built-in encryption and authentication features, as well as adopting whitelist and blacklist policies to regulate data flows.
3. Provide a method for updating firmware and applications. This gives a means to update the devices in the field to withstand future attacks when a security flaw is discovered.
4. Assert a "security-by-design" strategy. Manufacturers should adopt the mindset that security should be built into the design process so that vulnerabilities are identified, and hazards are mitigated before they occur. Furthermore, manufacturers who use a security-by-design approach simulate vulnerabilities early in the device development process, allowing them to be addressed proactively rather than reactively.

Although many of the security challenges surrounding wearables should be addressed during the design stage, choosing a design team with experience and competence in this area is crucial. The very same applies for teams that conduct market research, to avoid the purchasing and adoption of vulnerable solutions that could compromise or even endanger critical processes, like those involved in crisis management.

Physical Characteristics

Wearables must continue to function in extreme environments; therefore, they must be protected against:

- Dust
- Water
- External mechanical impacts

According to IEC 60529 Nomenclature, these wearables should have, at least, an IP57 protection rating, which means: dust must not enter in such a quantity as to interfere with the proper functioning of the equipment, and they must withstand, without any leakage, full immersion at 1 meter for 30 minutes.

According to IEC 62262 Nomenclature, these wearables should have, at least, an IK06, which means: it must withstand impacts of 1 Joule of energy.

5.5.7. Analysis of T4.5 questionnaire

This last section of the survey presents the most relevant aspects surveyed from first responders regarding task 4.5:

- Desired functionality of wearables (e.g., smart watch) for emergency situations
- Usefulness of wearables during first triage in emergency situations
- Essential biosignals for first triage
- Wearables used comply with medical regulations (e.g., FDA)
- Necessary or desirables aspects to better identify or locate a victim in a first triage (e.g., visual indicators, sounds)
- Convenience of presenting the patient status on the screen of the wearable (e.g., a bright color indicating the status)
- Usefulness of a system that, using wearables in patients during first triage, suggest the best prioritization for patients' care
- Existing policies or guidelines in emergency situations for first responders regarding the maximum number of working hours and their resting periods
- Convenience of wearables measuring and showing the stress level of first responders during emergency actuations
- Current integration with existing technological solutions (e.g., smartphones, tablets or mobile applications)

Based on these aspects, the following table contains the most common answers for each of the previous topics.

	Most common answer in the Survey
Desired functionality of wearables for emergency situations.	Geolocation, vital signs
Usefulness of wearables during first triage in emergency situations.	Yes
Essential biosignals for first triage.	Movement sensor, heart rate, SpO2, blood pressure, consciousness, reaction to pain
Wearables used comply with medical regulations (e.g., FDA).	No use of wearables

	Most common answer in the Survey
Necessary or desirables aspects to better identify or locate a victim in a first triage.	Visual preferred, sound useful depending on the situation
Convenience of presenting the patient status on the screen of the wearable (e.g., a bright color indicating the status).	Yes
Usefulness of a system that, using wearables in patients during first triage, suggest the best prioritization for patients' care.	Yes, No
Existing policies or guidelines in emergency situations for first responders regarding the maximum number of working hours and their resting periods.	Yes, No
Convenience of wearables measuring and showing the stress level of first responders during emergency actuations.	Yes, No
Current integration with existing technological solutions (e.g., smartphones, tablets or mobile applications).	Bluetooth, NFC, WiFi

Table 53 - Results obtained for Task 4.5

Based on the previous answers, consulted organisations agreed about the relevance of the use of wearables in patients during first triage. Additionally, they identify those wearables could help for providing essential medical aspects of patients regarding biosignals. However, although they indicate that they could be useful, none of these entities use them. Based on that, this generates a great opportunity for harmonisation and digitalisation.

6. Legal barriers and ethical concerns

Ethical legal barrier can be addressed developing an impact assessment aiming to firstly detect possible concerns, and then to identify possible mitigation measures to be implemented by design and by default.

The ethical legal framework consists of a series of EU binding legislative initiatives and soft law tools aiming to develop a risk-based approach towards the flows of shared information. In particular, the GDPR provides the conditions to process personal data, while the EU Regulation n. 2018/1807 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union aims at boosting the free movement of non-personal data between different EU countries and IT systems in Europe, by removing obstacles and creating incentives for making data available at least in the public sectors.

These two described regulatory initiatives define the European Data Strategy, that is currently enriched by the proposals of Data Governance Act COM (2020) 767 final, aiming to make public sector data available for re-use, providing also conditions to share data under altruistic grounds; and the so-called Data Act, aiming to harmonise rules on fair access to and use of data either in private sector or public services.

The compliance with this complex regulatory system creates the basis to develop VALKYRIES solutions with an accountable approach, flexible to possible national constrains and additive conditions imposed by circumstances / cross-border scenarios / sectorial legislation and at the same time it allows to address ethical issues in a wider perspective, meeting not only binding requirements but also ethical principles internationally recognized. In fact, the impact assessment deals with personal data flows under article 35 GDPR, but the human-centric approach towards new data-driven technologies emerging from the mentioned initiatives boosts an analysis under all the involved fundamental rights. To this end, legal barriers and ethical concerns have been addressed as follows.

- **Data Management.** From a methodological viewpoint, the development of a Data Management Plan illustrating how data flows are generated and processed is the first step to identify critical steps in a data driven ecosystem.
- **Data protection compliance.** Personal data flows shall meet the requirements established under GDPR and in particular, shall comply with principles stated under article 5 (i.e principles of minimization, purpose limitation, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity and confidentiality). To this end, appropriate safeguards like encryption of flows and pseudo-anonymization techniques are implemented to enable the processing of personal data within the boundaries of lawfulness, fairness and accountability. In particular, the communication of personal data shall be developed by design enabling it only if necessary and essential to the identified purposes and between authorised organizations and trained staff.
- **Vulnerable data subjects.** Another ground of assessment is related to the vulnerability(ies) of data subjects. In the emergency scenarios, in fact, information generally refers to (at least) temporarily vulnerable persons. In addition, the level of vulnerability could be extended if we consider possible previous conditions of the victims. Therefore, data subjects could be victims of the event or relatives of victims, and at the same time they could also become patients (as they may report injuries), and/ or they could be minors, persons belonging to linguistic, socio-economic, ethnical etc minorities. These circumstances impose

to analyse the possible impact on fundamental rights including the identification of specific safeguards to address multiple vulnerabilities. Considering the involvement of first responders as users of the developed technology, the communication system shall be interoperable with healthcare services, without exposing -however- information to unauthorised or unlawful access / processing.

- Non-personal data flows. Non-personal data shall be processed considering both the standards adopted for personal data flows that need to be maintained to protect the whole communication system in order to avoid security flaws and possible limits identified to prevent any risk of misuse / dual use of information generated in the system.
- Acceptability and Usability. Another ground of assessment deals with the necessity to guarantee the system acceptability and usability by first responders. In this regard, the development of tailored training activities providing new skills and competence, including supervision roles respect to the digital solutions will facilitate the introduction of the system in the given supply chain.

7. Conclusions

7.1. WP4 conclusion

There is a considerable number of technologies applicable nowadays to emergency scenarios, although their purposes are diverse, being applicable in different scenarios or situations. Moreover, these technologies may have limitations based on the situation, especially when there are coverage restrictions or the infrastructure is disrupted, in situations such as natural disasters or terrorist attacks. Thus, the analysis provided in this deliverable intends to evaluate the current status of technological solutions applied to emergency scenarios, aiming to later detect gaps and, thus, opportunities for improvement.

7.2. Task conclusions

7.2.1. First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units

We have made an overview of possible units suitable for first aid responders as well as other responders (In some cases they will most likely be at the site before first aid responders). An example could be an accident at sea where other nearby ships will be the first response team, then most likely the coast guard, a sea rescue team or a rescue helicopter (They often carry medical personnel).

A questionnaire is out and results are collected nearly every day. We have also conducted 6 in-depth interviews and a complete analysis and report will come in the next period. We are testing a number of different vehicles and will report on this in the autumn.

7.2.2. Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals

This task has been to identify which existing technologies provide reliable communications to improve current EU first responder capabilities. This analysis has identified gaps, challenges and regulatory barriers to adoption, resulting in a set of current and promising future opportunities. From this set, security measures at the level of secure communication protocols and what technologies provide in this regard have been analysed. It has been detected that current communication technologies are quite varied, and it depends on the characteristics of the scenario and how well they work (in terms of functionality and security provided).

For example, in Spain, we were fortunate enough to witness a multi-casualty incident and visit the ECC in the community of Madrid. As a result, there is no extensive use of communication technologies that could ensure faster action by Firefighters, Civil Protection, Health Services, etc. and the Madrid emergency coordination center (M112).

We are fully aware of the need for a robust communications scheme between network entities. The current amount of technology and the identification of new markets for support to first responders in multi-victim incidents is more than enough to improve the current performance.

7.2.3. Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies

The scope of this task has been to identify which technologies will be deployed by the emergency services of the countries present in the consortium to mitigate the negative effects of a multi-casualty incident.

Solutions for current C&C applications are very limited. For example, in Spain, we were fortunate enough to witness a multi-victim incident and to visit the ECC of the community of Madrid. As a

result, there is no software integration among the organisations such as Firefighter, Civil Protection, Health services, etc. and the emergency coordination centre of Madrid (M112). Indeed, the problem is maximised if we extrapolate the interoperability constraints at European scale. The only data gateway between countries is through the telephone.

Interoperability standards do exist at the European level for geographic information systems and at the operational level. In terms of standards, EU countries have protocols and tools in order to digitise many of the actions. However, each country has limited resources. Moreover, the deployment of resources is very arbitrary depending on the scope of the incident, the location of the incident, the date of the incident and the countries affected.

We are fully conscious of the fact that we are in an era of constant digitalisation. The flow of information between organisations has to become more frequent and shall easier to resolve through technologies that provides for a secure exchange of data. With this data crossover, tools for data processing and exploitation will be crucial to identify emerging needs to support first responders in multi-victim incidents.

7.2.4. The digitalisation on first aid actuations

The aim for this task 4.4 was to explore the capabilities and benefits that the digitalization of the first aid actuations could offer.

The application of digitalization capabilities in the context of emergency actuations is a disruptive technique yet to be explored, thus the current applications are almost inexistent. Furthermore, these applications are not restricted as emergency support, as they are promising solutions for educational and training purposes.

Keeping in mind the current digital potential and the fact that we live in the era of the digitalization, it is highly recommended to integrate these capabilities in the current workflow to support first responders in multiple dimensions.

7.2.5. Instrumentation and health support wearable devices

After the landscape on the possible solutions that currently exist for wearable devices, the technology is very advanced in terms of wearable devices. These devices can facilitate and speeding up the task of first responders in both triage and C&C aspects. For this, we have studied the solutions offered by the different types of wearable devices that exist today, and which would be the priority functionalities that first responders would need. Based on this, a search was carried out of the technologies that exist today to solve these problems.

However, it has been identified that although the devices are very capable of carrying out the necessary tasks, the majority of first responders do not use this type of device. This is mainly due to the lack of infrastructure for their use, and the need for a universal method that works in any type of environment, even when there is no coverage.

Because of this, wearable devices are elements that soon will be incorporated into the tasks of first responders to facilitate and coordinate MCIs.

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9. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
ADPCM	Adaptive differential pulse-code modulation
AGPS	Assisted Global Positioning System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	automatic identification system
ALS	Airborne Laser Scanning
ANSI	American National Standards Institute
API	Application programming interfaces
AR	Augmented Reality
ASW	Automatic Speech Recognition
AVL	Automatic Vehicle Locator
BI	Business Intelligence
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
BRMS	Business Rules Management System
C&C	Command and Control
C2	Command and Control
C3ISR	Command, Control, Communication, Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
COP	Common Operational Picture
COPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
CORP	Common Operational Relevant Picture
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSS3	Cascading Style Sheets Level 3
DCT	Discrete Cosine Transform
DGPS	Differential Global Positioning System
DM	Data Mart
DRL	Drools Rule Language
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
DVD	Digital Video Disc
ECG	Electrocardiogram
EDO	European Drought Observatory
EFAS	European Flood Awareness System
EFFIS	European Forest Information System
ELT	Extract, Load, Transform
EMS	Emergency Management Service
EO	Electro-optical sensors
ETL	Extract, Transform and Load
FAW	Fusion Analytics Warehouse
GDO	Global Drought Observatory

Acronym	Description
GDPR	General Framework of the Data Protection Regulation
GEO	Geostationary Orbit
GI&T	Geographic Information and Technology
GIS	Geographic Information System
GloGAS	Global Flood Awareness System
GMES	Global Monitoring for Environment and Security
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSCP	General Secretariat for Civil Protection
GSDIs	Global Spatial Data Infrastructure
GSO	Geosynchronous orbit
GvSIG	Generalitat Valenciana Geographic Information System
GWIS	Global Wildfire Information System
HAPS	High-altitude platform station
HD	High Definition
HEO	Highly Elliptical Orbit
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language (HTML)
IAS	International AIDS Society
ICH	International Council for Harmonisation
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
IR	Infrared
iSIM	Integrated Subscriber Identity Module
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
KES	KIE Execution Server
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KWB	Business Central Workbench
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
LGPL	Lesser General Public License
LPC	Linear predictive coding
LRF	Laser Range Finder
LRIT	Long-Range Identification and Tracking
LWIR	Long-wave infrared
MDCT	Modified Discrete Cosine Transformation
MDG	Master Data Governance
MDX	Multidimensional Expressions
MEO	Medium Earth Orbit
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MON	Message-Oriented Middleware
MPEG	Moving Picture Experts Group
MWIR	Mid-Waved Infrared sub-band

Acronym	Description
NEC	Biometric Personal identification
NFC	Near Field Communication
NHS	National Health Service
NIR	Near-infrared
NIS	Natural and Industrial System
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
NSDI	National Spatial Data Infrastructure
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OLAP	On-Line Analytical Processing systems
OLTP	On-Line Transactional Processing systems
OODA	Observe, Orient, Decide, Act
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
PC	Personal Computer
PDI	Pentaho Data Integration
PEST	Political Economical Sociological Technological
Ph	Potential of Hydrogen
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
POI	Point Of Interest
Q&A	Questions and Answers
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RGB	Red, Green and Blue
RSS	Really Simple Syndication
RVLC	Reversible Variable Length Coding
SA	Situational Awareness
SaR	Search and Rescue
SAR	Synthetic-aperture radar
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructure
SEVIRI	Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager
SIGINT	Signals of Intelligence
SOA	Services based Architecture
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SSDT	Server Data Tools
SSO	Sun-synchronous Orbit
SWIR	Short-wave infrared
SWMS	Safe Work Method Statement
SWOT	Strengths Weaknesses Opportunities Threats
TVF	Trusted Verification Function
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
UI	User Interface
USB	Universal Serial Bus
VHR	Very High Resolution
VIS	Visible Image Size
VoIP	Voice over IP
Vos	Video Objects

Acronym	Description
VR	Virtual Reality
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Feature Service
WiFi	Wireless Fidelity
WMS	Web Map Service
XML	Extensible Markup Language
RPAS	Remote Piloted Aircraft System
VLOS	Visible Line of sight
BVLOS	Beyond VLOS
FPV	First Person View
AGL	Above Ground Level
AMSL	Above Mean Sea Level
NOTAM	Notice To Airmen
ConOps	Concepts of Operation
ATC	Air Traffic Control
OM	Operation Manual
NSM	Nasjonal Sikkerhetsmyndighet
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft System
UAV	Unmanned Aircraft Vehicle

Table 54 - Glossary

10. Annex C - WP4 questionnaire

To obtain a complete landscape of the current technological situation in Europe, a questionnaire was carried out with first responders to find out about certain issues related to T4.2, T4.3, T4.4 and T4.5. For this purpose, the questionnaire first asked for the country of origin of the organization responding to the questionnaire. Nine organizations responded to this questionnaire, distributed among countries as follows:

Figure 104 - Country participation in the questionnaire

As can be seen, there is a homogeneous representation from first responders in different countries of Europe. Additionally, they have been asked about the role they perform in an emergency incident. From these nine entities, two of them were medical institutions and two were dedicated to fire control and rescue services. Additionally, four entities were dedicated to emergency coordination and management, being the one remaining focused on incident analysis and report.

After depicting the distribution of institutions between countries, this section subsequently presents the key aspects consulted for each of the tasks previously discussed, also presenting the most common answers per question. This aims to easily understand the results of the questionnaire and to get an understanding of the current technological landscape in relevant first responder organisations in Europe. Finally, a summary for each task is presented, indicating the conclusions obtained from the previous responses, highlighting the needs that these entities have, aiming to align them with the objectives of the Valkyries project.

10.1. Task 4.1 Questions

1. Describe your most common tasks as a first responder
2. In transport – towards a mission – describe how you receive information:
 - a. What kind of information is provided?
 - b. Communication/technological tools in use?
 - c. What is the role of leaders in this phase?
3. During operation as a first responder – Describe how you receive information
 - a. What kind of information is provided?
 - b. Communication/technological tools in use?
 - c. What is the role of leaders in this phase?

4. Can you draw a sketch of the lines of command and of communication during operation? (Provide pen/paper)
5. In operation – what communication technologies is in use? Drones? Pictures? Text? Verbal?
6. Any need of changes in operation as first responder – more or less information?
7. Have you experienced when there has been information overflow?
8. How do you communicate also with positional data to command centre?
9. Any forthcoming innovation on technology?
10. Something you would like to add?

10.2. Task 4.2 Questions

1. Do you implement security measurements during the transmission of communication in emergency situations? For example, the use of methods or protocols for secure transmission such as VPN, HTTPS, IPSec or proxys.
2. In emergency situations with a dramatic limitation of network capabilities, do you consider the option of transmitting information without security capabilities? That is to say, those situations where you require a prioritization of the transmission of information over its protection.
3. Is there a priority by authorities or first responders when sending data?
4. Which privacy constraints or data protection regulations apply in your country?
5. What vehicles or elements do you have available to increase coverage in real scenarios?
6. Do your security systems include systems such as IDS, firewalls or honeypots?
7. What communication technologies do you use and in which contexts? For example, TETRA, mobile networks (2G, 3G, 4G, 5G), Wi-Fi, ad-hoc communications, satellite communications or wired communications.
8. Which are the limitations identified in the usage of the previously indicated technologies based on your experience? For example, network coverage issues, limitations in data transfer rates, or similar.
9. Are satellite networks used for purposes other than geolocation in emergencies? If so, what availability of satellites exist to be used for emergencies, and what are the limitations that you have detected?
10. Are ad-hoc systems currently used to overcome coverage problems with traditional technologies, such as drones or air balloons? If that is not the case, do you consider them relevant?
11. Do you consider the application of emergent communication technologies such as LPWAN technologies or D2D communications?
12. Using repeaters (e.g., TETRA repeaters) in zones without network coverage is enough for operating in a reduced space, such as a certain building or zone? Using a TETRA gateway to connect terminals with the network infrastructure is an acceptable solution? What are the limitations in the real field based on your experience?
13. Is it feasible to deploy additional antennas to provide wide coverage in rural or adverse areas during an emergency? Do you experience huge differences between offering connectivity in a metropolitan area compared to rural ones? Are there specific organisms in your country in charge of these tasks?

10.3. Task 4.3 Questions

1. Which is your infrastructure of your Incident Command Post? (Rack, Servers, Equipment, etc)
2. Is the infrastructure of your components and terminals prepared to operate in heavy humidity conditions, et? Any regulations?
3. Which C&C Communication technologies do you use, supported by you C&C application? (Tetra, xG, etc)
4. Which capabilities shall support the Geographical Information System?
5. Why do you consider that the GIS tool could be advantageous for increasing the situational awareness of emergency coordinators in a cross-border multiple victim incident?
6. In which way are social networks integrated with your geographic information system?
7. Which digital formatted (Vectorial / Raster) is running on your GIS and for what kind of information it is used?
8. Do you have any tri-dimensional representational tool (3D GIS)? (for example: DEM: Digital Elevation Model)
9. Which Database system is supported by your GIS?
10. Is it your GIS (or any additional services from your GIS tool) open source (free of charge) software?
11. Which localization systems it is using by your C&C?
12. Which issues did you find regarding your location systems?
13. Is C&C application using any vehicle or people localization system in order to linked Emergency Vehicles or First responders?
14. Video - Which compression techniques are installed in your C&C application?
15. Audio - Which compression techniques are installed in your C&C application?
16. Are any modern encryption technology carries out in your C&C application?
17. Which information will be mandatory
18. In order to enhance the personnel adaptability, operational decision making and course of action planning, which tools are you using in your C&C application? (Big Data analytics, advanced simulation environments, etc)
19. Any back-up storage is provided in your C&C System? In affirmative case, which technology is been using? (Messaging Broker (Kafka, RabbitMQ, etc))
20. How do you synchronize your databases between the application from your Incident command post (truck, etc) and your application from your Base command post (112 - Coordination command post)?
21. What information will be essential to share with other agencies in a cross-border multiple victim incident?
22. Any back-up storage is provided in your C&C System? In affirmative case, which technology is been using?
23. Which technology do you use in order to link external sensoristic integration data?
24. Is it multiplatform C&C application? It is able to run on different OS. Do you consider web based is a must for this kinds of applications?
25. Is your C&C application able to access, processing and store signals and images / maps, IRS integration systems, security, etc. in cloud?
26. How do you manage the critical infrastructures on GIS?

27. Is there any C&C Application able to interconnect applications between different agencies?

10.4. Task 4.4 Questions

1. Which application being used by first responders offers a real-time representation of emergencies (if any)?
2. Would you consider useful the AI support on emergency situations (e.g.. optimal evacuation routes, priority of evacuations)?
3. In an emergency with multiple victims, do you think it is of vital importance that all actors in positions of responsibility are getting the same information? Do you consider it operational to set up a virtual crisis room where the entire conflict is managed in addition to the forward command post?
4. Do you consider the digital literacy level of first responders enough to face the digitalization of emergency actuations?
5. Do the first responders use any kind of wearable to track their actions or monitor their status during actuations or training activities?
6. Do you use any kind of digital support for educational or training activities?
7. Would you consider useful the use of virtual reality (e.g. VR headset) for educational or training purposes?
8. Would you consider useful the use of virtual reality (e.g. reality glasses) for emergency actuations?
9. Would you consider useful the use virtual events for simulacrum purposes?
10. Is there any other educational purpose to be identified?
11. Are the trainings/simulations/educational activities results stored in order to evaluate the progress of the first responders?

10.5. Task 4.5 Questions

1. What is the desired functionality of wearables (e.g., smart watch) that it would be relevant in emergency situations for you? For example, to get information about the heart rate of a patient or the geolocation.
2. Would it be interesting that wearables are used during the first triage in an emergency situation?
3. In case of considering biosignals, which would be essential for a first triage?
4. If you use wearables, do they complain with medical regulations such as FDA? What device or model do you use? Are they proprietary or for commercial use?
5. What is necessary or desirable to better identify or locate a victim in a first triage? For example, visual indicators or sounds.
6. Would it be relevant that wearables continuously present the patient status on screen? For example, to display a bright red light if the patient's status is critical.
7. Would it be useful a system that, using wearables in patients during first triage, suggests the best prioritization for patients' care?
8. Are there policies or guidelines in emergency situations for first responders regarding the maximum number of working hours and their resting periods?
9. Would it be interesting that wearables measure and show the stress level of first responders during emergency actuations?
10. How do you integrate wearables with existing technological solutions, such as smartphones, tablets, or mobile applications?

